

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Annex to Deliverable D4.1: Cluster profiles analysis

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Introduction

This annex presents the full set of cluster profiles developed as part of the ECHOES consultation analysis. Each profile represents a distinct community configuration identified through the systematic analysis of survey responses, combining socio-professional characteristics, data practices and technological engagement.

The profiles are not intended as rigid or mutually exclusive categories. Rather, they capture recurring patterns across the dataset, reflecting how different groups of users interact with cultural heritage data, tools and infrastructures. As such, they should be understood as analytical constructs that support the interpretation of the consultation results and the identification of user needs.

The development of the profiles is grounded in a structured mapping of survey variables covering multiple dimensions, including professional positioning, data production processes, documentation practices, technological adoption, data management and sharing behaviours, and expectations towards digital tools and services . These dimensions have been analysed in combination in order to identify coherent configurations of practices and constraints across the dataset.

For each cluster, a dedicated profile document has been produced. These documents provide:

- a description of the profile and its defining characteristics
- a summary of key findings across the main thematic areas of the consultation
- an interpretation of practices, challenges and expectations
- a comparative analytical framing based on selected cross-cutting dimensions (digital maturity, governance, infrastructure and collaboration)

Not all analytical dimensions are available for every profile, as their inclusion depends on the availability and relevance of specific variables within each configuration. Where applicable, these dimensions support a more in-depth interpretation of how practices are structured and how they relate to broader systemic conditions.

Taken together, the profiles provide a detailed and nuanced representation of the diversity of communities engaged in digital cultural heritage. They constitute a key analytical component of the Atlas of Communities, supporting the identification of user requirements, the design of services and the development of targeted engagement and capacity-building strategies within the ECHOES project.

Cluster Profiles Analysis

Profile: Academia and Research

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

A1.3. What is your level of education?

- Bachelor
- Masters
- Doctorate

A2. What is your current working status?

- Employed
- Student
- Other

A4. Do you work for:

- A private non-profit organisation
- A public non-profit organisation

A5. What type of institution / organisation / company do you work for?

- University, research institute or research infrastructure

A6 Field of professional activity:

- Research in Social Sciences and Humanities
- Science Engineering and Applied Research
- Other (research)

A8. Are you involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or any other project relevant to the Cultural Heritage Cloud?

- National
- European
- International

Base: 108 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Academia and Research* profile includes respondents with higher education qualifications (Bachelor, Master's or Doctorate) who are either employed, students or engaged in other professional activities within academic environments. They work primarily in universities, research institutes or research infrastructures, typically within public or private non-profit organisations. Their professional activities span a wide range

of disciplinary areas, including research in the Social Sciences and Humanities, Science, Engineering and Applied Research, as well as other research-related domains.

Many respondents are also involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or initiatives connected to the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Overall, this profile represents professionals engaged in academic research, education and training—from lecturers and professors to doctoral students and researchers—who contribute to knowledge production, interdisciplinary collaboration and the development of cultural heritage as a field of study and innovation.

Summary of findings

Tools and services

The technological configuration of the Academia and Research profile reflects a relatively broad engagement with digital tools, although adoption levels vary across analytical, spatial and data management domains.

In the area of annotation and analytical tools, manual annotation of digital assets represents the most widespread practice, reported by 40.7% of respondents. Automated analytical approaches remain more limited: automated content analysis tools reach 17.6%, while Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) reach 14.8%. Automatic shape or texture recognition tools remain less common (10.2%). At the same time, 16.7% report not using annotation or analysis tools.

Spatial and visualisation technologies show a differentiated but significant level of engagement. Tools for 3D scanning, modelling, rendering and reconstruction are reported by 45.4% of respondents, followed by Geographic Information Systems (GIS) at 38.9%. Immersive environments such as Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality and Mixed Reality reach 29.6%, while LiDAR technologies reach 19.4% and BIM/HBIM tools 17.6%. Nevertheless, 40.7% indicate that they do not currently use 3D or spatial technologies.

Engagement with data management infrastructures (*Figure 1.1*) appears relatively consolidated.

C1.3b. What data management and storage tools or services do you use or would like to use?	Count	%
Data collection, management and structuring	43	39.8%
Resource storage and retrieval systems	23	21.3%
Data interoperability and API integration	21	19.4%
Answered "No" to C1.3a. Are you using data management and storage tools or services?	21	19.4%

Figure 1.1 Use of data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

Tools for data collection management and structuring are reported by 39.8% of respondents, while resource storage and retrieval systems reach 21.3% and

interoperability or API integration tools reach 19.4%. However, nearly one fifth of respondents (19.4%) report not using data management tools.

The use of formal knowledge representation tools is more selective. Knowledge graphs and linked data technologies are used or considered by 31.5% of respondents, while taxonomies and controlled vocabularies reach 14.8% and ontologies 9.3%. At the same time, 44.4% report not using formal knowledge representation tools.

Overall, the technological configuration of the Academia and Research profile suggests a balanced engagement with analytical and spatial tools, accompanied by a moderate but not universal adoption of structured data management and semantic technologies.

Access models and authentication

Access to digital tools and services within the Academia and Research profile is predominantly structured around open and institutionally mediated environments, while commercial and hybrid models coexist within the same ecosystem (*Figure 1.2*).

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	92	85.2%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	63	58.3%
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	47	43.5%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	38	35.2%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	29	26.9%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	27	25.0%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	15	13.9%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	5	4.6%

Figure 1.2 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4)

Free, open-access services represent by far the most widespread configuration, reported by 85.2% of respondents. Open-source software is also widely adopted, reaching 58.3% of the profile. Hybrid access configurations are common as well: 43.5% report using services that are free with a licence or optional paid features. Commercial models remain present but less dominant, with paid licence-based services used by 26.9% of respondents and subscription-based services by 25.0%. Trial-based access appears more limited (13.9%), while pay-per-use models remain marginal (4.6%). At the same time, 35.2% report relying on in-house or custom-built tools developed within their own organisations.

Authentication practices reflect the strong institutional anchoring typical of academic environments. Institutional login systems represent the most common method, used by

81.5% of respondents. Commercial identity providers also play an important role, particularly Google-based authentication (50.0%). Research-oriented identifiers are also relatively prominent, with ORCID used by 40.7% of respondents, while Microsoft accounts reach 26.9%. Other authentication systems, including enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions (14.8%), remain less widespread, alongside EU Login, Apple ID and social media accounts.

Taken together, these patterns suggest that researchers operate within hybrid access environments combining open infrastructures, institutionally managed systems and widely used commercial platforms, with institutional authentication mechanisms playing a central role in mediating access to digital research tools and services.

Objectives of tool use

The objectives guiding the use of digital tools within the Academia and Research profile are primarily oriented towards scientific investigation and knowledge production (*Figure 1.3*).

C5. What are your main objectives when using the tools?	Count	%
Scientific research and knowledge production	21	44,7%
Data analysis, modelling and machine learning	10	21,3%
Data management, organisation and storage	8	17,0%
Data visualisation and interpretation	7	14,9%
Digital documentation, annotation and text processing	6	12,8%
Access, discovery and retrieval of information	6	12,8%
Dissemination, communication and public engagement	5	10,6%
Heritage preservation and conservation	4	8,5%
Automation and efficiency of workflows	4	8,5%
Collaboration and knowledge sharing	3	6,4%

Figure 1.3 Main objectives in the use of digital tools (C5)

The most frequently reported objective concerns scientific research and knowledge production (44.7%), indicating that digital tools are mainly used to support the formulation of research questions, the analysis of cultural heritage data and the generation of new scholarly insights.

Computational and analytical uses also play a relevant role. Data analysis, modelling and machine learning are mentioned by 21.3% of respondents, while 17.0% highlight the use of tools for data management, organisation and storage. Data visualisation and interpretation are reported by 14.9%, and tools supporting digital documentation, annotation and text processing or information discovery and retrieval are each mentioned by 12.8%.

Other objectives reflect broader scholarly and operational functions, including dissemination and public communication (10.6%), heritage preservation and conservation (8.5%), workflow automation and efficiency (8.5%), and collaboration or knowledge sharing (6.4%).

Overall, digital tools appear to be primarily mobilised to support research and analytical activities, while also facilitating the organisation, interpretation and dissemination of cultural heritage data.

Data production processes and objectives

Data production within the Academia and Research profile is strongly oriented towards the generation of knowledge and the support of scholarly investigation (*Figure 1.4*).

D2. What are the primary objectives of producing data in your work?	Count	%
Answering research questions (e.g., contributing to academic or scientific studies, such as material characterisation, provenance study, etc.)	92	85,2%
Developing educational materials (e.g., creating resources for teaching or training)	57	52,8%
Public communication or awareness (e.g., sharing findings with a general audience)	50	46,3%
Archiving or preserving information (e.g., maintaining records for future reference)	47	43,5%
Preparing reports (e.g., internal reports, technical documentation, or project summaries)	44	40,7%
Cataloguing information (e.g., metadata creation for management or reporting purposes)	41	38,0%
Creating conservation or restoration plans (e.g., documenting objects for heritage preservation, condition reports)	27	25,0%
Supporting decision-making (e.g., providing insights for strategic planning or policy-making)	27	25,0%
Monitoring and evaluation (e.g., tracking progress or assessing impact)	25	23,1%

Figure 1.4 Primary objectives of data production (D2)

The vast majority of respondents (85.2%) report producing data primarily to answer research questions, confirming the central role of data creation in academic research activities.

At the same time, data production also supports a range of complementary academic and professional functions. Over half of respondents (52.8%) indicate that data are produced to develop educational materials, reflecting the close connection between research and teaching in academic environments. Public communication and dissemination are also significant objectives (46.3%), while 43.5% report producing data for archiving and preserving information. Similarly, 40.7% indicate that data production contributes to the preparation of reports, and 38.0% refer to cataloguing activities, such as the creation of metadata for documentation or management purposes.

More specialised objectives include the development of conservation or restoration plans (25.0%), monitoring and evaluation activities (23.1%), and supporting decision-

making processes (25.0%). These results suggest that research data are frequently mobilised beyond purely scholarly contexts, contributing to documentation, heritage management and communication activities.

The survey also indicates that researchers are often directly involved in the analytical processing of the data they produce. A majority of respondents (58.3%) report analysing their own data, while 22.2% do so only occasionally and 19.4% indicate that data processing is carried out by others. Overall, this pattern reflects a research environment in which data production and analysis are closely intertwined within the same scholarly workflows.

Types, formats and documentation of data

The types of data used within the Academia and Research profile reflect the diversity of sources typically mobilised in scholarly work (*Figure 1.5*).

D3. What types of data do you typically create, consult or reuse?	Count	%
Historical or archival records (legacy information, records from the past)	65	60,2%
Published research outputs (previously disseminated academic or scientific findings)	65	60,2%
Textual or written information (e.g., narratives, documentation, reports, articles)	59	54,6%
Quantitative data (numerical data, statistics, measured values)	52	48,1%
Spatial / geographical information (location-based data, maps, geographic features)	43	39,8%
Descriptive metadata (summaries or categorisations of datasets)	39	36,1%
Observational findings (field notes, natural observations, event logs)	34	31,5%
Experimental results (outcomes from controlled, reproducible experiments)	33	30,6%
Survey and interview responses (data from consultations, interviews, or polls)	23	21,3%
Administrative or regulatory records (government data, legal information, regulations)	22	20,4%
Structural or spatial representations (conceptual models, spatial relationships)	21	19,4%
Environmental measurements (data from ecological monitoring or natural systems)	17	15,7%
Social or behavioural information (data from social networks, behavioural studies)	14	13,0%
Machine-generated insights (automated logs, data from sensors or IoT devices)	12	11,1%
Biological or genomic information (DNA sequences, biological samples, genetic data)	4	3,7%

Figure 1.5 *Types of data created, consulted or reused (D3)*

Historical or archival records and published research outputs are the most common categories, each reported by 60.2% of respondents. Textual information (54.6%), quantitative data (48.1%) and spatial or geographical information (39.8%) are also widely used, together with descriptive metadata (36.1%), observational findings (31.5%) and experimental results (30.6%). Other data types appear less frequently, including survey

responses (21.3%), administrative records (20.4%), structural representations (19.4%) and environmental measurements (15.7%).

In terms of formats, open standards are relatively widespread. A plurality of respondents report mainly using open formats (44.4%), while 37.0% combine open and proprietary formats. Exclusive reliance on closed formats remains limited (3.7%), although 14.8% indicate uncertainty about the formats used.

Documentation practices rely primarily on relatively lightweight approaches. Simple notes (48.1%), annotations directly within data (46.3%) and manual documentation files (41.7%) are the most common methods, while metadata creation is reported by 36.1% of respondents. Smaller shares indicate the use of structured documentation systems (17.6%), established standards or protocols (19.4%), controlled vocabularies (13.0%) or automated documentation systems (9.3%).

When controlled vocabularies are used, domain-specific thesauri such as PACTOLS, MIMO, Iconclass, RKD and TaDiRAH are the most frequently cited, followed by international vocabularies including Getty AAT, TGN, ULAN and VIAF and national authority files such as GND, BnF, LoC and IdRef. Linked open data identifiers (e.g., Wikidata, Geonames, ORCID, ROR) and ontologies or metadata schemas such as CIDOC CRM and LIDO are also mentioned, although less frequently.

Data management and storage

Storage practices within the Academia and Research profile show a strongly hybrid but predominantly local and institutional configuration (*Figure 1.6*).

Local storage remains the most widespread environment for primary datasets, with 75.9% of respondents indicating that more than half of their data are stored locally. Institutional servers also play a major role, with 50.0% reporting that at least half of their data are stored on organisation-managed infrastructures. Cloud-based commercial platforms represent a relevant complementary environment, used for more than half of primary datasets by 44.4% of respondents. By contrast, repositories appear much less central as primary storage locations: only 7.5% report storing more than half of their data in domain-specific repositories and 11.1% in generic open-access repositories. Collaborative platforms (13.9%), self-hosted servers or personal websites (18.5%) and social networks or forums (14.8%) also remain secondary.

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (<50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	6 (5,6%)	20 (18,5%)	21 (19,4%)	61 (56,5%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	79 (73,1%)	21 (19,4%)	6 (5,6%)	2 (1,9%)

In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	52 (48,1%)	44 (40,7%)	9 (8,3%)	3 (2,8%)
On cloud-based commercial platforms (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	24 (22,2%)	36 (33,3%)	28 (25,9%)	20 (18,5%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	98 (90,7%)	6 (5,6%)	4 (3,7%)	0 (0,0%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, organisation or university-managed storage)	22 (20,4%)	32 (29,6%)	27 (25,0%)	27 (25,0%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	61 (56,5%)	32 (29,6%)	6 (5,6%)	9 (8,3%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	57 (52,8%)	35 (32,4%)	9 (8,3%)	7 (6,5%)
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	67 (62,0%)	21 (19,4%)	9 (8,3%)	11 (10,2%)

Figure 1.6 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9)

A similar pattern emerges for access to secondary datasets. Local environments again represent the most common point of access, with 67.6% of respondents reporting that they access more than half of the data they consult or reuse locally. Institutional or private servers are also significant, used for more than half of secondary datasets by 36.1% of respondents, while cloud-based commercial platforms reach 33.3%. Access through repositories remains more limited: 13.0% report consulting more than half of reused data through domain-specific repositories, and 20.4% through generic open-access repositories. Collaborative platforms, subscription-based services and social networks remain marginal as dominant access points.

Overall, these patterns suggest that academic and research data practices are supported primarily by local and institutional infrastructures, while repositories and collaborative platforms are used more selectively rather than as the main environments for storing or accessing research data.

Sharing, licensing and challenges

Data sharing appears to be a common practice within the Academia and Research profile, although it is often implemented in flexible or conditional forms (*Figure 1.7*).

A large majority of respondents indicate that they share data at least occasionally: 27.8% report always enabling access to their data, while 69.4% do so sometimes. Only a very small minority (2.8%) indicate that they do not share their data.

D10. Do you share the data you produce?	Count	%
Yes, sometimes	75	69,4%
Yes, always	30	27,8%
No	3	2,8%

Figure 1.7 Data sharing practices (D10)

The conditions under which data are shared reveal a mixed model combining open access with various forms of restriction or mediation. Fully open sharing remains present but not dominant: 34.3% of respondents indicate that more than half of their data are shared openly without restrictions, and 37.0% report sharing more than half of their data under a specific open licence. At the same time, conditional forms of sharing are also widespread. For instance, 39.8% report sharing more than half of their data only for specific purposes, while 26.9% indicate that more than half of their data may be shared upon request. Conversely, several restrictive conditions tend to apply to a minority of datasets: embargo periods, anonymisation procedures or formal agreements are most often reported as applying to less than half of shared data.

Respondents also report a range of challenges affecting data sharing and reuse. The most frequently cited obstacles concern the additional effort required to prepare data for sharing (57.4%) and legal or contractual constraints such as intellectual property rights (55.6%). Issues related to data or metadata quality and reliability are also widely reported (54.6%), together with concerns about potential data misuse (46.3%). Technical barriers (44.4%), confidentiality or privacy concerns (38.0%), and the lack of appropriate infrastructures (46.3%) further complicate sharing practices, while the persistence of non-digitised materials (26.9%) and unclear guidelines regarding data sharing (22.2%) represent additional constraints.

Overall, these results suggest that while data sharing is broadly embedded in academic practices, it is often mediated by legal, technical and organisational considerations that shape how and under which conditions research data can be made accessible.

Needs & Expectations

Academic users express needs linked to research complexity, data-intensive workflows and the integration of digital tools into scientific practices.

The main challenges relate to technical and infrastructure limitations, together with financial constraints and the continuous need to acquire new skills. The learning curve remains significant, especially in relation to specialised tools and evolving methodologies (Figure 1.8).

Interoperability issues and data-related challenges, including standardisation and access, further affect the efficiency of research processes.

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	13	38,2%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	10	29,4%
Training, documentation and capacity building	9	26,5%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	8	23,5%

Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	7	20,6%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	7	20,6%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	6	17,6%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	5	14,7%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	5	14,7%
Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	5	14,7%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	4	11,8%
Connectivity and offline functionality	3	8,8%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	3	8,8%

Figure 1.8 Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3)

Human resource constraints and limited institutional support also play a role, particularly when advanced technical expertise is required but not readily available. Connectivity issues and documentation gaps can further slow down adoption and effective use.

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for improved interoperability and integration between systems, supported by shared standards and better collaboration frameworks. Training and documentation are considered essential to support both adoption and effective use.

Additional expectations include improved user-friendliness, stronger infrastructure and scalable storage solutions, as well as better data management, retrieval and sharing functionalities. There is also a demand for more sustainable and open solutions. Advanced functionalities such as automation and AI are recognised as valuable, particularly for data processing and analysis, but remain secondary to core needs around usability, integration and resource availability.

Infrastructure & governance

Engagement with institutional data infrastructures appears limited within the Academia and Research profile (*Figure 1.9*).

A large majority of respondents (78.7%) report not being involved in the management of institutional databases, servers or repositories, indicating that infrastructural responsibilities are typically handled by specialised technical staff rather than by researchers themselves.

F2.3. Do you use ontological models (e.g., CIDOC CRM, SKOS)?	Count	%
Yes	10	9,3%
No	10	9,3%
I don't know	3	2,8%
Not involved in database/server/repository management (F1)	85	78,7%

Figure 1.9 Use of ontological models (F2.3)

Among the smaller group of respondents who are involved in such activities (21.3%), the use of ontological models shows a mixed pattern. Within this subset, 43.5% report using ontological frameworks such as CIDOC CRM or SKOS, while an equal share indicate that they do not use them and 13.0% report being unsure.

Overall, these results suggest that formal semantic modelling remains a specialised practice associated with a relatively small group of researchers involved in infrastructure management, rather than a widespread component of everyday academic research workflows.

Overall Conclusion

The Academia and Research profile reflects a community strongly oriented towards knowledge production, analytical investigation and the interpretation of cultural heritage data. Digital tools are widely used to support research activities, particularly for data analysis, spatial technologies, documentation and the management of research materials. At the same time, engagement with more advanced infrastructures—such as formal knowledge representation tools or ontological models—remains more selective and is often concentrated among researchers involved in specialised technical or infrastructural roles.

Data production within this profile is closely connected to research objectives, teaching activities and public dissemination, highlighting the multifaceted role of academic work. Researchers rely on a diverse range of data types, including archival sources, textual materials, quantitative datasets and spatial information, and typically combine relatively lightweight documentation practices with more structured metadata and vocabulary-based approaches when required.

Infrastructure and storage practices reveal a hybrid ecosystem in which local environments and institutional infrastructures coexist with cloud platforms and repositories. Although data sharing is widely practiced, it is often mediated by legal, technical and organisational constraints, reflecting the complexity of managing research data within academic contexts.

Overall, the profile illustrates a research community that actively engages with digital resources to produce, analyse and disseminate knowledge, while continuing to navigate challenges related to interoperability, technical infrastructure, skills development and the sustainable management of research data.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This section examines the relationship between production tools (C1.2b), documentation practices (D8.1), and data management configurations (C1.3b), as well as their connection to data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess how the use of tools and the organisation of documentation and data management practices contribute to different levels of maturity, and to identify whether more advanced configurations are associated with more integrated and systematic data practices within this profile.

3D modelling and visualisation (C1.2b) × Data management and storage (C1.3b)

The cross-analysis between production tools and data management configurations shows a broadly consistent pattern, with data collection and structuring representing the most common configuration across all tool types (*Figure 1.10*).

3D modelling and visualisation (C1.2b) × Data management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
3D scanning or modeling, rendering and reconstruction	22	8	11	8
Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM)	9	5	3	2
Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LIDAR)	9	4	4	4
Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial representation of information	18	10	8	6
Virtual Reality (VR) / Augmented Reality (AR) / Mixed Reality (MR)	10	10	5	7
Answered NO to C1.2a	16	9	10	9

Figure 1.10 Relationship between 3D modelling and visualisation tools (C1.2b) and data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

However, this predominance needs to be interpreted in light of the relationship between tools and practices. Even in the presence of more advanced production technologies – such as 3D scanning, LIDAR, or GIS – data management remains primarily oriented towards structuring rather than interoperability. This suggests that the adoption of sophisticated tools does not necessarily translate into more integrated or system-level data practices.

At the same time, some variations can be observed. Tools that are more closely associated with modelling and system-based workflows, such as BIM or GIS, show a relatively higher association with interoperability practices, indicating a stronger orientation towards data integration. Virtual and immersive technologies (VR/AR) display a more balanced pattern between structuring and interoperability, reflecting their hybrid role between data production and experiential use.

Respondents who do not report using production tools show a higher proportion of cases with no structured data management practices, suggesting that the absence of dedicated tools is associated with lower levels of formalisation.

Overall, the results indicate that while production tools influence data management practices to some extent, they do not fundamentally shift the dominant orientation towards data structuring. Instead, they introduce only limited variations, with more

advanced tools supporting a gradual – but not systematic – move towards interoperability.

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and the use of formal knowledge tools reveals a fragmented and weakly aligned pattern, with no clear correspondence between the level of documentation and the adoption of semantic technologies (*Figure 1.11*).

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)	Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies	Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies	Ontologies	Answered NO to C1.4a
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	20	9	2	21
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	19	10	3	18
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	19	10	2	14
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	7	3	1	8
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	16	6	5	12
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	7	4	5	5
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	2	1	2	5
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	4	3	5	2

Figure 1.11 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and use of formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b)

Across both simpler practices – such as notes, annotations, and manual documentation – and more structured approaches – including documentation systems and metadata creation – the distribution of tool usage remains mixed. Knowledge graphs and related technologies appear consistently across most documentation practices, but are accompanied by a similarly high proportion of respondents who do not report using any formal knowledge tools. This indicates that even relatively structured documentation practices do not systematically translate into the adoption of semantic technologies.

The absence of a strong alignment is particularly evident in more advanced documentation configurations. Even in cases involving documentation systems or automated processes, a substantial share of respondents report not using formal knowledge tools.

A more coherent pattern can be observed in relation to standards and controlled vocabularies, where the use of ontologies and other semantic tools becomes more prominent. This indicates that when documentation practices explicitly engage with

standardisation and semantic structuring, the adoption of formal knowledge tools becomes more consistent.

Overall, the results suggest that documentation practices and the use of formal knowledge tools evolve relatively independently within this profile. Rather than forming a tightly integrated system, they reflect a heterogeneous landscape in which structured documentation does not necessarily imply the use of advanced semantic technologies.

Data management (C1.3b) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between data management configurations and data sharing practices reveals a clear relationship between the frequency of sharing and the level of maturity of data management approaches (Figure 1.12).

Sharing (D10) x Management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API	Resource storage and retrieval	Answered NO to C1.3a
Yes, always	7	11	7	5
Yes, sometimes	34	10	16	15
No	2	0	0	1

Figure 1.12 Relationship between the use of data management and storage tools (C1.3b) and data sharing practices (D10)

A shift can be observed between occasional and systematic sharing. Respondents who report sharing data “sometimes” are more strongly associated with data collection and structuring practices, indicating a focus on organising data without necessarily integrating them into broader systems. In contrast, those who report sharing data “always” show a relatively stronger association with data interoperability and integration, suggesting a more advanced approach oriented towards connecting and reusing data across contexts.

This pattern indicates that more consistent sharing practices are associated with more developed data management configurations. As sharing becomes more systematic, data practices appear to move beyond basic structuring towards greater interoperability and integration.

At the same time, a non-negligible share of respondents who share data only occasionally also report the absence of structured data management practices, reinforcing the idea that lower levels of sharing are associated with less formalised approaches.

Overall, the results suggest that the frequency of data sharing is closely linked to the level of data management maturity, with more regular sharing corresponding to more integrated and advanced data practices.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This section examines the relationship between storage environments (D9), data sharing practices (D10), and the challenges (D13) associated with different infrastructural configurations.

The objective is to assess how storage environments influence both the regularity of data sharing and the types of barriers encountered, and to identify the extent to which infrastructural conditions shape data circulation within this profile.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and data sharing practices shows a consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the most common mode of sharing (*Figure 1.13*).

At the same time, variations emerge in relation to the level of openness. More open licensing approaches – such as unrestricted sharing or the use of open licenses – are associated with higher proportions of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), indicating that fewer access constraints support more regular and continuous data exchange.

In contrast, more restrictive or conditional forms of sharing – including formal agreements, sharing upon request, or for specific purposes – are more strongly associated with occasional sharing practices. In these cases, data exchange tends to occur on a more situational and case-by-case basis.

Across all licensing configurations, the proportion of respondents who do not share data remains very limited, indicating that sharing is almost always present, regardless of the conditions applied.

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	18	18	1
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	17	23	0
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	9	16	0
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	5	15	0
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	4	8	0
Upon request only	6	22	1
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	13	33	2
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	4	6	1

Figure 1.13 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and data sharing practices (D10)

Overall, the results suggest that while data sharing is widespread across this profile, the degree of openness in licensing plays a role in shaping its regularity, with more open frameworks supporting more consistent and systematic sharing practices

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and perceived challenges reveals a broadly consistent distribution across all configurations, with no single barrier clearly dominating within any specific licensing model (*Figure 1.14*).

Across all licensing approaches – from open to more restrictive or conditional forms – challenges related to legal constraints, the effort required to prepare data for sharing, and concerns about misuse tend to appear with slightly higher proportions. At the same time, other barriers, including data quality, technical limitations, and infrastructure related issues, are also consistently represented across all configurations.

While the overall structure remains stable, some variations can be observed. More open licensing approaches show a slightly stronger emphasis on data quality and effort-related challenges, reflecting the requirements associated with preparing data for broader dissemination. In contrast, more controlled forms of sharing – such as sharing upon request, through formal agreements, or after anonymisation – tend to place relatively more emphasis on concerns related to misuse, privacy, and legal constraints. Configurations based on specific purposes also display a more evenly distributed pattern, with multiple challenges appearing at similar levels.

Licensing (D12) True (50–75%) & True (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	16	12	20	13	17	15	10	13	9
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	28	18	23	15	27	21	10	15	9
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	13	9	15	14	21	11	9	13	7
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	7	8	13	11	9	9	6	7	5
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	6	5	9	8	6	7	4	4	4
Upon request only	12	10	16	18	16	13	9	17	9
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	21	17	29	28	25	26	11	20	11
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	5	7	7	8	3	6	0	3	2

Figure 1.14 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Overall, the results suggest that challenges associated with data sharing are largely independent of licensing conditions. However, different governance configurations introduce subtle shifts in the types of concerns that are more prominently perceived, particularly in relation to risk, compliance, and the operational effort required to enable sharing

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This section examines the relationship between storage environments (D9), data sharing practices (D10), and the challenges (D13) associated with different infrastructural configurations.

The objective is to assess how different storage environments relate to both the regularity of data sharing and the types of barriers encountered, and to identify the extent to which infrastructural conditions shape data circulation and operational constraints within this profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and data sharing practices reveals a largely consistent pattern across the most commonly used configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant mode of sharing (Figure 1.15).

Across widely used environments such as local storage, cloud-based platforms, and institutional servers, sharing remains predominantly occasional, with very similar distributions across these contexts.

At the same time, a different pattern emerges in storage environments that are inherently oriented towards openness and collaboration. Public repositories and collaborative platforms show a substantially higher proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), indicating that when storage infrastructures are explicitly designed for access and dissemination, they are more likely to support continuous and structured sharing practices.

Across all configurations, the absence of sharing is minimal, indicating that data sharing is almost always present within this profile.

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Sharing (D10)		
	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	25	54	3
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	2	6	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	14	34	0
Institutional servers or websites	14	40	0
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	7	5	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	9	6	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	4	12	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	0	4	0
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	6	14	0

Figure 1.15 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

Overall, the results suggest that while most storage environments are associated with similar, predominantly occasional sharing practices, infrastructures specifically designed for openness and collaboration play a key role in enabling more systematic and consistent data sharing.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and perceived challenges reveals a broadly consistent distribution across all configurations, with no single barrier clearly dominating within any specific environment (Figure 1.16).

Across all storage types, challenges related to legal constraints, effort required for data preparation, and concerns about misuse tend to appear among the most prominent, confirming the presence of structural issues that persist regardless of the infrastructural context. Other barriers – including technical limitations, infrastructure-related

constraints, and data quality issues – are also consistently represented across environments.

Storage (D9) True (50–75%) & True (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	43	33	44	43	48	39	23	38	20
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	5	3	6	4	5	4	2	3	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	22	20	27	26	22	24	12	24	16
Institutional servers or websites	30	22	33	26	26	24	15	29	13
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	9	6	7	7	5	6	2	4	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	9	4	7	5	7	3	2	3	2
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	6	7	9	8	8	12	6	8	4
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	1
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	11	7	15	10	10	10	7	10	7

Figure 1.16 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

At the same time, some variations emerge in the relative prominence of specific challenges. Local storage environments show a slightly stronger emphasis on effort-related constraints, suggesting a higher burden in preparing and managing data for sharing. Institutional infrastructures, in contrast, display a more pronounced focus on infrastructure-related limitations, reflecting the complexity of organisational systems and dependencies. Cloud-based environments present a more balanced distribution across different types of challenges, while social platforms are relatively more associated with technical barriers.

Overall, the results suggest that while the general structure of challenges remains stable across storage environments, different infrastructures introduce subtle shifts in the types of issues that are more prominently experienced. These variations point to context-specific constraints layered on top of broader, shared challenges in data management and sharing.

Profile: Cultural Communicator

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

D2. What is the primary purpose of the data you create?

→ Developing educational materials or Public communication or awareness

D14. What are your primary objectives when producing, consulting or reusing data?

→ Public engagement or educational purposes

A6 – Field of professional activity

→ Education, mediation and audience engagement

Base: 147 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Cultural Communicators* profile represents respondents who produce and use data primarily for educational purposes, public communication or audience engagement. These actors work in roles focused on mediation, outreach or knowledge dissemination within cultural heritage contexts.

Their activities frequently involve the production of educational materials, public communication resources or engagement-oriented content designed to make cultural heritage information accessible to wider audiences. They often operate in educational, mediation or audience engagement roles and contribute to translating heritage knowledge into formats suitable for public interaction.

Overall, this profile reflects actors whose work emphasises communication, accessibility and audience engagement in the use and dissemination of cultural heritage data.

Summary of findings

Access models

Responses indicate a strong reliance on open and freely accessible digital tools. The most widely reported access model consists of free, open-access services, used by 84.4% of respondents, indicating that dissemination and communication activities often depend on tools that can be accessed without financial or institutional barriers (*Figure 2.1*).

Other access configurations remain present but less dominant. Free tools with licensing conditions are used by 43.5% of respondents, while subscription-based services are reported by 38.1%. Paid licence-based tools are somewhat less common (26.5%), and in-house or custom-built tools are used by 20.4% of respondents. More occasional access models include trial-based services (12.2%) and pay-per-use systems (2.7%), which appear only marginally within this profile.

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	124	84.4%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	73	49.7%

Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	64	43.5%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	56	38.1%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	39	26.5%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	30	20.4%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	18	12.2%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	4	2.7%

Figure 2.1 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4).

In addition, almost half of respondents report using open-source software (49.7%), suggesting that freely available and modifiable tools play an important role in supporting communication, dissemination and public engagement activities within cultural heritage contexts.

Documentation of data

Documentation practices within this profile are generally informal and oriented toward practical working methods rather than structured documentation frameworks. The most common approach consists of simple notes, reported by 50.3% of respondents, indicating that documentation often takes place through basic written annotations or personal records (*Figure 2.2*).

D8.1. How do you typically document the data you produce?	Count	%
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	74	50.3%
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	66	44.9%
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	65	44.2%
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	40	27.2%
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	31	21.1%
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	12	8.2%
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	10	6.8%
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	6	4.1%

Figure 2.2 Documentation practices for the data produced (D8.1)

Other widely used practices include manual documentation files (44.9%) and annotations directly within data or files (44.2%), suggesting that documentation is frequently embedded within working materials rather than managed through dedicated systems. More structured approaches appear less common. Metadata creation is reported by 27.2% of respondents, while documentation systems are used by 21.1%.

More formal documentation infrastructures remain relatively limited within this profile. Only 8.2% report following established documentation standards, while controlled vocabularies (6.8%) and automated documentation systems (4.1%) are used by small shares of respondents.

Taken together, these findings highlight that Cultural Communicators tend to rely on flexible and lightweight documentation practices that support communication and dissemination activities rather than highly structured metadata or standards-based documentation frameworks.

Data management and storage

Storage practices within this profile are strongly oriented toward local and easily accessible environments. A large majority of respondents report storing most of their datasets locally (73.4%), indicating that communication and dissemination activities often rely on personal or locally managed storage systems.

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (<50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	9 (6.1%)	30 (20.4%)	28 (19.0%)	80 (54.4%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	114 (77.6%)	29 (19.7%)	2 (1.4%)	2 (1.4%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	102 (69.4%)	36 (24.5%)	6 (4.1%)	3 (2.0%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	25 (17.0%)	45 (30.6%)	43 (29.3%)	34 (23.1%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	128 (87.1%)	13 (8.8%)	6 (4.1%)	0 (0.0%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	51 (34.7%)	38 (25.9%)	25 (17.0%)	33 (22.4%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	105 (71.4%)	34 (23.1%)	6 (4.1%)	2 (1.4%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	61 (41.5%)	64 (43.5%)	12 (8.2%)	10 (6.8%)
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	76 (51.7%)	41 (27.9%)	15 (10.2%)	15 (10.2%)

Figure 2.3 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9)

Cloud-based commercial platforms also play a significant role, with 52.4% of respondents indicating that more than half of their data are stored on services such as Google Drive or Dropbox. Institutional servers are used for the majority of datasets by 39.4% of respondents, suggesting that institutional infrastructures support storage in a substantial but less dominant share of cases.

Other storage environments appear much less central within this profile. Self-hosted servers (20.4%) and collaborative platforms such as GitHub or Wikidata (5.5%) are rarely used as primary storage systems. Similarly, domain-specific repositories (2.8%) and generic open-access repositories (6.1%) are seldom used to store the majority of datasets.

This pattern suggests that Cultural Communicators tend to rely on practical and readily accessible storage solutions, particularly local environments and commercial cloud platforms, rather than highly specialised repository infrastructures.

Data sharing

Data sharing is a common practice within this profile, although it often occurs in a context-dependent manner. A large majority of respondents report that they sometimes share their data (69.4%), indicating that dissemination and communication activities frequently involve sharing materials depending on project needs, audiences or institutional conditions (*Figure 2.4*).

D10. Do you share the data you produce?	Count	%
Yes, sometimes	102	69.4%
Yes, always	39	26.5%
No	6	4.1%

Figure 2.4 Data sharing practices (D10)

A smaller but still significant share report that they always share their data (26.5%), suggesting that open or regular data circulation forms part of the workflow for some respondents. Only a small minority indicate that they do not share their data (4.1%).

These responses point to an environment where Cultural Communicators generally operate in environments where data sharing is widespread, although its regularity tends to vary according to the specific context of communication, dissemination or public engagement activities.

Collaboration

Collaboration with developers and technical teams appears relatively limited within this profile. The most common form of interaction consists of regular meetings and feedback sessions, reported by 25.9% of respondents. A smaller share indicates direct involvement in testing and iterative development processes (16.3%), suggesting occasional participation in the refinement of digital tools (*Figure 2.5*).

Other forms of collaboration are less widespread. Some respondents contribute through requirement documentation (12.9%) or by participating in workshops or hackathons (10.9%), while collaborative platforms such as Slack or Trello (8.8%) and email-based communication (7.5%) are reported by smaller shares.

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams?	Count	%
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	38	25.9%
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	24	16.3%
Through detailed requirement documentation	19	12.9%
Participation in workshops or hackathons	16	10.9%
Using collaborative tools like Slack, Trello, or Jira, or Figma	13	8.8%
Via email or written reports only	11	7.5%

Figure 2.5 Collaboration practices with development teams (E6)

Taken together, these findings indicate that Cultural Communicators are only occasionally involved in the technical development of digital tools, with collaboration typically occurring through feedback or consultation rather than direct participation in development processes.

Needs & expectations

Cultural communicators express needs strongly linked to accessibility, usability and the practical integration of digital tools into communication and dissemination activities.

C2. What difficulties do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?	Count	%
Financial constraints and costs	40	48.8%
Technical, infrastructure and hardware limitations	36	43.9%
Skills, training and learning curve	34	41.5%
Interoperability and system integration issues	28	34.1%
Connectivity and access limitations	26	31.7%
Usability and user experience limitations	24	29.3%
Legal, copyright and data governance concerns	18	22.0%
Human resources and staffing constraints	18	22.0%
Vendor dependency, tool sustainability and support limitations	13	15.9%
Data access and availability constraints	11	13.4%
Organisational and policy barriers	10	12.2%
Data quality, heterogeneity and standardisation issues	9	11.0%
Documentation, guidance and best practice gaps	9	11.0%
Domain-specific limitations and lack of fit	6	7.3%

Figure 2.6 Main difficulties in the use of digital tools and resources (C2)

The main challenges relate to financial constraints and technical limitations, together with skills gaps and the effort required to learn and adopt new tools. Connectivity issues and interoperability problems further affect their ability to efficiently manage and share content across platforms. Usability limitations also play a significant role, particularly when tools are not designed for non-technical users (Figure 2.6).

Human and organisational constraints contribute to these difficulties, especially in smaller teams or resource-constrained contexts where digital tasks must be integrated into already complex workflows.

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for more interoperable and integrated systems, alongside improved user-friendliness and simplified interfaces to facilitate adoption. Training and capacity building are also important, particularly to support non-specialist users. There is also a clear demand for more affordable solutions and stronger structural support mechanisms.

Additional expectations highlight the importance of improved technical infrastructure, clearer legal and governance frameworks, and stronger collaboration and international networking opportunities. Respondents also stress the need for user-centred design approaches and more accessible data sharing environments.

Advanced functionalities such as automation and AI are mentioned, but remain secondary to usability, accessibility, sustainability and support needs.

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the Cultural Communicators profile reflects professionals primarily engaged in the dissemination, communication and public interpretation of cultural heritage data. Their practices are strongly oriented toward the use of accessible digital tools and flexible documentation methods that support storytelling, outreach and educational activities.

The results also indicate that these respondents rely mainly on open-access tools and locally managed storage environments, while structured repository infrastructures or formal documentation standards are less central to their workflows. Data sharing is widely practiced but often occurs in a context-dependent and narrative-oriented manner, reflecting the communicative goals of this profile.

Taken together, these findings highlight a group of professionals who play a key role in translating heritage data into accessible narratives and public-facing content, contributing to the visibility, interpretation and societal engagement of cultural heritage resources.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the relationship between documentation practices (D8.1), storage infrastructures (D9), and data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different levels of documentation structuring are associated with more consistent or distributed data practices, or whether these dimensions remain only weakly connected.

Documentation practices (D8.1) × Data sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and data sharing behaviours shows a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the regularity of sharing (*Figure 2.7*).

Documentation (D8.1) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	22	43	1
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	23	42	0
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	21	52	1
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	12	28	0
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	2	10	0
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	10	21	0
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	3	7	0
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	3	3	0

Figure 2.7 Relationship between documentation practices (D8.1) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across all documentation types, “Yes, sometimes” clearly represents the dominant modality, indicating that sharing is predominantly situational. The proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) remains moderate and relatively stable across most practices, with slightly lower values observed for more formalised approaches such as the use of standards.

No clear distinction emerges between informal and more structured documentation practices. Manual documentation, annotations and simple notes display distributions similar to those observed for metadata, documentation systems and controlled vocabularies. In particular, the use of standards is associated with the lowest proportion of systematic sharing, suggesting a weak alignment between formalisation and sharing behaviours.

Overall, the results indicate that the level of documentation structuring does not significantly influence the regularity of data sharing within the profile.

Documentation (D8.1) × Where data are stored or archived (D9)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and storage infrastructures shows a highly consistent distribution across all configurations, with limited variation in proportional terms (*Figure 2.8*).

Documentation (D8.1) x Storage (D9) <small>True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%)</small>	Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	Institutional servers or websites	Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	Social networks or forums (e.g. Research Gate)	Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers or personal websites
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	48	3	32	23	6	3	13	4	18
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	46	3	37	25	4	5	11	1	16
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	59	2	42	30	6	3	15	1	16
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	26	2	20	21	2	3	8	1	10
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	7	0	4	5	2	1	0	0	3
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	21	2	15	12	1	1	3	1	10
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	4	0	3	5	1	2	0	0	3
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	5	1	3	2	0	1	1	0	0

Figure 2.8 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and where data are stored or archived (D9)

Across all documentation types, local storage clearly represents the primary environment, followed by cloud-based platforms and, to a lesser extent, institutional infrastructures. This threefold structure remains stable regardless of the type or level of documentation practice, indicating that storage choices are largely independent of how documentation is carried out.

Differences between practices are minimal. Informal approaches such as manual documentation, annotations and simple notes display distributions very similar to more structured practices such as metadata creation, documentation systems and the use of controlled vocabularies. Only minor variations emerge, with slightly higher use of institutional environments for controlled vocabularies and a marginally stronger presence of repositories in standards-based practices.

Overall, the results suggest that the level of documentation structuring does not significantly influence storage configurations, which remain broadly consistent across all practices.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between access models (C4) and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different access configurations are associated with variations in the regularity of data sharing, or whether sharing remains largely independent of these conditions

Access models (C4) × Sharing practices (D10)

The cross-analysis between access models and data sharing practices shows a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the regularity of sharing (*Figure 2.9*).

Access C4 x Sharing D10	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	34	86	4
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality)	18	45	1
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	2	15	1
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	12	42	2
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	9	29	1
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	0	4	0
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	9	21	0
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	12	59	2

Figure 2.9 Relationship between access models (C4) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across all access types, “Yes, sometimes” clearly represents the dominant modality. The proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) remains comparatively low across most configurations.

Differences between access models are minimal. Open, licensed, in-house and commercial configurations display very similar distributions, suggesting that the type of access does not significantly influence sharing behaviours. In particular, open-source environments show a high concentration of situational sharing, indicating that openness of tools does not necessarily correspond to more systematic data sharing.

Overall, the results indicate that data sharing practices are largely independent of access models, with only marginal variation across configurations.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between storage infrastructures (D9) and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different storage environments are associated with variations in the regularity of data sharing, or whether sharing remains largely independent of infrastructural configurations.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage infrastructures and data sharing practices shows a largely consistent pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the regularity of sharing (*Figure 2.10*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Sharing (D10)		
	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	28	76	4
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	2	2	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	23	52	2
Institutional servers or websites	16	40	2
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	3	5	1
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	5	3	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	7	15	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	2	4	0
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers or personal websites	8	22	0

Figure 2.10 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across all storage environments, “Yes, sometimes” clearly represents the dominant modality. The proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) is moderate and relatively stable across the main infrastructures, including local, cloud-based and institutional environments.

Differences between storage types are minimal. The primary infrastructures display very similar distributions, suggesting that the choice of storage does not significantly influence sharing behaviours. Some variations can be observed in less frequently used environments, but these are based on small numbers and should be interpreted with caution.

Comparative Analysis – Collaboration

This block examines the relationship between collaboration modalities (E6), documentation practices (D8.1), and data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different forms of collaboration are associated with variations in the structuring of documentation and the regularity of data sharing, or whether these practices remain largely independent of collaboration settings.

Collaboration (E6) × Documentation (D8.1)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and documentation practices shows a highly consistent distribution across all configurations, with limited variation in proportional terms (Figure 2.11).

Collaboration (E6) x Documentation (D8.1)	Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	20	21	14	18	9	10	7	2
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	11	10	9	10	7	6	4	2
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	7	5	5	8	5	5	3	2
Participation in workshops or hackathons	8	8	8	9	7	3	4	1
Through detailed requirement documentation	11	11	7	8	4	5	2	2
Via email or written reports only	9	7	4	6	2	2	3	1

Figure 2.11 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data documentation practices (D8.1)

Across all forms of collaboration, manual documentation, annotations and, to a lesser extent, metadata creation represent the most prominent practices. This structure remains stable regardless of the collaboration modality, indicating that the way collaboration is organised does not significantly influence how documentation is carried out.

More structured documentation practices, such as the use of standards, controlled vocabularies and automated systems, remain marginal across all configurations. Only minor variations can be observed, with slightly higher reliance on manual documentation in less interactive settings such as email-based communication, and a somewhat more balanced distribution in workshop-based contexts.

Overall, the results suggest that documentation practices are largely independent of collaboration modalities, with a stable predominance of informal approaches across all configurations.

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and data sharing practices shows a generally consistent pattern, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant modality across all configurations. This indicates that sharing remains largely situational regardless of how collaboration is organised (Figure 2.12).

Collaboration (E6) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	12	26	0
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	6	18	0
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	3	10	0
Participation in workshops or hackathons	3	13	0
Through detailed requirement documentation	9	10	0
Via email or written reports only	2	9	0

Figure 2.12 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data sharing practices (D10)

At the same time, some variation can be observed in the proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”). More structured collaboration settings – particularly those based on detailed requirement documentation – show a higher share of consistent sharing behaviours. By contrast, less formal or more ad hoc modalities, such as workshops or email-based communication, display lower levels of systematic sharing.

However, these differences remain moderate and do not substantially alter the overall configuration. Overall, the results suggest that collaboration has only a limited influence on the regularity of data sharing, which remains predominantly context-dependent across all collaboration modalities.

Profile: Data Documenters / Managers

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

C1.3a – Are you using data management and storage tools or services?

→ Yes

C1.4a – Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?

→ Yes

D8.1 – If yes, how do you document your data?

- Filling in metadata
- Using controlled vocabularies
- Following established standards or protocols
- Using a documentation system

F1 – Do you manage or contribute to any data storage system (e.g., server, repository, etc.)?

→ → Yes

F4 – What methods and systems do you use to store, archive and curate data?

- Metadata and documentation
- Standardised practices and formats
- Automation and scripting

Base: 56 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Data Documenters / Data Managers* profile represents respondents who are actively involved in the documentation, organisation and curation of data within structured digital environments. These professionals play a key role in ensuring that datasets are systematically described, organised and maintained through metadata, controlled vocabularies, established standards and documentation systems.

Their work is closely connected to the management or contribution to data infrastructures such as databases, repositories or servers. Through the use of data management tools, knowledge representation tools and structured documentation practices, they support the consistency, traceability and long-term usability of cultural heritage data.

Overall, this profile reflects professionals focused on the structured organisation and stewardship of data, contributing to reliable documentation practices and well-managed data infrastructures within cultural heritage contexts.

Summary of findings

Tools development

Many respondents report participating in the development and configuration of digital tools used for managing and documenting data. The most commonly reported role is that of concept designer, indicated by 66.1% of respondents, suggesting a strong involvement in defining the objectives, features and workflows of tools and systems (Figure 3.1).

E3. What is your primary role in the development of such tools?	Count	%
Concept designer (e.g., defining objectives, features, or workflow)	37	66.1%
Project manager / coordinator (e.g., overseeing the development process)	34	60.7%
End-user / tester (e.g., using tools, providing requirements and feedback)	30	53.6%
Data scientist / analyst (e.g., integrating analysis needs into tool design)	21	37.5%
Developer / programmer (e.g., coding, scripting)	19	33.9%

Figure 3.1 Primary roles in the development of digital tools (E3)

A substantial share also contributes as project managers or coordinators (60.7%), overseeing development processes and coordinating activities related to the

implementation of digital infrastructures. Many respondents are additionally involved as end-users or testers (53.6%), providing operational feedback and requirements that inform the design and refinement of tools.

More technically specialised roles are also present within the profile. Around 37.5% report acting as data scientists or analysts, integrating analytical needs into tool design, while 33.9% participate as developers or programmers, contributing directly to coding or scripting activities. Together, these results indicate that Data Documenters and Data Managers are not only users of digital systems but also actively contribute to shaping the tools and infrastructures supporting data documentation and management practices.

Access models

Access to digital tools and services within this profile is largely structured around open and institutionally supported environments. The most widespread access model consists of free, open-access services, used by 82.1% of respondents. Open-source software is also widely adopted (78.6%), indicating a strong engagement with openly available technological ecosystems (Figure 3.2).

At the same time, a significant share of respondents report using tools developed in-house or custom-built within their organisations (66.1%), suggesting that many operate in institutional environments where digital systems are internally developed or adapted to specific documentation and data management needs. Other access configurations remain present but less dominant, including licence-based services (44.6%) and free-with-licence tools (44.6%), while subscription-based services reach 32.1% of respondents.

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	46	82.1%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	44	78.6%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	37	66.1%
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	25	44.6%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	25	44.6%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	18	32.1%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	5	8.9%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	5	8.9%

Figure 3.2 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4)

More occasional or situational access models are comparatively rare. Trial-based access and pay-per-use services are each reported by 8.9% of respondents. Taken together,

these findings highlight that Data Documenters and Data Managers primarily rely on open and institutionally supported tools, complemented by a range of licensed or commercial solutions depending on operational needs.

Data production objectives

The objectives guiding data production, consultation and reuse within this profile are primarily oriented toward improving the quality and structuring of heritage datasets. The most frequently reported objective is improving dataset completeness and establishing best practices for heritage data collection and analysis, indicated by 73.2% of respondents.

A similarly strong emphasis is placed on conducting new analyses or generating new insights, reported by 66.1% of respondents. Many respondents also highlight the role of data in supporting the management and protection of heritage assets, including informing conservation strategies and interventions (66.1%).

Other objectives remain significant but slightly less dominant. Public engagement and educational uses of data are mentioned by 67.9% of respondents, while validating hypotheses or identifying new patterns in data reaches 51.8%. A smaller but still relevant share of respondents (42.9%) reports using data to develop or refine tools, algorithms or models for digital visualisation and interpretation (*Figure 3.3*).

D14. What is your objective when you produce, consult or reuse data?	Count	%
To improve dataset completeness, establish best practices for heritage data collection and analysis	41	73.2%
To use data for wider public engagement and educational purposes, develop teaching resources and case studies	38	67.9%
To conduct new analyses or generate new insights, generate more comprehensive interpretations of heritage materials, to apply machine learning or AI to extract new insights	37	66.1%
To support the management and protection of heritage assets, inform conservation strategies and interventions, provide evidence to influence cultural heritage policies	37	66.1%
To validate hypotheses or verify findings, compare with current datasets or other sources of information, or identify new patterns, trends, or connections in the data	29	51.8%
To develop or refine tools, algorithms or models for prediction or data interpretation, digital visualisation and representation of heritage	24	42.9%
To support cultural industries, or economic activities related to heritage, create virtual or augmented reality experiences	18	32.1%

Figure 3.3 Data production objectives (D14)

Overall, these results indicate that respondents in this profile approach data production and reuse with a strong focus on improving data quality, strengthening documentation practices and supporting the analytical and operational use of cultural heritage datasets.

Documentation of data

Documentation practices within this profile show a strong orientation toward structured and standardised approaches to describing and organising data. The most widespread practice consists of filling in metadata fields, reported by 85.7% of respondents, indicating that formal metadata creation plays a central role in documenting datasets (Figure 3.4).

Structured documentation practices are also widely adopted. Following established standards or protocols, such as domain-specific documentation frameworks, is reported by 71.4% of respondents, while 64.3% indicate that they create manual documentation files to accompany datasets. A similarly high share (60.7%) use annotations directly on data, integrating documentation within working files and datasets.

Dedicated documentation infrastructures are also present within this profile. Documentation systems or structured platforms are used by 53.6% of respondents, while controlled vocabularies are reported by 50.0%, supporting consistent terminology and semantic alignment across datasets.

D8.1. How do you typically document the data you produce?	Count	%
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	48	85.7%
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	40	71.4%
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	36	64.3%
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	34	60.7%
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	30	53.6%
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	28	50.0%
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	27	48.2%
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	13	23.2%

Figure 3.4 Data documentation practices (D8.1).

More informal approaches remain part of everyday workflows. Simple notes, either handwritten or digital, are used by 48.2% of respondents, while automated documentation systems remain less widespread, reported by 23.2%.

Overall, these results indicate that Data Documenters and Data Managers rely on a combination of structured metadata practices, standards-based documentation and controlled vocabularies, complemented by manual and annotation-based methods that support the day-to-day organisation and interpretation of cultural heritage data.

Data management and storage

Institutional data governance within this profile appears uneven. Around one third of respondents (35.7%) report that their institution follows a published Data Management Plan, while a similar share (37.5%) indicate that no such framework exists and 26.8%

report uncertainty. This suggests that formal governance mechanisms are present in some institutional environments, but they are not systematically established across all contexts where Data Documenters and Data Managers operate (Figure 3.5).

D5. Does your institution follow a published Data Management Plan?	Count	%
No	21	37.5%
Yes	20	35.7%
I don't know	15	26.8%

Figure 3.5 Presence of a Data Management Plan (D5).

Storage practices reveal a distributed infrastructure combining institutional, repository-based and local environments. Institutional servers or organisational storage systems represent the most prominent configuration, with 69.6% of respondents indicating that they store at least half of their data within organisation-managed infrastructures. Domain-specific repositories are also widely used, with 23.2% reporting that a large share of their data is stored in these environments and 8.9% indicating that they store most or all of their datasets there.

Local storage also remains relevant. Approximately 51.8% of respondents report storing at least half of their data on local devices, while 39.3% indicate that local storage contains most or all of their datasets. Other environments appear more complementary than primary. Cloud-based commercial platforms are used by 17.9% of respondents for a large share of their data, while self-hosted cloud solutions account for 30.4% when considering cases where they are used for at least some datasets.

Overall, the storage landscape for this profile reflects a hybrid configuration in which institutional infrastructures and domain-specific repositories play a central role, complemented by local and cloud-based environments supporting operational workflows and data access.

Data sharing

Data sharing appears to be a widespread practice within this profile. A majority of respondents report that they sometimes share their data (66.1%), while a substantial share indicate that they always share their data (33.9%). No respondents report never sharing data (Figure 3.6).

D10. Do you share the data you produce?	Count	%
Yes, sometimes	37	66.1%
Yes, always	19	33.9%
No	0	0.0%

Figure 3.6 Data sharing practices (D10).

These results suggest that data circulation is broadly embedded within the workflows of Data Documenters and Data Managers. However, the predominance of the “sometimes” category indicates that sharing often occurs in a situational or context-dependent manner rather than as a fully systematic practice.

Overall, this pattern suggests that while data sharing is common across the profile, its regularity is shaped by institutional conditions, project contexts and operational requirements surrounding the management and dissemination of cultural heritage data.

Collaboration

Collaboration with development teams is a common practice within this profile and often takes place through structured and iterative forms of interaction. The most widespread modality consists of regular meetings and feedback sessions, reported by 67.9% of respondents, indicating that ongoing dialogue between users and developers plays an important role in shaping digital tools and infrastructures.

A substantial share of respondents (57.1%) also report direct involvement in testing and iterative development processes, suggesting that many participants contribute to refining tools through practical experimentation and feedback cycles. Collaborative platforms such as Slack, Trello, Jira or Figma are used by 42.9% of respondents, supporting coordination and communication within development environments (*Figure 3.7*).

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams?	Count	%
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	38	67.9%
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	32	57.1%
Using collaborative tools like Slack, Trello, or Jira, or Figma	24	42.9%
Through detailed requirement documentation	16	28.6%
Participation in workshops or hackathons	16	28.6%
Via email or written reports only	15	26.8%

Figure 3.7 Collaboration practices with development teams (E6).

Other forms of collaboration remain present but less dominant. Around 28.6% of respondents report working with development teams through detailed requirement documentation, while a similar share participates in workshops or hackathons (28.6%). More traditional and less interactive forms of communication, such as email exchanges or written reports only, are reported by 26.8% of respondents.

These responses point to a collaborative environment where Data Documenters, Data Managers and development teams is generally structured around continuous feedback, testing and coordinated interaction, supporting the refinement and improvement of digital systems used for documenting and managing cultural heritage data.

Institutional infrastructure & governance

Respondents in this profile are strongly involved in the management and configuration of institutional data infrastructures. The most commonly reported database architecture is the relational database, managed by 66.1% of respondents. Object-oriented databases are also widely used (50.0%), while graph databases and NoSQL databases are each reported by 14.3% of respondents. More specialised infrastructures such as distributed databases remain relatively limited (5.4%).

Semantic and structured knowledge approaches are also present within this profile. Nearly half of respondents (46.4%) report using ontological models such as CIDOC CRM or SKOS to structure and organise data.

Institutional curation practices further reflect a structured approach to data management. A majority of respondents (58.9%) indicate that their systems rely on standardised practices or formats for storing and curating data, while 73.2% report that their institutions have long-term solutions for archiving data, suggesting a strong institutional commitment to long-term preservation.

Access to institutional infrastructures is often controlled. The most common configuration consists of internal access restricted to institutional staff, reported by 75.0% of respondents. More flexible access models also exist, including open access after account creation (35.7%), limited access for specific professionals (42.9%), and access upon request (30.4%). Fully open access without account creation is reported by 60.7% of respondents (*Figure 3.8*).

F7. What are the possible access methods to your servers, databases or repositories?	Count	%
Internal access only - restricted to institution / organisation / company staff	42	75.0%
Open access - without account creation or registration	34	60.7%
Limited access - restricted to certain professionals	24	42.9%
Open access - after account creation or registration	20	35.7%
Access upon request	17	30.4%

Figure 3.8 Access methods to servers, databases and repositories (F7).

Overall, these results indicate that Data Documenters and Data Managers operate within relatively structured institutional infrastructures combining formal database systems, standardised data management practices and controlled access environments supporting the long-term preservation and governance of cultural heritage data.

Needs & expectations

Data documenters express needs centred on structuring, standardising and ensuring the long-term usability of data across systems and contexts.

The main difficulties relate to technical and infrastructure limitations, together with interoperability issues and the complexity of managing heterogeneous data and metadata. The effort required to ensure consistency, quality and proper documentation is significant, especially in environments where standards are not fully aligned. Skills gaps and training needs further affect the ability to implement effective documentation practices.

Financial constraints, limited human resources and organisational barriers also play a role, impacting the sustainability of documentation processes and the capacity to maintain high-quality data over time.

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for stronger interoperability and better integration between systems, supported by shared standards and metadata harmonisation. Training, documentation and capacity building are seen as essential to improve practices and reduce complexity. There is also a demand for more user-friendly tools and more accessible solutions (*Figure 3.9*).

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	12	40.0%
Training, documentation and capacity building	9	30.0%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	8	26.7%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	6	20.0%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	6	20.0%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	6	20.0%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	5	16.7%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	5	16.7%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	4	13.3%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	4	13.3%
Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	4	13.3%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	3	10.0%
Connectivity and offline functionality	1	3.3%

Figure 3.9 *Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3).*

Additional expectations include improved infrastructure and storage for long-term preservation, better data management and retrieval functionalities, and more sustainable and open solutions. Automation and advanced processing are mentioned, particularly in relation to metadata extraction and enrichment, but remain secondary to the need for standardisation, integration and usability.

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the Data Documenters and Data Managers profile reflects professionals who play a central role in structuring, documenting and maintaining cultural heritage data within institutional environments. Their practices are characterised by the systematic

use of metadata, documentation standards and controlled vocabularies, combined with active involvement in the management of databases and data infrastructures.

The results also show that these respondents often contribute to the development and configuration of digital tools, while collaborating with technical teams through iterative and feedback-oriented processes. At the same time, their work is embedded in hybrid storage environments that combine institutional servers, repositories and local infrastructures.

Taken together, these findings highlight a profile strongly oriented toward data stewardship, where the organisation, documentation and long-term management of datasets represent key components of professional practice in digital cultural heritage contexts.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the relationship between documentation practices (D8.1), semantic structuring (F2.3), and the presence of institutional Data Management Plans (D5).

The objective is to assess the degree of alignment between operational documentation activities, semantic structuring practices and formal governance frameworks within the Data Documenters profile, in order to identify whether increasing levels of structuring correspond to greater organisational maturity or whether these dimensions remain only partially connected.

Documentation (D8.1) × Use of ontological models (F2.3)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and semantic structuring reveals a weak and non-linear relationship within the Data Documenters profile (*Figure 3.10*).

Documentation D8.1 × Semantic structuring F2.3	Yes	No	I don't know	Answered No to F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	12	10	5	0
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	13	12	9	0
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	15	14	7	0
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	13	10	7	0
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	21	16	11	0
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	21	14	5	0
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	7	2	4	0
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	17	6	5	0

Figure 3.10 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and use of ontological models (F2.3)

Across the more informal documentation modalities – particularly simple notes, annotations and manual documentation – the distribution between respondents engaged and not engaged in semantic structuring remains relatively balanced. No clear predominance emerges, and a substantial proportion of respondents report uncertainty. This indicates that these practices, while widespread, are not inherently associated with structured semantic approaches and are often embedded in operational or individual workflows with limited formalisation.

A moderate shift can be observed in relation to intermediate documentation practices, such as the use of documentation systems, metadata creation and adherence to established standards. In these cases, the proportion of respondents reporting engagement in semantic structuring increases, particularly for standards-based practices. However, this increase remains partial: a significant share of respondents still report no involvement in semantic structuring, indicating that these practices do not systematically translate into formal semantic integration.

A more distinct pattern emerges only in the case of practices that are intrinsically semantic, particularly the use of controlled vocabularies. Here, the majority of respondents report engagement in semantic structuring, and the proportion of non-engagement decreases substantially. Automated documentation systems show a similar orientation, although their limited diffusion and higher levels of uncertainty suggest a more marginal and less consolidated configuration.

Overall, the table suggests that the relationship between documentation and semantic structuring is not progressive or cumulative. Rather than increasing steadily with the level of documentation formalisation, semantic structuring appears to be associated primarily with specific practices that explicitly embed semantic logic. As a result, documentation activities within this profile remain only partially aligned with semantic infrastructures, revealing a structural gap between documenting data and formally structuring it for interoperability and reuse.

Documentation (D8.1) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and the institutional presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a weak and inconsistent alignment within the Data Documenters profile (*Figure 3.11*).

Across informal documentation practices – including simple notes, annotations and manual documentation – the distribution between respondents reporting the presence and absence of a Data Management Plan remains relatively balanced, with a substantial proportion of uncertainty. In several cases, the absence of a DMP slightly prevails, indicating that these practices are largely embedded in operational workflows that are not systematically connected to formal governance frameworks.

A similar configuration persists across intermediate documentation practices, such as the use of documentation systems and metadata creation. In these cases, the proportion of respondents reporting the absence of a DMP remains equal to or higher than those reporting its presence. This suggests that even widely adopted and partially structured documentation activities do not necessarily correspond to institutionally formalised data management strategies.

A partial shift can be observed in relation to adherence to established standards, where the distribution between the presence and absence of a DMP becomes more balanced and the level of uncertainty decreases. However, this does not result in a clear predominance of structured governance environments, indicating that standards-based practices are not systematically embedded within formal data management frameworks.

Documentation (D8.1) × DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	10	9	8
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	11	15	8
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	12	13	11
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	10	11	9
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	16	20	12
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	17	16	7
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	2	8	3
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	13	11	4

Figure 3.11 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

More specialised practices display differentiated patterns. The use of controlled vocabularies shows a comparatively stronger association with the presence of a Data Management Plan, suggesting a closer alignment between semantic structuring and formal governance. By contrast, automated documentation systems are predominantly associated with the absence of a DMP, indicating that automation practices are not necessarily integrated within institutional data management strategies.

Overall, the table suggests that documentation practices within this profile are largely decoupled from formal governance frameworks. The presence of a Data Management Plan does not systematically correspond to more structured or advanced documentation approaches, highlighting a structural gap between operational documentation activities and institutional data management strategies.

Use of ontological models (F2.3) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between semantic structuring and the institutional presence of a Data Management Plan shows a clearer alignment compared to documentation-related practices (Figure 3.12).

Semantic structuring (F2.3) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Yes	14	8	4
No	4	10	4
I don't know	2	3	7
Answered No to F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?	0	0	0

Figure 3.12 Relationship between the use of ontological models (F2.3) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Respondents engaged in semantic structuring are more likely to report the presence of a Data Management Plan, although a significant proportion still operates without one. Conversely, among those not engaged in semantic structuring, the absence of a DMP clearly predominates, indicating a stronger association between non-semantic practices and non-structured governance environments.

A distinct pattern of uncertainty also emerges: respondents unsure about their involvement in semantic structuring tend to be equally uncertain about the presence of a Data Management Plan, suggesting limited awareness of both dimensions.

Overall, semantic structuring appears more closely connected to institutional governance than documentation practices. However, this relationship remains partial, indicating that semantic approaches are not yet systematically embedded within formal data management frameworks.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between access models (C4), data sharing practices (D10), and the presence of institutional Data Management Plans (D5).

The objective is to assess whether different access configurations and governance frameworks are associated with variations in data sharing behaviours within the Data Documenters profile, or whether these dimensions remain weakly connected.

Access models (C4) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between access models and data sharing practices shows a highly uniform configuration, with no variation in the occurrence of sharing across access types (Figure 3.13).

Given the absence of non-sharing cases, the analysis focuses on differences in the regularity of sharing. Across all access models, “Yes, sometimes” remains the dominant modality across all access models.

Access (C4) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
	Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	17	29
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	7	18	0
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	2	3	0
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	6	12	0
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	5	20	0
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	2	3	0
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	12	25	0
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	13	31	0

Figure 3.13 Relationship between access models (C4) and data sharing practices (D10)

Limited variation emerges across configurations. Open access environments – including free and open-access services and open-source software – show a slightly higher proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), while more restrictive models, such as licence-based services, are more concentrated in the “sometimes” category.

However, these differences remain marginal and do not significantly differentiate behaviours across access models. Overall, the results suggest that access configurations have only a limited influence on the regularity of sharing, which remains predominantly context-dependent across the profile.

Sharing (D10) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between data sharing practices and the institutional presence of a Data Management Plan shows no clear alignment within the Data Documenters profile.

Among respondents who report sharing data systematically (“Yes, always”), the distribution between the presence and absence of a Data Management Plan is evenly balanced. A similar pattern emerges for those who share data more occasionally (“Yes, sometimes”), where responses are distributed almost equally across the three categories, including a substantial proportion of uncertainty (*Figure 3.14*).

These results indicate that the presence of a Data Management Plan does not correspond to more consistent or systematic sharing behaviours. No clear gradient emerges between governance frameworks and the regularity of data sharing.

Sharing (D10) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Yes, always	8	8	3
Yes, sometimes	12	13	12
No	0	0	0

Figure 3.14 Relationship between data sharing practices (D10) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between storage infrastructures (D9) and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different storage configurations are associated with variations in the regularity of data sharing within the Data Documenters profile, and to identify whether specific infrastructural environments support more systematic sharing behaviours or whether sharing remains largely independent of storage conditions.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage infrastructures and data sharing practices shows limited differentiation across configurations (*Figure 3.15*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	8	21	0
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	6	7	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	3	7	0
Institutional servers or websites	13	26	0
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	7	5	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	7	5	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	1	1	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	3	1	0
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	5	12	0

Figure 3.15 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

Given the absence of non-sharing cases, the analysis focuses on variations in the regularity of sharing. Across most storage environments – including local storage,

institutional servers, commercial cloud platforms and self-hosted solutions – “Yes, sometimes” represents the dominant modality.

A more differentiated pattern emerges in repository-based and collaborative environments, where the proportion of respondents reporting systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) increases and, in some cases, becomes the prevailing modality. This suggests that infrastructures explicitly oriented toward access and dissemination may support more consistent sharing behaviours.

However, these differences remain moderate and do not fundamentally alter the overall pattern. Storage configurations appear to influence the regularity of sharing to a limited extent, while sharing practices remain largely context-dependent across infrastructural environments.

Comparative Analysis – Collaboration

This block examines the relationship between collaboration modalities (E6), documentation practices (D8.1), and data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different forms of collaboration are associated with variations in the structuring of documentation and in the regularity of data sharing within the Data Documenters profile, and to identify whether more interactive or technically oriented collaboration environments correspond to more structured or consistent practices.

Collaboration (E6) × Documentation (D8.1)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and documentation practices shows a largely stable internal distribution across all configurations, with only limited variation in proportional terms (*Figure 3.16*).

Across all forms of collaboration, metadata creation and adherence to established standards consistently represent the most prominent practices, while automated systems remain marginal. This hierarchy remains largely unchanged regardless of the collaboration modality, indicating that collaboration does not substantially alter the overall structure of documentation practices.

At the same time, some minor variations can be observed. More structured and tool-based collaboration environments show a slightly higher proportion of documentation system use, while less interactive modalities – particularly communication via email or written reports – display a relatively higher reliance on manual documentation and a lower use of structured systems. Workshop-based contexts show a slightly stronger presence of annotations and simple notes, alongside a lower use of controlled vocabularies.

Collaboration (E6) x Documentation (D8.1)	Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	27	23	19	34	30	17	21	8
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	21	20	16	29	24	15	17	6
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	14	13	12	22	20	16	14	4
Participation in workshops or hackathons	10	12	12	16	13	9	8	5
Through detailed requirement documentation	12	12	9	15	13	10	9	4
Via email or written reports only	13	11	7	13	12	4	8	3

Figure 3.16 Relationship between collaboration (E6) and data documentation practices (D8.1)

However, these differences remain limited and do not significantly affect the overall configuration. Documentation practices within the profile appear proportionally stable across collaboration settings, with only localised variations in the degree of structuring.

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and data sharing practices shows a generally consistent pattern, with limited but observable variation in the regularity of sharing (Figure 3.17).

Collaboration (E6) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	14	24	0
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	14	18	0
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	11	13	0
Participation in workshops or hackathons	6	10	0
Through detailed requirement documentation	8	8	0
Via email or written reports only	6	9	0

Figure 3.17 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across all collaboration types, “Yes, sometimes” remains the most frequent modality, confirming that sharing is predominantly situational. However, differences emerge in the proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”). More structured and technically oriented collaboration environments – such as collaborative tools, iterative development

processes and requirement documentation – show a comparatively higher share of respondents reporting consistent sharing behaviours.

By contrast, less structured or more traditional modalities, including regular meetings and workshop-based collaboration, display a slightly lower proportion of systematic sharing. Communication limited to email or written reports shows a similar distribution, without a substantial deviation from the overall pattern.

Overall, the results suggest that collaboration has a modest influence on the regularity of sharing. While more structured collaboration environments are associated with slightly more consistent sharing practices, these differences remain limited, and sharing continues to be predominantly context-dependent across all collaboration modalities.

Profile: Data Producers (Scientific)

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

C1.1a. Are you using data annotation and analysis tools or services?

→ Yes

C1.2a. Are you using 3D modeling and visualisation tools or services?

→ Yes

C1.3a. Are you using data management and storage tools or services?

→ Yes

C1.4a. Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?

→ Yes

Base: 86 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The Data Producers (Scientific) profile represents respondents who are actively involved in the production, processing, documentation and management of research data, particularly in technically advanced and scientifically oriented contexts. These respondents typically operate in research environments where multiple stages of the data lifecycle are combined, including data collection, analysis, documentation and storage.

Their work frequently involves the use of advanced digital tools and infrastructures supporting scientific research, data processing and the interpretation of cultural heritage information.

Overall, this profile reflects technically engaged research actors who contribute directly to the creation, analysis and management of digital cultural heritage data.

Summary of findings

Tools and services

Data Producers show extensive engagement with advanced digital tools, particularly in the domain of 3D and spatial technologies. Almost all respondents (94%) report using or being interested in tools for 3D scanning, modelling, rendering and reconstruction. A substantial proportion also use GIS and spatial representation tools (61%), LiDAR technologies (47%), and immersive environments such as VR, AR or MR (43%). BIM and HBIM tools are used by approximately one third of the profile (33%).

C1.1b. Are you using data annotation and analysis tools or services?	Count	%
Tools for manual annotation of digital assets (text, image, audio, 3D, etc.)	55	64.0%
Handwriting Recognition (HTR) / Optical Character Recognition (OCR)	15	17.4%
Automated content analysis of speech and textual resources (NLP, machine translation, etc.)	9	10.5%
Automatic shape / texture recognition	7	8.1%

Figure 4.1 Data annotation and analysis tools (C1.1b).

With respect to data annotation and analysis, manual annotation tools are the most widespread (64%), while automated approaches such as OCR/HTR (17%), natural language processing and automated content analysis (11%), and shape or texture recognition (8%) are used by smaller subsets of respondents (*Figure 4.1*).

In the area of data management and storage, respondents report using tools for data collection management and structuring (37%), resource storage and retrieval systems (33%), and data interoperability or API integration (30%). Formal knowledge representation tools are also present, with nearly half of the profile (49%) using or being interested in knowledge graphs and semantic web technologies, followed by taxonomies and controlled vocabularies (35%) and ontologies (16%).

Access models and authentication

Access to digital tools is predominantly based on open or low-barrier models. The vast majority of respondents (87%) use free, open-access services, while 64% rely on open-source software. At the same time, a significant share also uses paid or restricted models, including licence-based services (38%) and subscription-based services (31%), indicating a mixed access ecosystem.

Authentication practices are largely institutional and professional. Institutional logins are used by 72% of respondents, followed by Google-based authentication (61%), ORCID (38%) and Microsoft accounts (36%). Other enterprise single sign-on systems are also relatively common (27%), while consumer-oriented identity providers play a marginal role (*Figure 4.2*),

C6. How do you typically log in or authenticate when accessing digital tools and services?	Count	%
Institutional login (organisation account)	62	72.1%
Google	52	60.5%
ORCID	33	38.4%
Microsoft	31	36.0%
Other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO)	23	26.7%
Apple ID	8	9.3%
EU Login	8	9.3%
EduGAIN	4	4.7%
Facebook	4	4.7%

Figure 4.2 Authentication methods for accessing digital tools and services (C6).

Data production processes and objectives

Data production activities are diverse and often combined. The most common processes include digitisation, transcription and 3D or spatial documentation (79%), archival research (72%), and the processing or reprocessing of data created by others (63%). Fieldwork (59%), analytical and examination methods (52%), observational approaches (47%) and computational methods (41%) are also widely used (Figure 4.3).

D1. What processes do you typically use to produce data?	Count	%
Digitisation, transcription and 3D and spatial documentation	68	79.1%
Archival research (e.g., consulting historical records, documents, or archives)	62	72.1%
Processing data / resources created by others or reprocessing your own primary data (e.g., data reanalysis, comparative studies, data aggregation and enrichment, transformation, modeling, interpretation, synthesis or fusion)	54	62.8%
Fieldwork (e.g., on-site data collection or acquisition, conservation treatment documentation and monitoring)	51	59.3%
Examination / analysis (e.g., visual inspection, instrumental analysis, laboratory testing, material analysis and testing, imaging and spectroscopy methods)	45	52.3%
Observation (e.g., direct or indirect observation of phenomena or processes)	40	46.5%
Computational methods (e.g., simulations, algorithms, or modeling)	35	40.7%
Surveys / questionnaires (e.g., collecting data through participant responses)	27	31.4%
Experimental methods (e.g., controlled experiments or trials, material reconstructions, accelerated ageing tests)	21	24.4%
Interviews or focus groups (e.g., qualitative data collection through discussion)	21	24.4%
Crowdsourcing or citizen science (e.g., engaging non-specialists to gather data)	20	23.3%

Figure 4.3 Data production processes (D1).

The objectives of data production are multiple and overlapping. The primary objective for most respondents is answering scientific or research questions (80%). However, data are also produced for archiving or preservation purposes (71%), cataloguing and metadata creation (59%), education and training (54%), conservation or restoration

planning (52%), reporting (51%), public communication (49%) and decision support (43%). This confirms that data production serves a broad range of scientific, operational and societal functions.

A slight majority of respondents (52%) report that they directly process or analyse the data they produce, while 27% do so occasionally and 21% do not engage in data processing themselves. This indicates that, although data production is widespread, analytical autonomy varies across the profile.

Types, formats and documentation of data

Data Producers work with a highly heterogeneous data environment. The most frequently created, consulted or reused data types include historical or archival records (73%), textual information (69%), descriptive metadata (59%), published research outputs (54%) and spatial or geographical data (48%). Quantitative data (44%) and administrative or regulatory records (41%) are also common.

In terms of formats, image files (94%) and document formats (90%) are nearly universal. Spreadsheets (71%), presentations (73%), text-based formats such as CSV, XML or JSON (67%), and 3D models and renders (67%) are also widely used. A substantial proportion of respondents work with archived formats (66%), databases (58%), web formats (48%), audio (37%), geospatial formats (36%) and code or scripts (34%), reflecting a technically complex data landscape (*Figure 4.4*).

D4. What data types and formats do you commonly use? This question refers to the data you produce, consult or reuse the most in your daily activities.	Count	%
Image formats (JPEG/JPG, PNG, TIFF, JPEG2000, SVG)	81	94.2%
Document formats (PDF, RTF, Word files, LaTeX)	77	89.5%
Presentations (e.g., PowerPoint, Keynote)	63	73.3%
Spreadsheets (e.g., Excel, ODS)	61	70.9%
3D models and renders (e.g., OBJ, STL, PLY, 3DS, GLTF, VRML)	58	67.4%
Text-based formats (TXT, CSV, JSON, XML, RDF, YAML, XMP)	58	67.4%
Archived or compression formats (e.g., ZIP, TAR)	57	66.3%
Databases (e.g., SQL, NoSQL, SQLite, relational, non-relational)	50	58.1%
Video formats (MP4, MKV, AVI)	42	48.8%
Web formats and renders (e.g., HTML, JavaScript, SVG, JSON-LD, HTML5 Video/Audio, WebVR/WebAR, live streams)	41	47.7%
Audio files (e.g., MP3, WAV)	32	37.2%
Geospatial data formats (GeoJSON, Shapefile (SHP), KML, GML)	31	36.0%
Code or scripts (e.g., Python .py, SQL .sql, R, MATLAB .m, JavaScript .js, Jupyter .ipynb)	29	33.7%
Statistical and analytical dataset formats (SAV (SPSS), RData, HDF5, NetCDF)	17	19.8%

Streaming data formats (AVRO, Parquet, Protobuf, Kafka, WebSocket, MQTT, RTSP, HLS)	4	4.7%
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Figure 4.4 Data types and formats commonly used (D4).

Respondents predominantly operate in hybrid format environments, with the majority reporting the use of both open and closed formats (57%), while over one third mainly rely on open formats (36%).

Documentation practices are well established. Most respondents rely on manual documentation (59%), annotations directly on data (57%) and simple notes (56%). Nearly half systematically fill in metadata fields (47%) or follow established standards and protocols (43%). Structured documentation systems (37%), controlled vocabularies (30%) and automated documentation approaches (16%) are also in use.

Data management and storage

Formal data governance is uneven. Only 31% of respondents report following a published Data Management Plan, while 38% do not and 30% are unsure.

Storage practices show a strongly hybrid and distributed landscape. Local storage remains central, with 60% of respondents storing at least half of their data on personal devices. Institutional servers are almost equally prominent (56%), indicating a significant reliance on organisation-managed infrastructures. Cloud-based commercial platforms are used intensively by 38% of respondents, while self-hosted environments account for around 30% (Figure 4.5).

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (<50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	4 (4.7%)	30 (34.9%)	15 (17.4%)	37 (43.0%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	56 (65.1%)	19 (22.1%)	8 (9.3%)	3 (3.5%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	43 (50.0%)	29 (33.7%)	8 (9.3%)	6 (7.0%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	17 (19.8%)	36 (41.9%)	18 (20.9%)	15 (17.4%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	72 (83.7%)	10 (11.6%)	1 (1.2%)	3 (3.5%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	16 (18.6%)	22 (25.6%)	18 (20.9%)	30 (34.9%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	41 (47.7%)	33 (38.4%)	10 (11.6%)	2 (2.3%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	44 (51.2%)	31 (36.0%)	7 (8.1%)	4 (4.7%)

On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	34 (39.5%)	26 (30.2%)	12 (14.0%)	14 (16.3%)
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Figure 4.5 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9)

In contrast, public or domain-specific repositories are used as primary storage locations by a much smaller segment (around 15–16%), suggesting that open repositories are more often complementary rather than dominant storage solutions. Overall, storage practices appear fragmented across personal, institutional and commercial infrastructures.

Sharing and challenges

Data sharing is widespread: 96% of respondents share data either always (30%) or sometimes (66%). However, sharing is accompanied by several challenges. The most frequently reported issues relate to data or metadata quality (65%), confidentiality and privacy (55%), legal or contractual restrictions (54%), concerns about misuse (44%), lack of time or resources (43%), and technical barriers (41%). Infrastructure-related constraints and unclear sharing guidelines are also reported by a substantial proportion of respondents (*Figure 4.6*).

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data?	Count	%
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	56	65.1%
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	47	54.7%
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	46	53.5%
Concerns about data misuse	38	44.2%
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	37	43.0%
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	35	40.7%
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	32	37.2%
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	31	36.0%

Figure 4.6 Challenges in data sharing, consultation and reuse (D13).

Collaboration

Collaboration is a central feature of this profile. Half of the respondents engage through regular meetings and feedback loops, while 43% are directly involved in testing and iterative development processes. Collaborative tools are used by 28%, and workshops or hackathons by 27%. More traditional forms of collaboration, such as written documentation or email-based exchanges, remain relevant but less dominant (*Figure 4.7*).

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams?	Count	%
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	43	50.0%
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	37	43.0%

Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	24	27.9%
Participation in workshops or hackathons	23	26.7%
Through detailed requirement documentation	17	19.8%
Via email or written reports only	16	18.6%

Figure 4.7 Collaboration practices with development teams (E6).

Needs & expectations

The needs and expectations expressed by Data Producers reflect the complexity and breadth of their data production workflows, which combine analytical, computational and documentation-intensive processes.

The most recurrent difficulties relate to interoperability and system integration, particularly in contexts where multiple production methods coexist (e.g. digitisation, computational analysis, reprocessing of datasets). The heterogeneity of data types and workflows generates challenges in aligning tools, formats and infrastructures. Data quality, standardisation and the effort required to prepare datasets for reuse also emerge as consistent concerns, especially given the strong emphasis on research-driven outputs.

Financial and resource constraints, together with the need for specialised skills, represent another central issue. The combination of advanced methods (e.g. modelling, experimental analysis, 3D documentation) and diverse objectives (research, preservation, reporting, education) requires continuous training and access to adequate infrastructures, which are not always available.

Suggested improvements emphasise stronger interoperability between systems, better alignment with shared standards and more integrated data environments capable of supporting the full data lifecycle. Respondents also highlight the need for improved infrastructure, scalable storage solutions and more efficient workflows for data processing and reuse. Training and capacity-building remain important, alongside the availability of affordable or open-source solutions. Automation and advanced analytical functionalities are mentioned as enabling factors, but remain secondary to integration and infrastructure needs (*Figure 4.8*).

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	14	51.9%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	9	33.3%
Training, documentation and capacity building	8	29.6%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	7	25.9%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	6	22.2%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	6	22.2%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	5	18.5%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	5	18.5%

Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	5	18.5%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	4	14.8%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	4	14.8%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	4	14.8%
Connectivity and offline functionality	3	11.1%

Figure 4.8 Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3)

Overall conclusion

Data Producers (Scientific) constitute a technically advanced, research-driven and highly engaged group. They operate in complex data environments, combine multiple production processes, and work with a wide range of data types and formats. Documentation and sharing practices are well established, and collaboration is both frequent and structured.

At the same time, the results highlight structural challenges related to data governance, fragmentation of storage solutions, and constraints around sharing and reuse. Addressing these issues would significantly enhance the capacity of this group to operate efficiently, sustainably and at scale.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity

This block cross-analyses documentation practices (D8.1) with data sharing behaviour (D10), reported challenges (D13), and primary storage locations (D9, focusing on respondents reporting predominant use of each storage location).

The objective is to assess how documentation practices relate to data sharing, storage configurations and perceived challenges within this profile.

Documentation (D8.1) × Sharing (D10)

Data sharing is widespread across all documentation practices. Respondents who rely on manual documentation, annotations, simple notes, metadata, standards, documentation systems, controlled vocabularies or automated systems overwhelmingly report sharing the data they produce, either “always” or “sometimes” (Figure 4.9).

Documentation (D8.1) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	15	35	1
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	16	33	0
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	15	32	1
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	17	23	0
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	14	23	0
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	17	15	0
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	11	15	0
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	7	7	0

Figure 4.9 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and data sharing practices (D10)

However, a proportional gradient is visible. More structured documentation approaches – particularly documentation systems, automated systems, and systematic metadata practices – show a higher share of respondents reporting that they “always” share their data. Less formalised practices such as manual documentation or simple notes are more concentrated in the “sometimes” category. This suggests that documentation formalisation is associated less with the occurrence of sharing than with its regularity.

Documentation (D8.1) × Challenges (D13)

When documentation practices are cross-analysed with reported challenges when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13), a stable hierarchy of difficulties emerges across all configurations (*Figure 4.10*).

Documentation (D8.1) x Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	35	30	25	25	22	21	18	20	14
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	35	31	28	24	26	21	21	17	16
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	32	29	24	24	20	19	20	17	13
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	28	24	26	16	23	17	18	14	13
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	30	22	22	14	18	13	16	10	11
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	23	21	19	12	14	11	12	11	8
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	22	15	16	8	14	10	12	9	5
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	10	10	9	9	8	6	4	3	6

Figure 4.10 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

For every documentation practice, the most frequently reported challenge relates to: Data or metadata quality, reliability and completeness. This is consistently followed by Confidentiality or privacy concerns and Legal or contractual restrictions.

A second tier of challenges – including concerns about misuse, the additional effort required to prepare data for sharing, and technical barriers – is also widely reported across all documentation types.

Importantly, this hierarchy remains structurally consistent regardless of how respondents document the data they produce. The main obstacles to sharing, consulting and reusing data appear systemic and recurrent across documentation approaches.

Documentation (D8.1) × Where data are stored or archived (D9)

A structural alignment emerges between documentation formalisation and storage configuration.

Less formalised documentation practices (manual documentation, annotations, simple notes) are predominantly anchored in local storage environments. In contrast, more structured practices (systematic metadata use, adherence to standards, documentation systems and controlled vocabularies) show a stronger association with institutional server environments as their primary storage location.

Documentation (D8.1) x Storage (D9) <small>True for (50–75%) & True for (76–100%)</small>	Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN)	Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	Institutional servers or websites	Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	34	5	20	29	8	7	10	3	20
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	32	7	23	28	8	7	6	2	19
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	34	4	21	27	6	5	8	3	15
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	20	7	14	28	7	7	4	1	16
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	21	10	10	26	11	8	1	2	15
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	18	5	11	20	7	6	5	2	13
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	13	8	5	18	6	6	0	1	9
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	12	1	4	10	2	3	2	0	6

Figure 4.11 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and where data are stored or archived (D9)

Rather than a uniform hybrid pattern, the data indicate a shift from locally centred storage toward institutionally anchored infrastructures as documentation becomes more formalised. Repository-based and collaborative environments coexist with these configurations but do not replace the dominant local or institutional infrastructures.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between the institutional presence of a Data Management Plan (D5), documentation practices (D8.1), reported challenges (D13), and data sharing behaviour (D10).

The objective is to assess how institutional governance frameworks relate to documentation practices, data sharing behaviour and the challenges experienced within this profile

Documentation (D8.1) × Data Management Plan (D5)

A visible alignment emerges between structured documentation practices and respondents who report that their institution follows a published DMP (Figure 4.12).

Documentation (D8.1) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	14	24	13
Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	14	22	13
Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	13	21	14
Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	17	16	7
Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	17	15	5
Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	10	15	7
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	12	12	2
Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)	7	6	1

Figure 4.12 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Less formalised documentation approaches (manual documentation, annotations, simple notes) show a stronger concentration in the “No” and “I don’t know” categories regarding institutional DMP adoption. In contrast, more structured practices – such as systematic metadata use, adherence to standards, and controlled vocabularies – display a more balanced distribution between “Yes” and “No”, with lower levels of uncertainty.

This suggests that institutional governance frameworks and documentation structuring tend to co-occur. However, the relationship is not deterministic: structured documentation is also present in contexts where no institutional DMP is reported.

Challenges (D13) × Data Management Plan (D5)

When the distribution of reported challenges (D13) is examined in relation to the institutional presence of a published Data Management Plan (D5), the overall structure of difficulties remains largely unchanged (*Figure 4.13*).

Challenges (D13) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	20	22	14
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	13	22	12
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	14	16	16
Concerns about data misuse	14	14	10
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	13	14	10
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	14	11	10
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	12	9	11
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	9	9	13
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	6	10	9

Figure 4.13 Relationship between challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

The relative weight of most challenges is broadly comparable across respondents reporting the presence of a DMP, its absence, or uncertainty about it. No consistent proportional reduction in reported difficulties emerges in connection with institutional DMP adoption.

The only clear deviation concerns confidentiality and privacy (including GDPR), which are proportionally more frequently reported among respondents indicating that their institution does not follow a published DMP. This suggests that institutional governance frameworks may be associated with more structured handling – or at least reduced perceived uncertainty – regarding privacy-related issues.

Overall, institutional DMP adoption does not substantially reshape the pattern of reported challenges when sharing, consulting or reusing data.

Challenges (D13) x Sharing (D10)

When reported challenges (D13) are analysed in relation to data sharing behaviour (D10), a highly stable pattern emerges across all categories (*Figure 4.14*).

Challenges (D13) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, sometimes			No
	Yes, always			
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	20	35	1	
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	14	32	1	
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	14	31	1	
Concerns about data misuse	8	27	3	
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	12	24	1	
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	12	22	1	
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	9	22	1	
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	9	21	1	
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	7	17	1	

Figure 4.14 Relationship between challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13) and data sharing practices (D10)

For every type of challenge, the majority of respondents report that they share data “sometimes”, followed by a consistent but smaller proportion who report sharing “always”. Cases of non-sharing remain marginal across all configurations.

This indicates that the presence or type of challenge does not significantly differentiate sharing behaviour. Rather than preventing data sharing, challenges appear to affect its regularity.

However, some proportional variations can be observed. In particular, concerns related to data misuse show a relatively higher incidence of non-sharing and a lower proportion of systematic (“always”) sharing compared to other challenges. This suggests that issues related to misuse may introduce slightly greater hesitation or restriction in sharing practices.

Overall, the results suggest that data sharing remains widespread among Data Producers despite the difficulties encountered.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between predominant storage configurations (D9) and both data sharing behaviour (D10) and reported challenges when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13).

The objective is to assess how storage configurations relate to the regularity of data sharing and the distribution of challenges within this profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

Across all storage configurations, data sharing remains widespread. Cases of non-sharing are marginal regardless of where data are primarily stored (*Figure 4.15*).

Storage (D9) True for (50–75%) & True for (76–100%) X Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	17	33	2
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	6	5	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	10	23	0
Institutional servers or websites	14	34	0
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	7	7	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	5	7	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	5	6	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	3	1	0
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	7	18	1

Figure 4.15 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing (D10)

However, proportional differences emerge in the regularity of sharing. Respondents whose data are predominantly stored in repository-based environments (domain-specific or public repositories) show a higher proportional incidence of “always” sharing compared to those primarily relying on local storage or institutional servers, which are more concentrated in the “sometimes” category.

This suggests that repository-based storage configurations may be associated with more systematic sharing practices, while locally centred infrastructures are compatible with sharing but more often on an occasional basis.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The overall hierarchy of challenges remains stable across storage configurations. Data or metadata quality remains dominant regardless of where data are primarily stored, indicating that storage type does not alter the main structural concern (*Figure 4.16*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) X Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	32	26	26	26	21	21	14	19	17
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	11	4	6	3	6	5	5	3	2
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	21	19	22	17	14	15	11	13	10
Institutional servers or websites	32	29	24	18	21	21	19	17	15
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	12	4	6	3	5	3	4	3	4
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	11	6	8	4	8	4	4	4	2
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	6	6	4	5	3	7	4	6	3
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	4	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	1
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	19	14	14	12	15	9	11	13	10

Figure 4.16 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Differences emerge in the proportional intensity of secondary challenges. Respondents predominantly relying on local storage and institutional servers report a broader concentration of privacy, legal and misuse-related concerns. Repository-based environments, while still characterised by quality-related issues, show comparatively lower proportional incidence of privacy concerns.

Technical barriers display a relatively even distribution across storage types, with no strong structural differentiation.

Overall, storage configuration affects the clustering and intensity of certain challenges, particularly privacy-related issues, but does not fundamentally reshape the overall pattern of difficulties encountered when sharing, consulting or reusing data.

Comparative Analysis – Collaboration

This block cross-analyses collaboration modalities (E6) with documentation practices (D8.1) and data sharing behaviour (D10).

The objective is to assess how different forms of collaboration relate to the formalisation of documentation practices and the regularity of data sharing within this profile.

Collaboration (E6) × Documentation (D8.1)

A structural alignment emerges between the degree of collaborative structuring and the formalisation of documentation practices (*Figure 4.17*).

Collaboration (E6) X Documentation (D8.1)	Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	28	28	21	29	29	18	20	10
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	22	23	21	26	23	15	15	9
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	14	13	11	20	18	16	13	7
Participation in workshops or hackathons	13	17	15	17	17	11	12	7
Through detailed requirement documentation	14	13	6	13	12	9	6	4
Via email or written reports only	12	12	7	9	8	3	5	3

Figure 4.17 Relationship between collaboration (E6) and data documentation practices (D8.1)

More structured forms of collaboration – such as the use of collaborative tools, direct involvement in testing and iterative development, and participation in workshops – show a higher proportional concentration of systematic metadata use, adherence to standards and documentation systems.

By contrast, respondents reporting collaboration primarily via email or written reports display a stronger reliance on manual documentation and a lower proportional use of structured documentation systems.

This suggests that collaborative structuring and documentation formalisation tend to co-occur, indicating an alignment between organisational coordination practices and data documentation approaches.

Collaboration (E6) × Data Sharing (D10)

Data sharing remains widespread across all collaboration modalities. However, proportional differences emerge in the regularity of sharing (*Figure 4.18*).

Collaboration (E6) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	12	30	1
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	13	23	1
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	11	12	1
Participation in workshops or hackathons	8	15	0
Through detailed requirement documentation	7	9	1
Via email or written reports only	3	13	0

Figure 4.18 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data sharing practices (D10)

More structured collaboration environments – particularly those involving collaborative tools or formal requirement documentation – show a higher proportional incidence of respondents reporting that they “always” share the data they produce.

Conversely, respondents relying primarily on email-based collaboration display a lower proportional share of systematic (“always”) sharing.

Overall, collaboration structure appears associated not with whether data are shared, but with how consistently sharing occurs.

Profile: Emerging Professionals / Early Career

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

A1.2 – Age group

→ 18-25 / 26-35

A1.3 – Level of education

→ Bachelor / Master / Doctorate

Base: 98 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Emerging Professionals / Early Career* profile represents respondents who are in the initial phase of their professional trajectory, identified through age group and education level.

These respondents include students, doctoral candidates and early career professionals entering or consolidating their position within cultural heritage and related digital environments.

Their activities often take place within academic or early professional contexts where engagement with digital tools, infrastructures and research practices is still developing. Overall, this profile reflects a cohort of early career actors progressively integrating into digital cultural heritage ecosystems.

Summary of findings

Project engagement

Involvement in heritage-related projects among Emerging Professionals appears heterogeneous. Over half of respondents (53.1%) indicate that they are not currently involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or the Cultural Heritage Cloud (*Figure 5.1*).

A8. Are you involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or any other project relevant to the Cultural Heritage Cloud?	Count	%
Not applicable	52	53.1%
National	32	32.7%
European	22	22.4%
International	11	11.2%

Figure 5.1 *Involvement in Digital Cultural Heritage projects (A8).*

At the same time, nearly one third (32.7%) report participation in national projects, while engagement at the European level reaches 22.4%. International involvement remains more limited (11.2%). As multiple levels of engagement could be selected, these percentages reflect overlapping participation patterns.

Overall, the data suggest that while a substantial portion of the profile is not yet directly embedded in structured heritage project environments, a visible segment is already participating in national and transnational initiatives, indicating early integration into broader heritage ecosystems.

Tools and services

Engagement with production-oriented tools among Emerging Professionals shows a differentiated pattern, with stronger uptake in visual and spatial domains than in advanced analytical automation. Manual annotation tools represent the most established practice (46.9%). Automated approaches remain limited: automated content analysis tools reach 13.3%, OCR/HTR 11.2%, and automatic shape or texture recognition 3.1%. Approximately one quarter (25.5%) report not using annotation and analysis tools, indicating that this area is not yet uniformly embedded within the profile (*Figure 5.2*).

C1.1b. Are you using data annotation and analysis tools or services?	Count	%
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Tools for manual annotation of digital assets (text, image, audio, 3D, etc.)	46	46.9%
Answered "No" to C1.1a	25	25.5%
Automated content analysis of speech and textual resources (NLP, machine translation, etc.)	13	13.3%
Handwriting Recognition (HTR) / Optical Character Recognition (OCR)	11	11.2%
Automatic shape / texture recognition	3	3.1%

Figure 5.2 Data annotation and analysis tools (C1.1b).

By contrast, spatial and 3D technologies display broader diffusion. A majority (59.2%) report engagement with tools for 3D scanning, modelling, rendering and reconstruction. GIS reaches 37.8%, LiDAR 28.6%, immersive environments such as VR/AR/MR 27.6%, and BIM/HBIM 23.5%. Around one third report no engagement with 3D or spatial technologies. As multiple selections were possible, percentages reflect overlapping adoption patterns. These results suggest a clear orientation toward visual and spatial production environments.

Engagement with data management and formal knowledge tools appears more selective. Tools for data collection management and structuring reach 32.7%, interoperability and API integration 22.4%, and resource storage and retrieval systems 20.4%, while 24.5% report not using data management tools. Knowledge graphs reach 29.6%, taxonomies 15.3%, and ontologies 5.1%, with 50% indicating no use of formal knowledge representation tools. Overall, structured data management and semantic infrastructures are present but not yet consolidated within early career practices.

Access models and authentication

Access to digital tools among Emerging Professionals is predominantly structured around open and low-barrier models, while commercial and restricted configurations coexist within the same ecosystem.

A large majority of respondents (80.6%) report using free, open-access services. Open-source software is also widely adopted, reaching 58.2% of the profile. At the same time, mixed and commercial access models are clearly present: free-with-licence solutions are used by 44.9%, subscription-based services by 29.6%, and licence-based services by 28.6%. Developed in-house or custom-built tools are reported by 21.4%, whereas pay-per-use models remain marginal (5.1%) (Figure 5.3).

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	79	80.6%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	57	58.2%
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	44	44.9%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	29	29.6%

Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	28	28.6%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	21	21.4%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	15	15.3%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	5	5.1%

Figure 5.3 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4)

Authentication practices reflect a combination of institutional integration and reliance on major commercial identity providers. Institutional logins constitute the dominant method (68.4%), followed by Google-based authentication (53.1%). Microsoft accounts are used by 29.6% of respondents, while ORCID reaches 15.3%. Other systems, including EU-level and federated academic authentication tools, remain marginal.

Taken together, these patterns indicate that Emerging Professionals operate within hybrid access environments that combine institutional infrastructures, open ecosystems and widely used commercial platforms. Integration into existing digital systems appears well established, although engagement with research-specific or federated authentication mechanisms remains comparatively limited.

Documentation of data

Documentation practices among Emerging Professionals are present but predominantly informal in structure.

Simple notes represent the most widespread approach, reported by 53.1% of respondents. Manual documentation files are used by 40.8%, and annotations directly on data by 37.8%, indicating that documentation activity is commonly embedded within day-to-day workflows rather than externalised into structured systems (*Figure 5.4*).

D8.1. How do you typically document the data you produce?	Count	%
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	52	53.1%
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	40	40.8%
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	37	37.8%
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	27	27.6%
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	18	18.4%
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	15	15.3%
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	9	9.2%
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	4	4.1%

Figure 5.4 Data documentation practices (D8.1).

More formalised practices are less widespread. Just over one quarter (27.6%) report systematically filling in metadata fields, while 18.4% use dedicated documentation

systems. Adherence to established standards or protocols reaches 15.3%, and the use of controlled vocabularies 9.2%. Automated documentation systems remain marginal (4.1%).

Overall, documentation behaviour within this profile appears pragmatic and practice-driven. While documentation is not absent, structured, standard-based and systematised approaches remain limited, suggesting that formal data governance practices are still in an early stage of consolidation among Emerging Professionals.

Needs & expectations

Emerging professionals express needs strongly linked to their transitional position, combining active engagement with digital tools and limited experience, resources and institutional support.

The most prominent challenges relate to skills gaps and learning curves, combined with technical and infrastructure limitations. The adoption of digital tools is often slowed down by the need to acquire new competencies while simultaneously dealing with complex systems and insufficient hardware or computing capacity. Financial constraints further reinforce these barriers, limiting access to advanced tools and services.

Interoperability issues and data-related challenges (including access, standardisation and integration) also emerge as significant obstacles, particularly when working across multiple platforms or datasets. These issues directly affect efficiency and increase the effort required to produce, manage and reuse data (*Figure 5.5*).

C2. What difficulties do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?	Count	%
Skills, training and learning curve	16	40.0%
Technical, infrastructure and hardware limitations	15	37.5%
Financial constraints and costs	14	35.0%
Interoperability and system integration issues	13	32.5%
Usability and user experience limitations	11	27.5%
Data access and availability constraints	7	17.5%
Connectivity and access limitations	7	17.5%
Legal, copyright and data governance concerns	6	15.0%
Data quality, heterogeneity and standardisation issues	6	15.0%
Vendor dependency, tool sustainability and support limitations	5	12.5%
Human resources and staffing constraints	5	12.5%
Documentation, guidance and best practice gaps	5	12.5%
Organisational and policy barriers	4	10.0%
Domain-specific limitations and lack of fit	3	7.5%

Figure 5.5 Main difficulties in the use of digital tools and resources (C2).

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for stronger interoperability and more integrated systems, alongside improved user-friendliness and simplified interfaces to reduce entry barriers. Training, documentation and structured capacity-building opportunities are seen as essential to support skill development. There is also a clear demand for more accessible and affordable tools, as well as improved infrastructure and scalable storage solutions.

Additional expectations include better alignment with shared standards, improved data access and availability, and stronger organisational support. While advanced functionalities such as automation and AI are mentioned, they remain secondary to foundational needs such as usability, training and system integration.

Overall conclusion

Emerging Professionals / Early Career respondents represent a cohort with solid operational engagement, particularly in production-oriented and spatial technologies. However, the adoption of structured data management and formal knowledge representation tools remains partial, and documentation practices are predominantly informal.

While integration within open and institutional digital ecosystems is well established, the consolidation of governance-oriented and semantically structured approaches is still in progress. Strengthening interoperability, standard-based documentation and infrastructural awareness at this stage would enhance long-term alignment within digital cultural heritage environments.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the relationship between technological production practices (C1.2b), data management tools (C1.3b), documentation modalities (D8.1), and formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b).

The objective is to assess the internal alignment between data production, management, documentation and semantic structuring within the Emerging profile, in order to identify areas of coherence as well as potential gaps between technological adoption and organisational structuring.

3D modelling and visualisation (C1.2b) × Data management and storage (C1.3b)

The cross-analysis between 3D/spatial technologies and data management tools shows differentiated patterns within the Emerging profile (*Figure 5.6*).

Production tools (C1.2b) × Data management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
3D scanning or modeling, rendering and reconstruction	23	12	11	12
Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM)	11	6	4	2
Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LIDAR)	10	8	8	2
Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial representation of information	12	14	8	3
Virtual Reality (VR) / Augmented Reality (AR) / Mixed Reality (MR)	9	7	5	6
Answered NO to C1.2a	8	6	7	11

Figure 5.6 Relationship between 3D modelling and visualisation tools (C1.2b) and data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

Across most technologies, data collection management and structuring is the most recurrent management dimension.

A distinct pattern emerges for GIS, where data interoperability and API integration represent the most prominent associated dimension. This suggests that spatial technologies are more frequently embedded in integration-oriented environments compared to other 3D domains.

By contrast, in 3D scanning and modelling – and, proportionally, in VR/AR/MR – a relatively high share of respondents report not using data management tools at all (C1.3a = No). In these cases, technologically advanced production practices are not consistently matched by structured management infrastructures.

Overall, the table indicates that within the Emerging profile, alignment between technological production and data management is uneven. Integration-oriented practices are concentrated in specific domains (notably GIS), while in other areas production appears to precede management consolidation.

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and formal knowledge representation tools shows a stable internal hierarchy within the Emerging profile (Figure 5.7).

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)	Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data	Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies	Ontologies	Answered NO to C1.4a
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	16	9	2	25
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	12	6	1	18
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	12	9	2	17
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	7	3	1	7
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	8	7	3	9
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	5	3	2	5
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	1	1	1	1
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	2	2	2	3

Figure 5.7 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and the use of formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b)

In the three more informal documentation modalities – simple notes, annotations and manual documentation – the share of respondents not using formal knowledge tools is comparatively higher than in other groups. This indicates a weaker alignment between informal documentation and formal knowledge representation.

Across all practices, knowledge graphs remain the most recurrent formal tool, followed by taxonomies and controlled vocabularies, while ontologies are consistently marginal. No documentation modality alters this order.

A slight variation appears in filling in metadata, where knowledge graphs and taxonomies reach nearly equivalent levels and the overall distribution among formal tools is more balanced.

Overall, formal knowledge representation is present but not systematic within the Emerging profile, and its use increases modestly with more structured documentation practices.

Comparative Analysis – Governance and Institutional Anchoring Block

This block examines the relationship between access models for digital tools and services (C4), authentication modalities (C6), and data management tools (C1.3b).

The objective is to assess whether different access configurations are associated with variations in authentication practices and in the structuring of data management within the Emerging profile.

Access models (C4) × Authentication (C6)

The cross-analysis between access models and authentication modalities reveals a stable overall structure, in which Institutional Login and Google-based authentication consistently represent the dominant access points across all configurations (Figure 5.8).

Access models (C4) × Authentication (C6)	Apple ID	EduGAIN	Eulogin	Facebook	Google	Institutional Login (log in using your organisation's credentials)	Microsoft	ORCID	Other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO)
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	11	1	3	5	45	55	27	14	6
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	7	0	1	5	26	32	14	9	5
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	2	0	1	1	13	9	2	1	1
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	5	0	2	3	18	20	9	4	5
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	2	0	2	2	12	21	8	7	6
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	1	0	0	1	2	4	3	1	2
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	4	1	0	0	6	18	3	5	3
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	7	0	3	5	33	38	17	10	9

Figure 5.8 Relationship between access models (C4) and authentication methods (C6)

However, a more detailed examination of proportional distributions highlights variations in how authentication is configured within different access environments.

In-house or custom-built tools display a stronger concentration around institutional login, with comparatively lower reliance on external identity providers.

By contrast, trial-based access models show a stronger proportional reliance on widely used external providers, particularly Google, indicating a more platform-oriented and less institutionally integrated environment.

Open-source environments present a more distributed configuration, with a comparatively higher proportional presence of Microsoft-based authentication alongside institutional and Google-based access.

Overall, while the dominant authentication structure remains stable, different access models are associated with variations in the relative balance between institutional and external identity systems.

Access models (C4) × Data management and storage (C1.3b)

The cross-analysis between access models and data management tools reveals differentiated but moderate patterns across digital ecosystems (*Figure 5.9*).

Open access configurations – including free, open-access services and open-source software – show a consistent predominance of data collection management and structuring. In these environments, interoperability and storage functions are present but secondary, and a non-negligible share of respondents report not using data management tools.

Paid subscription-based services display a different orientation. Here, resource storage and retrieval systems become the most prominent dimension, with interoperability also exceeding data collection. This suggests a stronger infrastructural focus associated with subscription-based environments.

A distinct configuration emerges in the case of in-house or custom-built tools. In this context, data interoperability and API integration represent the most recurrent dimension, while the proportion of respondents not using data management tools is comparatively lower. This indicates a more integration-oriented configuration within internally developed environments.

Paid licence-based services show a more balanced distribution across collection, interoperability and storage, without a clearly dominant dimension.

Overall, while differences across access models are not radical, the data indicate that the type of digital ecosystem is associated with variations in the orientation of data management practices, ranging from operational structuring to infrastructural storage and system integration.

Access (C4) × Data management tools (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	28	19	16	16
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	15	12	8	9
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	4	5	3	3
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	6	8	10	5
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	8	8	7	5
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	2	2	1	0
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	4	9	5	3
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	20	14	11	12

Figure 5.9 Relationship between access models (C4) and the use of data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

Profile: Freelance & Self-Employed

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

A2 – Working status

- Business owner / Entrepreneur
- Self-employed / Freelancer

D1. How do you typically produce data in your professional activity?

- Fieldwork
- Observation
- Examination / analysis
- Interviews or focus groups

D2. What is your primary objective when producing data?

- Preparing reports
- Creating conservation or restoration plans
- Supporting decision-making
- Monitoring and evaluation
- Public communication or awareness

Base: 104 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The Freelance / Self-Employed Users profile represents respondents working as independent professionals or entrepreneurs across different cultural heritage activities. Their work is typically organised around project-based or client-driven assignments rather than institutional infrastructures.

These respondents frequently produce data through fieldwork, observation, examination or interviews, and their data production activities are often linked to applied objectives such as reporting, conservation planning, monitoring, decision-making or communication tasks.

Overall, this profile reflects independent professionals whose data practices are shaped by project requirements, client needs and varying levels of access to technical resources or digital infrastructures.

Summary of findings

Tools and services

Freelance respondents report using a wide range of digital tools supporting different stages of digital heritage work. Within annotation and analysis activities, the most common tools are manual annotation systems for digital assets (50.0%), while more specialised automated analysis approaches such as natural language processing tools (10.6%), OCR/HTR technologies (11.5%), and automatic shape or texture recognition (2.9%) appear less widespread.

In terms of visualisation and spatial technologies, several tools are widely reported. 3D scanning and modelling technologies are used or of interest to 61.5% of respondents, while GIS tools (40.4%), LIDAR technologies (39.4%), and VR/AR/MR environments (36.5%) are also relatively common. BIM/HBIM systems are mentioned by a smaller share of respondents (27.9%).

For data management and storage tools, respondents most often report using or being interested in data collection management and structuring tools (33.7%) and resource storage and retrieval systems (32.7%), while interoperability and API integration tools (13.5%) are less frequently mentioned (*Figure 6.1*).

C1.3b. What data management and storage tools or services do you use or would like to use?	Count	%
Data collection, management and structuring	35	33.7%
Resource storage and retrieval systems	34	32.7%
Answered "No" to C1.3a. Are you using data management and storage tools or services?	21	20.2%
Data interoperability and API integration	14	13.5%

Figure 6.1 Data management and storage tools and services (C1.3b).

Finally, within knowledge representation technologies, knowledge graphs and linked data approaches (36.5%) appear most prominent, followed by taxonomies and controlled vocabularies (17.3%), while ontologies (3.8%) are used by a smaller share of respondents.

Overall, these results indicate that freelance and self-employed professionals engage with a diverse set of digital tools, combining practical annotation and visualisation technologies with more specialised infrastructures for data management and knowledge representation.

Access models and authentication

Freelance and self-employed professionals primarily rely on open and easily accessible digital tools. The large majority of respondents report using free, open-access services (81.7%), confirming the importance of low-cost or freely available infrastructures for professionals operating outside institutional environments. Other commonly used models include free tools with licensing conditions (48.1%) and open-source software (48.1%), suggesting that flexible and adaptable tools are widely adopted.

Paid solutions are also present but appear less dominant. Subscription-based services (35.6%) and paid licence-based tools (33.7%) are reported by roughly one third of respondents, while trial-based services (17.3%), in-house or custom-built tools (21.2%), and pay-per-use systems (7.7%) remain less common.

Authentication practices reflect the heterogeneous environments in which freelancers operate. The most common login methods are Google accounts (69.2%) and institutional credentials (47.1%), followed by Microsoft accounts (39.4%). A range of additional authentication systems are also used, including Apple ID (25.0%), other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions (18.3%), Facebook (16.3%), and ORCID (15.4%), while Eulogin (8.7%) remains less widespread (*Figure 6.2*).

C6. How do you typically log in or authenticate when accessing digital tools and services?	Count	%
Google	72	69.2%
Institutional Login (log in using your organisation's credentials)	49	47.1%
Microsoft	41	39.4%
Apple ID	26	25.0%
Other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO)	19	18.3%
Facebook	17	16.3%
ORCID	16	15.4%
Eulogin	9	8.7%
EduGAIN	0	0.0%

Figure 6.2 Authentication methods for accessing digital tools and services (C6).

These responses highlight that freelance professionals depend heavily on open-access and widely available digital ecosystems, while combining multiple authentication systems depending on the platforms and services they access.

Reuse of self-produced data

Freelance and self-employed respondents show a strong tendency to reuse data they have previously produced. Half of respondents report reusing their own data in some of their projects (<50%) (50.0%), while 48.1% indicate that they reuse their own datasets in the majority of their work, including 26.9% for a large part of their projects (50–75%) and 21.2% for most or all projects (76–100%).

Only a very small minority state that they never reuse previously produced data (1.9%) (Figure 6.3).

D15. Do you reuse your own data? Are you the main author of the data you reuse?	Count	%
Yes, for some of my projects (< 50%)	52	50.0%
Yes, for a large part of my projects (50 - 75%)	28	26.9%
Yes, for all or most of my projects (76 - 100%)	22	21.2%
I never reuse my old data (0%)	2	1.9%

Figure 6.3 Reuse of own data (D15)

Overall, these results suggest that self-produced datasets often represent an important knowledge base and working resource for freelance professionals, who frequently build new work on top of data generated in earlier projects.

Types, formats and documentation of data

Freelance and self-employed respondents report working with a wide variety of data types, often combining historical, textual and observational sources (Figure 6.4).

D3. What types of data do you typically create, consult or reuse?	Count	%
Historical or archival records (legacy information, records from the past)	77	74.0%
Textual or written information (e.g., narratives, documentation, reports, articles)	71	68.3%
Published research outputs (previously disseminated academic or scientific findings)	62	59.6%
Observational findings (field notes, natural observations, event logs)	53	51.0%
Administrative or regulatory records (government data, legal information, regulations)	39	37.5%
Spatial / geographical information (location-based data, maps, geographic features)	39	37.5%
Quantitative data (numerical data, statistics, measured values)	32	30.8%
Experimental results (outcomes from controlled, reproducible experiments)	31	29.8%
Descriptive metadata (summaries or categorisations of datasets)	29	27.9%
Structural or spatial representations (conceptual models, spatial relationships)	26	25.0%

Survey and interview responses (data from consultations, interviews, or polls)	26	25.0%
Environmental measurements (data from ecological monitoring or natural systems)	22	21.2%
Social or behavioural information (data from social networks, behavioural studies)	16	15.4%
Machine-generated insights (automated logs, data from sensors or IoT devices)	11	10.6%
Biological or genomic information (DNA sequences, biological samples, genetic data)	4	3.8%

Figure 6.4 *Types of data created, consulted or reused (D3).*

The most frequently reported data types include historical or archival records (74.0%), textual or written information (68.3%), and published research outputs (59.6%). Observational findings (51.0%) are also widely used, while other data types such as administrative records (37.5%), spatial or geographical information (37.5%), and quantitative data (30.8%) appear in smaller but still relevant shares. Other forms of data, including environmental measurements (21.2%), survey responses (25.0%), and experimental results (29.8%), indicate the diversity of materials handled by freelance professionals.

In terms of data formats, respondents most commonly report using a combination of open and closed formats (43.3%), while 34.6% primarily use open formats. A smaller share indicate reliance mainly on closed or proprietary formats (7.7%), and 14.4% report uncertainty about the type of formats they use.

Documentation practices tend to rely on relatively simple approaches. The most common method consists of simple notes (54.8%), followed by manual documentation files (44.2%) and annotations directly within data or files (40.4%). More structured documentation practices appear less common, including metadata creation (22.1%) and the use of documentation systems (20.2%). Formalised approaches such as documentation standards (10.6%), controlled vocabularies (8.7%), and automated documentation systems (5.8%) are reported by smaller shares of respondents.

Taken together, these findings suggest that freelance professionals work with diverse and heterogeneous data sources, often relying on flexible documentation practices and mixed-format environments rather than highly standardised data management frameworks.

Data management and storage

Formal data management frameworks appear relatively uncommon among freelance and self-employed respondents. Only 4.8% report that their organisation follows a published Data Management Plan, while a clear majority indicate that no DMP is in place (62.5%), and 32.7% are unsure whether such a framework exists.

Storage practices are strongly centred on local environments. A large majority of respondents report storing more than half of their datasets locally (74.0%), indicating

that personal devices and locally managed storage remain the primary infrastructure for managing data. Commercial cloud platforms also play a role, with 50.9% indicating that more than half of their data are stored on services such as Google Drive or Dropbox. Other infrastructures appear less central: institutional servers (24.0%) and self-hosted servers (25.0%) are used for the majority of datasets by smaller shares of respondents, while domain-specific repositories (2.9%) and generic open repositories (4.8%) are rarely used as primary storage environments (Figure 6.5).

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (<50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	8 (7.7%)	19 (18.3%)	10 (9.6%)	67 (64.4%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	92 (88.5%)	9 (8.7%)	3 (2.9%)	0 (0.0%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	82 (78.8%)	17 (16.3%)	3 (2.9%)	2 (1.9%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	22 (21.2%)	29 (27.9%)	23 (22.1%)	30 (28.8%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	94 (90.4%)	5 (4.8%)	3 (2.9%)	2 (1.9%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	54 (51.9%)	25 (24.0%)	10 (9.6%)	15 (14.4%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	84 (80.8%)	18 (17.3%)	2 (1.9%)	0 (0.0%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	54 (51.9%)	33 (31.7%)	9 (8.7%)	8 (7.7%)
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	50 (48.1%)	28 (26.9%)	9 (8.7%)	17 (16.3%)

Figure 6.5 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9).

A similar pattern appears in relation to access to secondary datasets. Most respondents report accessing more than half of the data they reuse locally (72.1%), while commercial cloud platforms are used for the majority of datasets by 47.1% of respondents. Access through institutional infrastructures (25.9%) or open repositories (8.7%) remains more limited, while collaborative platforms such as GitHub or Wikidata (9.6%) and social networks (23.1%) play a secondary role.

This pattern indicates that freelance professionals rely primarily on personal and cloud-based infrastructures for both storing and accessing data, while institutional repositories and specialised infrastructures are used less frequently within this profile.

Data sharing, licensing and challenges

Data sharing is relatively common among freelance respondents, although it often occurs in a flexible or context-dependent way. A large majority report that they sometimes share their data (75.0%), while 19.2% indicate that they always share their data. Only a small minority report not sharing their data (5.8%).

Sharing conditions vary considerably. Fully open sharing appears limited: only 36.5% report sharing more than half of their data openly without restrictions. Similarly, sharing under open licences remains relatively restricted, with 22.1% reporting that they apply open licences to the majority of their datasets. Other sharing models are more frequent. For instance, sharing upon request (27.8%) and sharing for specific purposes (42.3%) are more commonly used for a large share of datasets. Practices such as restricted access (19.2%) or formal agreements (26.9%) also appear in a portion of cases. In contrast, models such as embargo periods (9.6%) or anonymisation prior to sharing (9.6%) are rarely applied to the majority of datasets (Figure 6.6).

D12. Under which conditions do you typically share your data?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	32 (30.8%)	34 (32.7%)	18 (17.3%)	20 (19.2%)
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	63 (60.6%)	18 (17.3%)	17 (16.3%)	6 (5.8%)
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	50 (48.1%)	34 (32.7%)	10 (9.6%)	10 (9.6%)
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	52 (50.0%)	24 (23.1%)	17 (16.3%)	11 (10.6%)
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	82 (78.8%)	12 (11.5%)	8 (7.7%)	2 (1.9%)
Upon request only	33 (31.7%)	42 (40.4%)	12 (11.5%)	17 (16.3%)
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	24 (23.1%)	36 (34.6%)	25 (24.0%)	19 (18.3%)
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	77 (74.0%)	17 (16.3%)	5 (4.8%)	5 (4.8%)

Figure 6.6 Conditions for data sharing (D12).

Respondents also identify several obstacles affecting data sharing and reuse. The most frequently reported challenges include legal or contractual restrictions (50.0%), confidentiality or privacy concerns (49.0%), and concerns about potential data misuse (48.1%). Practical barriers are also common, including the effort required to prepare data for sharing (44.2%), lack of appropriate infrastructures (42.3%), and technical limitations (40.4%). Other issues include data quality concerns (40.4%), unclear sharing guidelines (33.7%), and the presence of non-digitised resources (28.8%).

Overall, these findings suggest that while freelance professionals frequently share data, this sharing tends to occur through selective or conditional mechanisms, shaped by legal constraints, practical limitations and the absence of consistent infrastructures for open data management.

Collaboration

Collaboration with developers or technical teams appears relatively limited within this profile. The most common form of interaction consists of regular meetings and feedback sessions (20.2%), followed by direct involvement in testing and iterative development processes (15.4%) (*Figure 6.7*).

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams?	Count	%
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	21	20.2%
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	16	15.4%
Through detailed requirement documentation	10	9.6%
Using collaborative tools like Slack, Trello, or Jira, or Figma	8	7.7%
Via email or written reports only	7	6.7%
Participation in workshops or hackathons	5	4.8%

Figure 6.7 Collaboration practices with development teams (E6).

Other forms of collaboration are less frequent. Some respondents report contributing through requirement documentation (9.6%), while smaller shares indicate the use of collaborative platforms such as Slack or Trello (7.7%) or email-based communication (6.7%). Participation in workshops or hackathons (4.8%) is reported only occasionally.

Overall, these results suggest that freelance and self-employed professionals tend to interact with development teams mainly through consultative or feedback-oriented roles, rather than through sustained participation in technical development processes.

Needs & Expectations

Freelance and employed professionals express needs closely tied to practical constraints, balancing operational efficiency with limited resources and autonomy.

The main challenges relate to financial constraints, technical and infrastructure limitations, and the need to continuously acquire new skills. The learning curve remains significant, particularly when tools are complex or not tailored to their specific professional needs. Interoperability issues and connectivity limitations further complicate workflows, especially when working across multiple tools and environments.

Usability issues also play an important role, as non-intuitive interfaces increase the time and effort required to adopt and effectively use digital solutions. Human resource limitations and the lack of institutional support amplify these challenges, particularly for independent professionals.

In terms of expectations (*Figure 6.8*) respondents emphasise the need for more user-friendly and accessible tools, alongside improved interoperability and integration between systems. There is also a strong demand for more affordable solutions and flexible pricing models adapted to smaller organisations or individual professionals.

Training and documentation are considered essential to support effective use, while improved infrastructure and scalable storage are also relevant. Additional expectations include better data management and sharing functionalities, as well as more sustainable and open solutions. Advanced functionalities such as automation and AI are mentioned, but remain secondary to usability, cost and integration needs.

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	16	38.1%
Interoperability and integration between systems	15	35.7%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	11	26.2%
Training, documentation and capacity building	10	23.8%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	8	19.0%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	8	19.0%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	7	16.7%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	7	16.7%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	7	16.7%
Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	7	16.7%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	6	14.3%
Connectivity and offline functionality	5	11.9%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	5	11.9%

Figure 6.8 Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3)

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the Freelance and Self-Employed profile reflects professionals who operate in highly flexible and often independent working environments, relying heavily on accessible digital tools and self-managed infrastructures. Their workflows combine diverse types of data—particularly historical, textual and observational materials—with a wide range of digital tools supporting annotation, visualisation and data management activities.

The results highlight a strong reliance on open and freely accessible tools, as well as on personal and cloud-based infrastructures for storing and accessing data. Formal governance mechanisms such as Data Management Plans or institutional repository infrastructures appear less central, reflecting the limited institutional support structures typically available to freelance professionals.

At the same time, data sharing practices remain relatively widespread but are often conditional and context-dependent, shaped by legal constraints, technical limitations

and the resources required to prepare datasets for publication. Respondents also emphasise challenges related to financial constraints, interoperability issues and skills development, pointing to the need for more accessible tools, improved technical integration and stronger training opportunities.

Taken together, these findings suggest that freelance professionals play an important role in producing, interpreting and reusing cultural heritage data, while navigating complex technological and organisational environments with limited institutional infrastructures.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This section explores the relationship between documentation practices (D8.1), storage environments (D9), reuse behaviours (D15), and the presence of Data Management Plans (D5).

The objective is to assess the extent to which operational practices – including documentation and data reuse – are structured and consistently implemented, and to identify whether they are supported by formal governance frameworks within the freelance context.

Documentation (D8.1) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and data sharing reveals a consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant modality. This indicates that sharing remains largely occasional, regardless of the type of documentation approach adopted.

Documentation (D8.1) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	8	46	3
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	9	31	2
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	11	33	2
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	6	15	0
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	6	15	2
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	3	7	1
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	2	4	0
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	2	7	0

Figure 6.9 Relationship between data documentation (D8.1) and data sharing practices (D10)

At the same time, a gradual variation emerges in relation to the level of formalisation of documentation practices. Less structured approaches, such as simple notes, are associated with lower levels of systematic sharing, while more formalised practices – including the use of documentation systems, metadata, and established standards – show a higher proportion of “Yes, always” responses. This suggests that increased structuring of documentation is associated with more regular sharing behaviours.

Across all practices, the proportion of “No” responses remains consistently low, indicating that data sharing is rarely absent, even when documentation is limited or informal.

Overall, the results suggest that while data sharing is generally present but not fully systematic, more structured and formalised documentation practices contribute to a greater regularity in sharing activities within this profile.

Documentation (D8.1) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a clear lack of alignment between operational activities and formal governance frameworks (*Figure 6.10*).

Documentation (D8.1) × DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	2	37	18
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	3	24	15
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	2	29	15
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	1	11	9
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	2	9	12
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	0	6	5
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	0	3	3
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, GEN TC 346, etc.)	0	3	6

Figure 6.10 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Across all documentation practices, the absence of a Data Management Plan represents the most frequent condition, while the proportion of respondents reporting its presence remains consistently minimal. This is consistent with the freelance nature of this profile, which typically operates outside institutional environments where such governance frameworks are more commonly implemented.

At the same time, a substantial proportion of respondents report uncertainty regarding the existence of a DMP, particularly in relation to more structured practices such as metadata creation, the use of standards, and controlled vocabularies. This suggests limited awareness of governance conditions, even where more advanced documentation approaches are in place.

No clear relationship emerges between the level of formalisation of documentation practices and the presence of a Data Management Plan. More structured approaches do not correspond to higher levels of governance, pointing to a disconnect between the development of documentation practices and institutional planning.

Overall, the results indicate that documentation within this profile is largely driven by practical needs rather than formal governance frameworks, highlighting a significant gap between operational practices and structured data management planning.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Reuse (D15)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and data reuse practices shows that reuse is widely present across all configurations, with only a very limited proportion of respondents reporting that they never reuse their data. This indicates that reuse represents a common practice within this profile, regardless of the storage environment adopted (Figure 6.11).

At the same time, reuse is most frequently reported as partial, with the majority of respondents indicating that they reuse data in less than half of their projects. This pattern is particularly evident in more commonly used environments such as local and cloud-based storage, where reuse appears to be present but not fully systematic.

A more balanced distribution emerges in institutional and self-hosted environments, where higher levels of reuse – including reuse in most or all projects – are comparatively more frequent. This suggests that more structured or controlled storage configurations may support more consistent reuse practices.

Overall, the results indicate that while data reuse is a widespread activity among freelancers, it tends to remain occasional rather than systematic, with only limited evidence of fully integrated reuse practices across projects.

Storage (D9) × Reuse (D15)	Yes, for some of my projects (< 50%)	Yes, for a large part of my projects (50 - 75%)	Yes, for all or most of my projects (76 - 100%)	I never reuse my old data (0%)
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	33	24	19	1
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	1	1	0	1
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	26	18	9	0
Institutional servers or websites	9	8	7	1
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	2	3	0	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	0	1	1	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	8	6	2	1
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	1	2	1	1
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	10	7	9	0

Figure 6.11 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data reuse practices (D15)

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This section examines the relationship between licensing conditions (D12) and data sharing practices (D10), as well as the challenges (D13) associated with different governance approaches.

The objective is to assess whether varying degrees of openness and restriction in data licensing influence the regularity of sharing and the nature of the barriers encountered within this profile.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and data sharing practices reveals a consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant mode of sharing. This indicates that data sharing remains largely occasional, regardless of the type of licensing applied (*Figure 6.12*).

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) X Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	11	25	2
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	9	13	1
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	2	18	0
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	5	20	3
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	5	5	0
Upon request only	5	22	2
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	11	32	1
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	3	7	0

Figure 6.12 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and data sharing practices (D10)

At the same time, some variation emerges in relation to the level of openness of licensing conditions. More open approaches – such as unrestricted sharing or the use of open licenses – are associated with higher proportions of “Yes, always” responses, suggesting that fewer constraints support more regular sharing practices. In contrast, more restrictive conditions – including access limitations, formal agreements, or sharing upon

request – are associated with lower levels of systematic sharing and a stronger reliance on occasional practices.

Across all licensing models, however, the proportion of respondents who do not share data remains consistently low, indicating that sharing is rarely absent even in the presence of restrictions.

Overall, the results suggest that while licensing conditions influence the regularity of data sharing, they do not determine its occurrence. Data sharing is widely practiced within this profile, but it remains predominantly situational, with more open licensing frameworks supporting a greater degree of continuity.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and perceived challenges reveals a broadly uniform distribution across all configurations, with no single barrier clearly dominating within any specific licensing model (*Figure 6.13*).

Licensing (D12) True for (50–75%) & True for (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	13	13	17	16	18	17	12	18	11
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	14	16	12	12	9	10	7	8	9
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	11	11	10	11	10	10	6	11	7
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	16	19	16	14	13	11	9	17	8
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	6	5	6	4	4	7	4	6	2
Upon request only	14	15	11	15	11	12	6	13	12
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	20	27	22	23	24	18	13	18	10
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	5	6	6	9	4	3	4	3	4

Figure 6.13 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Across all licensing approaches – from fully open to more restricted or conditional forms – the relative weight of different challenges remains remarkably consistent. Issues related to privacy, legal constraints, effort required for data preparation, and concerns about misuse tend to appear with slightly higher proportions, but without significant variation between licensing types. Other challenges, including technical limitations,

infrastructure gaps, and data quality concerns, are also consistently represented across configurations.

This overall stability suggests that the type of licensing applied does not substantially influence the nature of the barriers encountered. Instead, challenges appear to reflect broader structural and operational conditions that persist regardless of how access and reuse rights are defined.

A slightly more articulated distribution can be observed in more conditional licensing approaches, such as sharing for specific purposes, where a wider range of challenges is reported. However, this variation remains limited and does not indicate a fundamentally different pattern.

Overall, the results indicate that perceived challenges are largely independent of licensing conditions, pointing to systemic issues that extend beyond the specific frameworks used to regulate data access and reuse.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This section examines the relationship between storage environments (D9) and data sharing practices (D10), as well as the challenges (D13) associated with different infrastructural configurations.

The objective is to assess whether the choice of storage environment influences the frequency of data sharing and the types of barriers encountered, and to identify the extent to which infrastructural conditions shape data management practices within this profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and data sharing practices reveals a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” clearly representing the dominant mode of sharing (*Figure 6.14*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	18	54	5
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	1	1	1
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	11	40	2
Institutional servers or websites	6	19	0
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	2	2	1
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	2	0	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	5	11	1
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	2	3	0
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	8	17	1

Figure 6.14 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across the main storage environments – including local, cloud-based, institutional and self-hosted solutions – sharing is most frequently reported as occasional, while “Yes, always” remains secondary but consistently present. At the same time, the proportion of respondents who do not share data is very limited across all configurations, indicating that sharing is rarely absent.

Overall, the results suggest that storage infrastructures do not strongly influence the frequency of data sharing within this profile. Sharing appears to remain shaped primarily by professional, project-based and contextual conditions rather than by the storage environment itself.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and perceived challenges reveals a largely consistent distribution across all configurations, with no single barrier clearly dominating within any specific environment (Figure 6.15).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	28	34	40	39	35	32	24	34	26
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	2	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	19	27	28	32	24	20	17	21	14
Institutional servers or websites	14	14	12	12	10	11	7	13	9
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	3	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	2
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	9	7	8	7	5	9	5	8	6
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	2	1	0	1	2	2	0	1	2
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	12	15	18	14	12	11	10	15	9

Figure 6.15 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Across the main storage configurations – including local, cloud-based, institutional and self-hosted solutions – challenges related to legal constraints, concerns about misuse, and privacy issues tend to appear with slightly higher proportions, although without substantial variation between contexts. Other barriers, such as technical limitations, effort required for data preparation, and infrastructure-related constraints, are also consistently represented.

At the same time, minor variations can be observed in the relative prominence of specific challenges across environments. Cloud-based configurations show a slightly higher emphasis on concerns related to misuse and privacy, while local and self-hosted environments tend to give relatively more weight to legal and operational constraints. Institutional settings, in contrast, display a more balanced distribution, with a slightly stronger presence of issues related to data quality and compliance.

Overall, the results indicate that challenges are not strongly determined by storage infrastructures. Instead, they reflect broadly shared conditions, with only limited shifts in the types of concerns that are more prominently perceived across different environments.

Comparative Analysis – Collaboration

This section examines the relationship between collaboration modalities (E6), documentation practices (D8.1), and data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different forms of collaboration influence how documentation is produced and how consistently data is shared, and to identify the extent to which collaborative contexts shape operational practices within this profile.

Collaboration (E6) × Documentation (D8.1)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and documentation practices reveals a largely stable pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the types of documentation adopted (*Figure 6.16*).

Collaboration (E6) x Documentation (D8.1)	Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	12	13	12	7	5	4	5	2
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	10	10	10	6	5	5	3	3
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	4	5	5	3	4	5	2	3
Participation in workshops or hackathons	4	4	5	2	2	1	1	1
Through detailed requirement documentation	6	9	7	6	5	4	4	2
Via email or written reports only	6	5	5	4	1	2	3	1

Figure 6.16 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data documentation practices (D8.1)

Across different forms of collaboration – including regular meetings, direct involvement in development processes, the use of collaborative tools, and more formal or informal communication channels – the distribution of documentation practices remains broadly consistent. No specific mode of collaboration is associated with a distinct or clearly differentiated documentation approach, suggesting that collaborative settings do not strongly shape how documentation is produced or structured.

At the same time, minor variations can be observed. More interactive and informal contexts, such as workshops or feedback sessions, show a slightly higher reliance on simple notes, while more structured or tool-based collaborations display a marginally greater use of documentation systems. Communication channels based on written exchanges, such as email, tend to be more associated with manual documentation practices.

Overall, the results indicate that collaboration modalities have only a limited influence on documentation practices within this profile. Documentation approaches remain relatively stable across different collaborative configurations, with only subtle shifts reflecting the nature of specific interaction contexts.

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and data sharing practices reveals a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant mode of sharing (*Figure 6.17*).

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	6	15	0
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	3	13	0
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	3	5	0
Participation in workshops or hackathons	1	4	0
Through detailed requirement documentation	4	6	0
Via email or written reports only	1	6	0

Figure 6.17 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data sharing practices (D10)

Within collaborative contexts, sharing is consistently present across all forms of interaction – including meetings, direct involvement in development processes, the use of collaborative tools, and more formal or informal communication channels – with no instances of complete absence. This indicates that collaboration is systematically associated with some level of data sharing within this subset of the profile.

At the same time, the frequency of sharing remains largely occasional, regardless of the collaborative modality adopted. Only limited variation can be observed in the proportion of “Yes, always” responses. More structured forms of collaboration, such as those based on detailed requirement documentation or the use of collaborative tools, show slightly higher levels of systematic sharing, while more informal channels, such as email-based communication, are associated with lower levels.

Overall, the results suggest that collaboration plays a key role in enabling data sharing, ensuring its consistent presence where it occurs. However, it does not significantly increase the regularity of sharing, which remains predominantly situational even in more structured collaborative environments.

Profile: Institutional Anchors

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

A5 - Type of institution

- LAM (library, archive, museum)
- University, research institute or research infrastructure

- Governmental agency or other public authority
- Historical monuments, listed buildings, sites

A2 - Working status

- Employed
- Student

C6 - How do you typically log in or authenticate when accessing digital tools and services?

- → EDUGain
- Institutional Login
- Microsoft

D5 - Does your institution follow a published Data Management Plan?

- Yes

D9 - Where do you store the data you produce?

- On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)
- In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)
- On Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)

Base: 71 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Institutional Anchors* profile represents respondents embedded in institutional environments such as museums, universities, governmental bodies or heritage organisations. These actors operate within structured organisational contexts where institutional infrastructures and formal data management practices are more common.

Their work is typically supported by institutional authentication systems, organisational data infrastructures and structured storage environments such as institutional servers, repositories or subscription-based platforms. These conditions often reflect the presence of organisational policies or formal data management practices.

Overall, this profile reflects actors whose institutional positioning places them within established organisational infrastructures and workflows related to cultural heritage data management.

Summary of findings

Project engagement & profile positioning

Respondents in this profile include both institutional representatives and individuals contributing in their own professional capacity. A majority of respondents report answering the survey in their own capacity (70.4%), while a substantial share (29.6%)

participate as representatives of an institution. Although individual respondents represent the larger group, the presence of institutional representatives suggests that this profile includes actors who may play a role in shaping or coordinating institutional data environments within cultural heritage contexts.

The types of heritage assets most frequently used by respondents further reflect the institutional orientation of this profile. Digital representations of cultural heritage objects represent the most widely used resource, reported by 66.2% of respondents. These include digitised materials such as high-resolution images, scans or 3D models. Physical objects are also frequently used (19.7%), indicating that some activities remain directly connected to material heritage collections (*Figure 7.1*).

B2. Which of the following do you mostly use in your work?	Count	%
Digital representations (e.g., digitised versions of objects, such as high-resolution scans, photographs, or 3D models)	47	66.2%
Physical objects (e.g. artworks, sites, natural specimens, ...)	14	19.7%
Non-digital reproductions (e.g., printed photos, casts, or other physical replicas of the object)	6	8.5%
Multimedia assets (e.g., audio recordings, videos, or interactive media related to the object)	2	2.8%
Born-digital assets	2	2.8%

Figure 7.1 *Types of heritage assets mostly used in professional activities (B2).*

Other types of resources appear less common. Non-digital reproductions such as printed photographs or physical replicas are reported by 8.5% of respondents, while multimedia assets (2.8%) and born-digital heritage objects (2.8%) are mentioned only occasionally.

Overall, these results suggest that Institutional Anchors primarily operate in environments where digital representations of cultural heritage materials play a central role, while maintaining connections with physical collections and institutional heritage assets.

Institutional infrastructure & governance

Respondents in this profile show varying degrees of involvement in the management of institutional data infrastructures. A significant share of respondents (38.0%) report being directly involved in the management of their institution’s databases, servers or repositories. This indicates that a substantial portion of participants contribute to the configuration, maintenance or oversight of the digital environments that support the storage and organisation of cultural heritage data (*Figure 7.2*).

F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution’s database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?	Count	%
No	44	62.0%

Yes	27	38.0%
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Figure 7.2 *Involvement in the management of databases, servers or repositories (F1).*

At the same time, a larger group (62.0%) report not being directly involved in the technical management of these infrastructures. This suggests that while many respondents operate within institutional environments where such infrastructures are present, their role may be more focused on using or contributing to these systems rather than managing them directly.

Taken together, these responses indicate that Institutional Anchors include both actors responsible for managing institutional data infrastructures and professionals who interact with these systems as part of broader institutional workflows.

Tools and services

Respondents in this profile report using or showing interest in a range of digital tools supporting the annotation, analysis and management of cultural heritage data. Tools for manual annotation of digital assets represent the most frequently mentioned category (32.4%), indicating that many respondents work with systems allowing the tagging or description of text, images, audio or 3D content. Automated approaches are also present, including handwriting or text recognition technologies such as HTR or OCR (19.7%) and automated analysis of textual or speech resources using natural language processing techniques (18.3%), while a smaller share report interest in automatic shape or texture recognition tools (11.3%).

Interest in spatial and visualisation technologies is also significant. More than half of respondents (54.9%) report using or wishing to use tools for 3D scanning, modelling or reconstruction. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are mentioned by 38.0% of respondents, followed by virtual or augmented reality technologies (28.2%) and LiDAR-based data acquisition (23.9%), while Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM) appears less frequently (9.9%).

Tools supporting data management are also widely mentioned. Systems for data collection management and structuring are reported by 36.6% of respondents, followed by tools supporting data interoperability and API integration (31.0%) and resource storage and retrieval systems (23.9%). Some respondents also report interest in formal knowledge representation tools, including knowledge graphs and semantic web technologies (31.0%), taxonomies and controlled vocabularies (22.5%) and ontologies (16.9%) (*Figure 7.3*).

C1.4b. Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?	Count	%
Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data	22	31.0%
Answered No to C1.4a - Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?	21	29.6%

Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies	16	22.5%
Ontologies	12	16.9%

Figure 7.3 Formal knowledge representation tools and services (C1.4b).

Access models and authentication

Respondents in this profile primarily rely on open and institutionally supported access models when using digital tools and services. The most widely reported configuration consists of free, open-access services, used by 81.7% of respondents. Open-source software is also widely adopted (57.7%), while a substantial share report using tools developed in-house or custom-built within their institutions (52.1%). These results suggest that institutional environments often combine openly accessible tools with internally developed infrastructures tailored to organisational needs (Figure 7.4).

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	58	81.7%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	41	57.7%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	37	52.1%
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	33	46.5%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	26	36.6%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	23	32.4%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	7	9.9%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	7	9.9%

Figure 7.4 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4).

Other access models remain present but less dominant. Free services operating under specific licensing conditions are reported by 46.5% of respondents, while paid licence-based tools (36.6%) and subscription-based services (32.4%) are also used in a number of institutional contexts. More occasional configurations include trial-based access and pay-per-use models, each reported by 9.9% of respondents.

Authentication practices appear strongly anchored in institutional infrastructures. The most common method consists of institutional login systems, reported by 95.8% of respondents, indicating that access to digital tools is largely mediated through organisational credentials. Other authentication providers include Google accounts (36.6%), ORCID identifiers (33.8%), Microsoft accounts (22.5%), and other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions (16.9%). More specialised solutions such as EduGAIN (7.0%), Apple ID (5.6%) and Eulogin (5.6%) are reported less frequently, while social login systems such as Facebook remain marginal (1.4%).

The distribution therefore reflects that Institutional Anchors typically operate within hybrid access environments that combine open tools, institutionally developed infrastructures and authentication systems managed through organisational identities.

Data production processes and objectives

Respondents in this profile report using a range of methods to produce cultural heritage data, combining research-based, documentation and analytical approaches. The most frequently reported process consists of digitisation, transcription and 3D or spatial documentation (71.8%), closely followed by archival research (67.6%). Fieldwork also represents an important activity (53.5%), while many respondents report processing or reanalysing existing datasets (54.9%), indicating that institutional environments often involve both primary data collection and the transformation of previously created resources.

Other methods appear in smaller but still relevant shares. Examination and analytical procedures such as visual inspection or laboratory analysis are reported by 35.2% of respondents, while computational approaches including modelling or algorithmic methods reach 33.8%. Surveys or questionnaires (33.8%), observational practices (32.4%) and interviews or focus groups (28.2%) are also reported, suggesting that institutional data production often combines qualitative and analytical approaches. Crowdsourcing initiatives (19.7%) and experimental methods (14.1%) appear less frequently.

The objectives guiding data production further reflect the institutional orientation of this profile. The most widely reported goal consists of answering research questions (78.9%). Many respondents also emphasise archiving or preserving information (63.4%) and cataloguing data through metadata creation (54.9%). Public communication activities are also significant (57.7%), while other objectives include preparing reports (38.0%), developing educational materials (36.6%), supporting decision-making (28.2%) and creating conservation or restoration documentation (26.8%) (Figure 7.5).

D2. What are the primary objectives of producing data in your work?	Count	%
Answering research questions (e.g., contributing to academic or scientific studies, such as material characterisation, provenance study, etc.)	56	78.9%
Archiving or preserving information (e.g., maintaining records for future reference)	45	63.4%
Public communication or awareness (e.g., sharing findings with a general audience)	41	57.7%
Cataloguing information (e.g., metadata creation for management or reporting purposes)	39	54.9%
Preparing reports (e.g., internal reports, technical documentation, or project summaries)	27	38.0%
Developing educational materials (e.g., creating resources for teaching or training)	26	36.6%
Supporting decision-making (e.g., providing insights for strategic planning or policy-making)	20	28.2%

Creating conservation or restoration plans (e.g., documenting objects for heritage preservation, condition reports)	19	26.8%
Monitoring and evaluation (e.g., tracking progress or assessing impact)	13	18.3%

Figure 7.5 Data production objectives (D2).

Taken together, these results indicate that Institutional Anchors typically produce data through a combination of research, documentation and institutional management practices.

Sharing, licensing and challenges

Responses in this profile indicate a differentiated use of data access channels, combining institutional infrastructures, direct sharing practices and, to a lesser extent, repository-based dissemination.

Institutional repositories represent the most structured channel, with a large majority of respondents (76.0%) making more than half of their data accessible through their organisation’s repository. Dissemination through publications and reports is also relatively established (55.0%), while more informal channels such as email or commercial cloud platforms are widely used but primarily for a smaller share of data, indicating a more situational use. Open-access repositories remain less central, with most respondents using them for less than half of their datasets, and domain-specific repositories appearing only marginally integrated into regular workflows.

Licensing practices show a differentiated use of sharing conditions. Open sharing without restrictions is applied to more than half of the data by 38.0% of respondents. Other conditions are also used for a significant share of datasets: access restrictions (19.7%), formal agreements (18.3%) and embargo periods (14.1%) are applied to more than half of the data by a notable portion of respondents. Sharing upon request is common, but primarily used for a smaller portion of datasets (52.1%) (Figure 7.6).

D12. Under which conditions do you typically share your data?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	18 (25.4%)	26 (36.6%)	15 (21.1%)	12 (16.9%)
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	18 (25.4%)	26 (36.6%)	16 (22.5%)	11 (15.5%)
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	29 (40.8%)	28 (39.4%)	9 (12.7%)	5 (7.0%)
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	33 (46.5%)	25 (35.2%)	10 (14.1%)	3 (4.2%)
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	38 (53.5%)	23 (32.4%)	8 (11.3%)	2 (2.8%)
Upon request only	19 (26.8%)	37 (52.1%)	11 (15.5%)	4 (5.6%)

For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	12 (16.9%)	30 (42.3%)	18 (25.4%)	11 (15.5%)
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	39 (54.9%)	24 (33.8%)	6 (8.5%)	2 (2.8%)

Figure 7.6 Conditions for data sharing (D12).

Challenges associated with sharing and reuse are both structural and governance-related. Data or metadata quality (60.6%), the effort required to prepare data for sharing (52.1%) and legal or contractual restrictions (53.5%) represent the most significant barriers. Additional constraints include non-digitised materials (45.1%), concerns related to confidentiality and privacy (42.3%) and limitations in available infrastructure (39.4%). Technical barriers and unclear guidelines are also reported, although to a lesser extent.

Needs & Expectations

Institutional anchors express needs linked to coordination, long-term sustainability and the management of complex organisational ecosystems.

The main challenges relate to skills gaps and the learning curve, combined with financial constraints and technical limitations. These factors affect the capacity to adopt and maintain digital tools at scale. Interoperability issues and data-related challenges (including quality, standardisation and access) further complicate workflows, particularly in multi-institutional or cross-domain contexts.

Human resource limitations and organisational barriers also play a significant role, as institutions often need to balance strategic objectives with limited operational capacity and internal expertise. Legal and governance concerns add another layer of complexity, especially when dealing with sensitive or regulated data.

In terms of expectations, respondents strongly emphasise the need for improved interoperability and integration between systems, supported by shared standards and collaborative frameworks. Training and capacity building are considered essential to support adoption and ensure consistent practices across teams (Figure 7.7).

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	11	45.8%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	6	25.0%
Training, documentation and capacity building	5	20.8%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	5	20.8%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	5	20.8%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	4	16.7%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	3	12.5%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	3	12.5%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	3	12.5%

Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	3	12.5%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	2	8.3%
Connectivity and offline functionality	2	8.3%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	2	8.3%

Figure 7.7 *Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3)*

Additional expectations include more user-friendly tools, better infrastructure and scalable storage, as well as stronger support for data management and advanced processing functionalities. There is also a demand for more sustainable and open solutions, alongside improved organisational support and governance mechanisms to ensure long-term impact.

Overall Conclusion

The Institutional Anchors profile highlights actors operating within organisational environments where cultural heritage data production, management and dissemination are closely connected to institutional infrastructures and responsibilities. Respondents typically work with digital representations of heritage assets and participate in data production activities combining documentation, research and institutional reporting functions.

While a significant share of respondents are directly involved in managing institutional databases, servers or repositories, many others interact with these infrastructures through their daily professional activities. Their work therefore often sits at the intersection between operational data practices and the institutional systems that support them.

The results also indicate that Institutional Anchors rely on a combination of open-access tools, open-source solutions and internally developed infrastructures. At the same time, challenges related to interoperability, skills development, limited resources and legal constraints continue to shape how digital tools and data-sharing practices are implemented within institutional contexts.

Overall, this profile illustrates the role of institutional actors as key connectors between heritage data production, organisational infrastructures and broader data-sharing ecosystems.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This section examines the relationship between data production methods (D1), data management practices (C1.3b), and the use of semantic tools (C1.4b).

The objective is to assess how different types of production activities and tool adoption are associated with varying levels of data structuring, interoperability, and overall maturity, and to identify the extent to which operational practices reflect more advanced and integrated approaches to data management within this profile.

Production processes (D1) × Data management and storage (C1.3b)

The cross-analysis between data production methods and data management configurations highlights a clear relationship between the type of activity performed and the way data are structured and handled (*Figure 7.8*).

Production (D1) × Data management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
Archival research (e.g., consulting historical records, documents, or archives)	15	16	13	4
Digitisation, transcription and 3D and spatial documentation	19	18	11	3
Computational methods (e.g., simulations, algorithms, or modeling)	9	9	5	1
Crowdsourcing or citizen science (e.g., engaging non-specialists to gather data)	7	6	1	0
Examination / analysis (e.g., visual inspection, instrumental analysis, laboratory testing, material analysis and testing, imaging and spectroscopy methods)	9	8	6	2
Experimental methods (e.g., controlled experiments or trials, material reconstructions, accelerated ageing tests)	3	5	1	1
Fieldwork (e.g., on-site data collection or acquisition, conservation treatment documentation and monitoring)	14	12	7	5
Interviews or focus groups (e.g., qualitative data collection through discussion)	10	2	6	2
Observation (e.g., direct or indirect observation of phenomena or processes)	12	5	5	1
Processing data / resources created by others or reprocessing your own primary data (e.g., data reanalysis, comparative studies, data aggregation and enrichment,	12	17	8	2
Surveys / questionnaires (e.g., collecting data through participant responses)	12	6	4	2

Figure 7.8 Relationship between data production processes (D1) and the use of data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

Across most production practices, data collection management and structuring and data interoperability and integration emerge as the two dominant configurations, while resource storage and retrieval systems consistently play a more secondary role. This suggests that data management within this profile is primarily oriented towards organising and connecting data, rather than simply storing it.

At the same time, distinct patterns can be observed depending on the nature of the production activity. Practices based on primary data generation – such as fieldwork, observation, surveys, and interviews – tend to be more strongly associated with data collection and structuring. In contrast, activities involving the transformation, analysis, or reuse of existing data – including computational methods, experimental approaches, and data processing – show a relatively stronger association with interoperability and integration practices.

More documentation-oriented or hybrid practices, such as archival research or examination, display a more balanced distribution across different data management approaches, indicating the need to both organise and connect heterogeneous data sources.

Overall, the results suggest that data management practices within this profile are closely aligned with the nature of data production activities. Rather than following a single dominant model, they adapt to the specific operational requirements of each type of production process, reflecting a differentiated and context-dependent approach to digital maturity.

Data management and storage (C1.3b) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)

The cross-analysis between the use of semantic tools and documentation or data management configurations highlights a clear relationship between the adoption of specific tools and the type of data practices implemented (*Figure 7.9*).

Tools (C1.4b) x Data management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data	6	9	7	0
Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies	6	8	2	0
Ontologies	7	1	3	1
Answered NO to C1.4a	7	4	5	5

Figure 7.9 Relationship between the use of data management and storage tools (C1.3b) and the use of formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b)

Tools such as knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies, and taxonomies are primarily associated with data interoperability and integration. In these cases, interoperability emerges as the most prominent configuration, suggesting that these tools are mainly used to connect, structure, and integrate data across systems rather than for basic organisation or storage purposes.

A different pattern can be observed for ontologies, which appear more strongly associated with data collection and structuring. This indicates a more localised or internal use of these tools, oriented towards organising data rather than enabling broader interoperability, and highlights a more heterogeneous use of semantic technologies within the profile.

Respondents who do not report using semantic tools display a more fragmented pattern, with a higher proportion also indicating the absence of structured documentation or data management practices. This suggests that the lack of dedicated tools is associated with lower levels of formalisation in data handling.

Overall, the results indicate that the use of semantic tools is closely linked to more advanced and integration-oriented data practices, while their absence corresponds to less structured and less formalised approaches to documentation and data management.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This section examines the relationship between licensing conditions (D12), data sharing practices (D11), and the challenges (D13) associated with different governance configurations.

The objective is to assess how varying degrees of openness and restriction influence both the channels through which data are shared and the types of barriers encountered, and to identify the extent to which governance frameworks shape data circulation within institutional contexts.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Sharing channels (D11)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and data sharing channels reveals a clear relationship between the level of openness and the type of dissemination practices adopted.

Across all licensing configurations, institutional repositories consistently emerge as the most prominent channel, indicating their central role in enabling structured and sustained access to data within institutional contexts. This pattern remains stable regardless of whether data are shared openly or under more restrictive conditions.

At the same time, differences can be observed depending on the degree of openness. More open licensing approaches – such as unrestricted sharing or the use of open licenses – are more strongly associated with formal and structured dissemination channels, including institutional repositories, publications, and, to a lesser extent, public open-access platforms. This suggests that openness facilitates integration into established and visible dissemination infrastructures (*Figure 7.10*).

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) ✕ Sharing (proxy) (D11) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%)	Shared by email, direct communication, or commercial cloud-based file-sharing platforms (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox)	Shared through publications (scientific or public), annexes of administrative documents, or other reports	Made accessible within my institution / organisation / company repository	Made accessible through a public repository or generic-purpose Open-access platforms (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare)	Made accessible through domain specific repositories (e.g., Archives Portal Europe, EUScreen)	Made accessible through digital stores (e.g. Unity Assets Store, _Fab marketplace_)
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	11	16	23	13	9	2
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	9	15	22	15	11	1
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	5	8	9	4	4	1
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	6	6	9	5	4	1
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	3	6	8	4	3	2
Upon request only	12	8	10	2	4	2
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	17	19	19	9	5	2
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	5	6	5	3	2	1

Figure 7.10 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and the ways in which data are shared or made accessible (D11)

In contrast, more restrictive or conditional sharing approaches – such as sharing upon request or under specific access conditions – are more frequently associated with direct and less formal channels, particularly email or cloud-based file sharing. This indicates a shift towards more controlled and case-by-case data exchange practices when access conditions become more constrained.

Intermediate configurations, such as sharing for specific purposes or after anonymisation, display a more balanced distribution across channels, combining both structured and direct forms of dissemination.

Overall, the results suggest that while institutional infrastructures remain central across all conditions, licensing frameworks play a significant role in shaping how data are shared, influencing the balance between formal, repository-based dissemination and more direct, controlled exchange practices.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between licensing conditions and perceived challenges reveals a broadly consistent distribution across all configurations, with no single barrier clearly dominating within any specific licensing model (Figure 7.11).

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	15	13	14	12	13	9	12	5	6
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	19	12	18	10	18	9	14	6	5
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	8	5	9	8	8	3	5	5	4
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	9	7	9	10	4	2	7	2	4
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	4	5	7	6	5	4	5	2	2
Upon request only	11	8	9	10	7	5	7	7	4
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	16	14	19	16	14	8	10	9	5
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	3	3	6	4	5	4	3	1	2

Figure 7.11 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Across all licensing approaches – from open to more restrictive or conditional forms – challenges related to data quality, legal constraints, and the effort required to prepare data for sharing tend to appear with slightly higher proportions, although without substantial variation between configurations. Other barriers, including concerns about misuse, privacy issues, technical limitations, and infrastructure gaps, are also consistently represented.

At the same time, minor variations can be observed in the relative prominence of specific challenges. More conditional or controlled forms of sharing – such as formal agreements, anonymisation, or sharing for specific purposes – show a slightly stronger emphasis on legal constraints, effort-related barriers, and concerns about misuse. However, these differences remain limited and do not indicate fundamentally different patterns.

Overall, the results suggest that the challenges associated with data sharing are largely independent of licensing conditions. Instead, they reflect broader structural and operational constraints that persist across different governance frameworks, with only subtle shifts in the types of concerns that are more prominently perceived.

Profile: Low-Digital Users

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

D5. Do you use a Data Management Plan (DMP)?

→ No or I don't know

D6. In what formats are your data stored?

→ Closed / proprietary formats or I don't know

D8. Do you document your data?

→ No

D9. Where do you store your data?

→ Locally (hard drives, internal server) >75%

Base: 48 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Low Digital Users* profile represents respondents who show limited adoption of digital tools and structured data management practices. Their workflows tend to rely on local storage solutions and proprietary formats rather than interoperable infrastructures or shared repositories.

These respondents typically report the absence of formal data management plans, limited documentation practices and a low level of engagement with structured data standards. Data are most often stored locally and rarely shared through digital infrastructures or open repositories.

Overall, this profile reflects actors with lower levels of digital integration in their data practices, often operating with limited resources, limited technical support or reduced exposure to structured data management environments.

Summary of findings

Profile positioning

Low digital users are primarily affiliated with universities, public institutions and cultural heritage organisations, with a particularly strong presence in academic and research environments alongside conservation-focused roles. Their work is mainly concentrated in heritage conservation, preservation and research-related activities (*Figure 8.1*).

They engage with a broad range of heritage assets, with a notable focus on textual and archival resources, as well as visual materials, physical objects and archaeological sites.

They are typically involved in documentation, research or conservation-related tasks, but show limited engagement with advanced digital tools and data-driven workflows. Digital technologies are not central to their professional practice and are often used only at a basic or occasional level.

This profile is characterised by low digital maturity and limited integration into digital ecosystems, with a stronger reliance on traditional methods and isolated tools rather than structured, interoperable environments.

A6. Which of the following best describes your professional activity or the field(s) in which your work primarily fits?	Count	%
Cultural heritage conservation and preservation	26	54.2%
Research and studies in social sciences and humanities	19	39.6%
Education, mediation and audience engagement	10	20.8%
Museology and collection management	9	18.8%
Documentation, archives, and information management	6	12.5%
Science, engineering and applied research	6	12.5%
Other (research)	5	10.4%
Digital technologies and data management	2	4.2%
Urban and spatial planning	2	4.2%
Management, policy, governance and exploitation	1	2.1%
Artistic creation and art market	0	0.0%

Figure 8.1 Professional fields and activities (A6).

Data production processes

Data production within the Low Digital Users profile is primarily grounded in traditional and practice-based approaches, with archival research representing the most common process (60.4%), followed by fieldwork activities (50.0%). Observation (41.7%) and examination or analytical methods (39.6%) also play a significant role, indicating a strong reliance on direct engagement with heritage assets and materials (*Figure 8.2*).

D1. What processes do you typically use to produce data?	Count	%
Archival research (e.g., consulting historical records, documents, or archives)	29	60.4%
Fieldwork (e.g., on-site data collection or acquisition, conservation treatment documentation and monitoring)	24	50.0%
Observation (e.g., direct or indirect observation of phenomena or processes)	20	41.7%
Examination / analysis (e.g., visual inspection, instrumental analysis, laboratory testing, material analysis and testing, imaging and spectroscopy methods)	19	39.6%
Processing data / resources created by others or reprocessing your own primary data (e.g., data reanalysis, comparative studies, data aggregation and enrichment, transformation, modeling, interpretation, synthesis or fusion)	14	29.2%
Surveys / questionnaires (e.g., collecting data through participant responses)	14	29.2%
Digitisation, transcription and 3D and spatial documentation	13	27.1%
Interviews or focus groups (e.g., qualitative data collection through discussion)	12	25.0%
Experimental methods (e.g., controlled experiments or trials, material reconstructions, accelerated ageing tests)	8	16.7%
Computational methods (e.g., simulations, algorithms, or modeling)	4	8.3%
Crowdsourcing or citizen science (e.g., engaging non-specialists to gather data)	3	6.3%

Figure 8.2 Data production processes (D1).

More structured but still accessible practices, such as digitisation (27.1%), interviews (25.0%), and surveys (29.2%), are present but not dominant. Processing or reusing

existing data remains limited (29.2%), while more advanced or specialised approaches – including experimental methods (16.7%), computational techniques (8.3%), and crowdsourcing (6.3%) – are only marginally adopted.

Overall, data production is characterised by low technological complexity and a preference for manual, observational and field-based methods, with limited integration of computational or highly digitised processes.

Data management and storage

Storage practices within the Low Digital Users profile are strongly centred on local environments, with all respondents storing most or all of their data on personal devices (100.0%) (Figure 8.3).

Institutional servers represent the only partially established alternative, with around one third of respondents storing a large share of their data in these environments (33.4%). Cloud-based commercial platforms play a more limited role, with most users relying on them only for a smaller portion of their data (41.7%), and a relatively small share using them extensively (14.6%).

All other storage solutions remain marginal. Domain-specific repositories, open-access platforms and self-hosted infrastructures are used by only a very small minority (4.2%), while collaborative platforms and subscription-based services are almost entirely absent.

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	48 (100.0%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	40 (83.3%)	4 (8.3%)	2 (4.2%)	2 (4.2%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	38 (79.2%)	6 (12.5%)	2 (4.2%)	2 (4.2%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	15 (31.3%)	20 (41.7%)	6 (12.5%)	7 (14.6%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	45 (93.8%)	1 (2.1%)	2 (4.2%)	0 (0.0%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	20 (41.7%)	12 (25.0%)	8 (16.7%)	8 (16.7%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	44 (91.7%)	3 (6.3%)	1 (2.1%)	0 (0.0%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	27 (56.3%)	15 (31.3%)	4 (8.3%)	2 (4.2%)

Figure 8.3 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9).

This pattern highlights a strong reliance on familiar and easily accessible storage solutions, with limited engagement with more complex or distributed data infrastructures.

Overall, storage practices are highly concentrated on local solutions, with very limited adoption of structured, institutional or shared infrastructures.

Data sharing and challenges

Data sharing within the Low Digital Users profile is present but largely situational. The majority of respondents report sharing data only sometimes (77.1%), while a smaller proportion always share (8.3%), and a non-negligible segment does not share data at all (14.6%). This indicates that sharing practices are not systematically embedded and remain dependent on specific contexts or conditions.

The challenges associated with sharing and reuse are both technical and governance-related (*Figure 8.4*). The most frequently reported barriers include concerns about data misuse (43.8%) and technical barriers (43.8%), alongside limitations in infrastructure or available platforms (39.6%) and confidentiality or privacy concerns (39.6%). Resource-related constraints also play a significant role, particularly the lack of time or capacity required to prepare data for sharing (35.4%).

Data-related issues are also relevant, including problems with data or metadata quality and completeness (29.2%) and the presence of non-digitised materials (29.2%). Legal and contractual restrictions (20.8%) and unclear guidelines (25.0%) further contribute to limiting more consistent sharing practices.

Overall, sharing within this profile remains irregular and constrained by a combination of technical, organisational and risk-related factors, with multiple barriers preventing more systematic access and reuse of data.

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data?	Count	%
Concerns about data misuse	21	43.8%
Technical barriers (e.g., difficulty accessing or using the required tools or platforms, large format files unable to be shared by common open means)	21	43.8%
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (including GDPR compliance when data refers to specific persons, e.g. archival material)	19	39.6%
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	19	39.6%
Extra effort is required, lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	17	35.4%
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	14	29.2%
Non-digital data, resource is not digitised	14	29.2%
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	12	25.0%
Legal or contractual restrictions, intellectual property rights / other legal issues	10	20.8%

Figure 8.4 Challenges in data sharing, consultation and reuse (D13).

Needs & expectations

Low digital users express needs primarily related to basic access, understanding and effective use of digital tools.

The main challenges are strongly linked to skills gaps and the learning curve, which represent the most significant barrier to adoption. Financial constraints and limited access to adequate infrastructure further restrict their ability to engage with digital tools. Usability issues also play an important role, as complex or non-intuitive interfaces discourage use and limit the exploitation of available functionalities (*Figure 8.5*).

C2. What difficulties do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?	Count	%
Skills, training and learning curve	9	64.3%
Financial constraints and costs	7	50.0%
Technical, infrastructure and hardware limitations	6	42.9%
Usability and user experience limitations	5	35.7%
Human resources and staffing constraints	4	28.6%
Connectivity and access limitations	3	21.4%
Interoperability and system integration issues	2	14.3%
Legal, copyright and data governance concerns	2	14.3%
Data access and availability constraints	2	14.3%
Documentation, guidance and best practice gaps	2	14.3%
Vendor dependency, tool sustainability and support limitations	1	7.1%
Organisational and policy barriers	1	7.1%
Domain-specific limitations and lack of fit	1	7.1%
Data quality, heterogeneity and standardisation issues	0	0.0%

Figure 8.5 *Main difficulties in the use of digital tools and resources (C2).*

Additional challenges include limited access to resources, insufficient training opportunities and, in some cases, connectivity constraints, all of which contribute to low levels of adoption and confidence.

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for more accessible and easy-to-use tools, supported by targeted training and clear documentation. Increasing access to information about available tools and how to use them is seen as essential. There is also a demand for more affordable solutions and improved infrastructure.

Basic functionalities such as data access and simple automation are perceived as valuable, but expectations remain focused on foundational needs: usability, guidance, and accessibility rather than advanced features or complex integrations.

Overall Conclusion

Low Digital Users emerge as a profile characterised by limited adoption of digital tools and infrastructures, with practices strongly rooted in traditional, manual and locally managed approaches. Data production is primarily based on archival research, fieldwork and observation, with only marginal engagement in computational or advanced digital methods.

Data management and storage configurations reflect this low level of digital integration, with a near-total reliance on local environments and minimal use of institutional, shared or open infrastructures. Governance practices remain weakly formalised, and data sharing is present but largely situational rather than systematic.

Barriers to more advanced digital engagement are multiple and cumulative, combining technical limitations, lack of infrastructure, resource constraints and skills gaps. Concerns related to data misuse, privacy and legal restrictions further contribute to limiting openness and reuse.

Overall, this profile appears positioned at an early stage of digital maturity, where practices are primarily oriented toward basic data handling and preservation, with limited integration into broader digital ecosystems and constrained capacity for scalable, interoperable and collaborative data use.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This section examines the relationship between storage environments (D9), data sharing practices (D10), and perceived challenges (D13).

The objective is to assess whether different storage configurations and constraints influence the regularity of data sharing, and to identify whether limitations related to infrastructure, resources or perceived risks affect the ability to manage and circulate data within this profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage configurations and data sharing practices shows a consistent pattern across all environments, with “Yes, sometimes” representing the dominant modality. This indicates that sharing remains largely occasional rather than systematically embedded in workflows (*Figure 8.6*).

Across all storage types, the proportion of “Yes, always” responses is consistently low, suggesting a limited degree of regularised sharing practices. At the same time, a non-negligible presence of “No” responses emerges in several configurations, indicating that data sharing is not only inconsistent but, in some cases, absent.

Differences between storage environments are limited, with broadly similar distributions across configurations. Overall, the type of storage does not significantly influence the regularity of data sharing.

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) X Sharing (D10)			
	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	4	37	7
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	1	1	2
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	2	10	1
Institutional servers or websites	2	12	2
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	1	2	1
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	0	0	1
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	0	4	2
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	0	1	1
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	0	2	1

Figure 8.6 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between storage configurations and perceived challenges shows a distributed pattern, with no single barrier clearly dominating across environments. Challenges appear to be multi-dimensional, reflecting a combination of technical, organisational and perceptual factors.

Across the most robust configurations, however, a slight but consistent emphasis emerges on concerns related to data misuse, which tend to appear among the most frequently reported barriers. This pattern is observable particularly in local, cloud-based and institutional environments, suggesting that issues of control, trust and potential misuse play a recurring role in shaping data practices.

At the same time, technical barriers and limitations related to infrastructure also appear regularly across configurations, indicating that practical constraints continue to affect data management and sharing processes. Other challenges, such as data quality, effort required for preparation, or lack of clear guidelines, are present but more evenly distributed and do not define distinct patterns.

Overall, the results suggest that challenges are not strongly determined by the type of storage environment. Instead, they reflect a combination of operational constraints and perceived risks that affect data practices in a relatively consistent manner across different configurations (Figure 8.7).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) X Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	14	19	10	21	17	21	14	19	12
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	3	0	0	0	2	2	0	1	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	4	4	2	7	4	5	5	4	4
Institutional servers or websites	7	7	2	9	4	5	4	8	4
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, ...)	2	0	0	0	3	3	0	1	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	3	1
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Figure 8.7 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Challenges (D13) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between perceived challenges and data sharing practices shows a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with “Yes, sometimes” overwhelmingly representing the dominant modality. This indicates that data sharing remains predominantly situational, regardless of the type of barrier encountered.

At the same time, some nuanced differences emerge across specific challenges. Barriers related to effort, lack of infrastructure and unclear guidelines are associated with very high levels of occasional sharing and minimal instances of non-sharing. This suggests that these constraints tend to slow down or complicate sharing processes, but do not generally prevent them.

By contrast, challenges related to data quality and concerns about misuse show a comparatively higher proportion of “No” responses. Although still limited in absolute terms, this pattern indicates that issues affecting trust, reliability or perceived risk are more likely to lead to the absence of sharing.

Other challenges, including privacy, legal constraints and technical barriers, display intermediate configurations, with occasional sharing remaining predominant and only limited variation in systematic or non-sharing behaviours.

Overall, the results suggest that while data sharing is consistently situational across all conditions, different types of challenges influence its outcomes in distinct ways, with

operational barriers affecting continuity and trust-related concerns more directly impacting the decision to share (Figure 8.8).

Challenges (D13) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	1	9	4
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	2	15	2
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	1	8	1
Concerns about data misuse	1	17	3
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	0	16	1
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	3	16	2
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	1	12	1
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	1	17	1
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	1	11	0

Figure 8.8 Relationship between the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13) and data sharing practices (D10)

Profile: Open Data & Policy-Oriented

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

C1.3a Data management: usage

→ Yes

C1.4a Knowledge representation: usage

→ Yes

D6. Do you mainly use open or closed formats?

→ Open formats

D10.1. If yes, how do you share your data?

→ Publicly with the broader community

OR

D11. How is your data made accessible?

→ Made accessible through a public repository or generic-purpose Open-access platforms (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare) >50%

OR

D12. Under what licensing terms is your data made available?

→ Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain) or under Creative Commons >50%

Base: 77 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Open Data & Policy-Oriented* profile represents respondents who adopt open and shareable data practices in their work with cultural heritage information. These actors rely on data management and knowledge representation tools while favouring the use of open formats and practices that enable data accessibility and reuse.

Their data are frequently shared publicly, made accessible through repositories or distributed under open licensing conditions. These practices support broader dissemination and reuse of cultural heritage information and contribute to more transparent and accessible data environments.

Overall, this profile reflects respondents whose data practices are oriented toward openness, accessibility and responsible sharing of cultural heritage data.

Summary of findings

Access models

Responses indicate a strong preference for open and freely accessible digital tools. The vast majority report using free, open-access services (88.3%), indicating that activities related to open data and policy development are largely supported by tools that do not impose financial or access barriers (*Figure 9.1*).

Open and collaborative technological environments also appear particularly important. Open-source software is used by 70.1% of respondents, while custom-built or in-house developed tools are reported by 51.9%, suggesting that institutions involved in open data initiatives frequently rely on adaptable infrastructures or develop their own technical solutions.

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	68	88.3%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	54	70.1%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	40	51.9%

Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	31	40.3%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	23	29.9%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	14	18.2%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	5	6.5%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	3	3.9%

Figure 9.1 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4).

Other access models are less central. Free services with licensing conditions (40.3%) and paid licence-based tools (29.9%) remain present but secondary, while subscription-based services (18.2%) are used by a smaller share of respondents. More occasional access models include pay-per-use systems (6.5%) and trial-based services (3.9%).

Overall, these results suggest that Open Data and Policy-oriented professionals operate in environments strongly aligned with open infrastructures, open-source ecosystems and flexible technological solutions, which support data accessibility, reuse and governance initiatives

Data management and storage

Institutional data governance practices within this profile appear uneven. While 26.0% of respondents report that their institution follows a published Data Management Plan, a majority indicate that this is not the case (50.6%), and 23.4% are unsure whether such a plan exists. This suggests that even among professionals engaged with open data and policy topics, formalised data management frameworks are not consistently implemented at the institutional level.

Storage practices show a mix of institutional infrastructures and more accessible storage environments. Local storage is widely used, with 46.8% of respondents indicating that more than half of their datasets are stored locally. Institutional servers also play an important role, with 68.9% reporting that a majority of their data are stored on institutional infrastructures (*Figure 9.2*).

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	16 (20.8%)	25 (32.5%)	7 (9.1%)	29 (37.7%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	42 (54.5%)	19 (24.7%)	10 (13.0%)	6 (7.8%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	30 (39.0%)	29 (37.7%)	7 (9.1%)	11 (14.3%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	17 (22.1%)	32 (41.6%)	17 (22.1%)	11 (14.3%)

Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	64 (83.1%)	8 (10.4%)	2 (2.6%)	3 (3.9%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	14 (18.2%)	10 (13.0%)	17 (22.1%)	36 (46.8%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	30 (39.0%)	29 (37.7%)	13 (16.9%)	5 (6.5%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	47 (61.0%)	18 (23.4%)	7 (9.1%)	5 (6.5%)
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	41 (53.2%)	21 (27.3%)	9 (11.7%)	6 (7.8%)

Figure 9.2 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9).

Open repositories appear less dominant as primary storage environments. Only 20.8% of respondents report storing more than half of their datasets in domain-specific repositories, and 23.4% do so in generic open-access repositories. Commercial cloud platforms are used for the majority of datasets by 36.4% of respondents, while collaborative platforms such as GitHub or Wikidata are used as primary storage environments by a smaller share (23.4%).

Taken together, these findings highlight that although this profile is strongly associated with open data principles, storage practices still rely heavily on local and institutional infrastructures, while open repositories are used more selectively rather than as the main storage environment for most datasets.

Challenges to data sharing and reuse

Respondents identify several obstacles that limit the effective implementation of open data practices. The most frequently mentioned issue concerns data or metadata quality, reliability and completeness (72.7%), indicating that concerns about data quality remain a major barrier to wider sharing and reuse (Figure 9.3).

Legal and organisational constraints are also significant. Around half of respondents highlight legal or contractual restrictions (50.6%) and the additional effort required to prepare data for sharing (49.4%). Confidentiality and privacy concerns (45.5%) further complicate the process of making data openly accessible.

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data?	Count	%
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	56	72.7%
Legal or contractual restrictions, intellectual property rights / other legal issues	39	50.6%
Extra effort is required, lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	38	49.4%
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (including GDPR compliance when data refers to specific persons, e.g. archival material)	35	45.5%
Non-digital data, resource is not digitised	29	37.7%

Technical barriers (e.g., difficulty accessing or using the required tools or platforms, large format files unable to be shared by common open means)	27	35.1%
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	26	33.8%
Concerns about data misuse	25	32.5%
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	12	15.6%

Figure 9.3 Challenges in data sharing, consultation and reuse (D13).

Other barriers include non-digitised resources (37.7%), technical limitations (35.1%), and lack of appropriate infrastructures for sharing (33.8%). A smaller share of respondents also mention concerns about data misuse (32.5%) and unclear guidelines regarding sharing (15.6%).

Needs & expectations

Users express needs centred on interoperability, standardisation and the effective sharing and reuse of data across systems and communities.

The main challenges relate to interoperability issues and technical limitations, combined with financial constraints and the complexity of managing heterogeneous datasets. Data quality, standardisation and documentation are also significant concerns, particularly in relation to ensuring that data can be meaningfully reused. Skills gaps and the learning curve further affect the adoption and implementation of open data practices.

Legal, organisational and sustainability-related issues also emerge, especially in relation to data governance, licensing and the long-term maintenance of open infrastructures.

In terms of expectations, respondents strongly emphasise improved interoperability and integration between systems, supported by shared standards and metadata harmonisation. There is also a clear demand for better support for collaboration and data sharing, including more accessible open repositories and improved data management and retrieval functionalities (*Figure 9.4*).

Training and documentation remain important to support broader adoption, alongside the need for more sustainable, open and cost-effective solutions. Infrastructure improvements and scalable storage are also relevant. Advanced functionalities such as automation and AI are considered useful, particularly for data processing and enrichment, but remain secondary to core needs around integration, standardisation and openness.

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	13	41.9%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	9	29.0%
Training, documentation and capacity building	8	25.8%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	7	22.6%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	7	22.6%

Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	6	19.4%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	6	19.4%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	6	19.4%
Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	6	19.4%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	5	16.1%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	5	16.1%
Connectivity and offline functionality	3	9.7%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	3	9.7%

Figure 9.4 Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3).

Infrastructure and archiving practices

Respondents in this profile report a range of practices used to preserve and manage cultural heritage data. The most frequently mentioned approaches include backup and redundancy mechanisms (41.6%), followed by automation and scripting for archiving workflows (37.7%), and the use of metadata and documentation practices (33.8%). Collaboration with trusted repositories (32.5%) and the adoption of standardised practices and formats (31.2%) also appear relatively common.

Other approaches are reported less frequently. These include local storage solutions (27.3%), cloud-based archiving (24.7%), physical archiving practices (23.4%), and digital preservation platforms (22.1%). More specialised practices, such as institutional enterprise systems (16.9%), periodic data review and migration (11.7%), data lifecycle management (9.1%), and encryption or security measures (6.5%), appear in a smaller share of responses (*Figure 9.5*).

Overall, the results indicate a combination of practical data preservation measures and structured archiving practices, with particular emphasis on redundancy, automation and documentation as core elements of institutional data management infrastructures.

F4. What methods and systems do you use to store, archive and curate data within your organisation?	Count	%
Backup and redundancy (creating duplicate copies of data for safety, stored across multiple locations to ensure resilience)	32	41.6%
Automation and scripting (using automated workflows and scripts to manage archiving tasks, including scheduled backups and data migration)	29	37.7%
Metadata and documentation (archiving data along with descriptive information, annotations, and contextual details for easier discovery and use)	26	33.8%
Collaboration with trusted repositories (depositing data in recognised repositories or archives that ensure long-term preservation and accessibility)	25	32.5%
Standardised practices and formats (following established protocols and using standard file formats to ensure long-term data preservation and compatibility)	24	31.2%
Local storage solutions (storing data on physical devices, such as external drives, NAS devices, or optical media)	21	27.3%
Cloud-based archiving (using cloud platforms for data storage, including general cloud services and dedicated archival solutions)	19	24.7%

Physical archiving (maintaining physical records or media, such as printed documents, microfilm, or magnetic tapes, in secure environments)	18	23.4%
Digital preservation platforms (employing specialised tools and systems designed for long-term digital preservation and compliance with archival standards)	17	22.1%
Institutional or enterprise systems (archiving within organisational repositories or enterprise systems like research data centres and DAM/CMS platforms)	13	16.9%
Periodic review and migration (regularly reviewing archived data for obsolescence and migrating to updated formats or systems to maintain usability over time)	9	11.7%
Data tiering and lifecycle management (managing data by moving it between storage types based on usage, transitioning from active to archival storage over time)	7	9.1%
Encryption and security (protecting archived data through encryption and implementing strict access controls to ensure confidentiality and integrity)	5	6.5%

Figure 9.5 Data storage, archiving and curation methods (F4).

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the Open Data and Policy-Oriented profile reflects professionals who are strongly engaged with data governance, openness and institutional frameworks for data sharing. Their practices are characterised by a clear reliance on open-access and open-source digital tools, often complemented by in-house or institutionally developed infrastructures.

At the same time, the results highlight several structural challenges affecting the implementation of open data principles. While respondents are closely involved with policy and governance aspects of data, formal data management plans remain unevenly adopted, and storage practices continue to rely significantly on local or institutional infrastructures rather than dedicated open repositories.

Barriers to broader data sharing are largely linked to data quality issues, legal constraints and the effort required to prepare datasets for publication, reflecting the complexity of implementing open data in practice. Respondents also emphasise the importance of improving interoperability, strengthening infrastructure and expanding collaborative frameworks to support more effective data reuse.

Taken together, these findings suggest that this profile plays a key role in promoting open data policies and governance frameworks, while simultaneously addressing the practical, legal and infrastructural challenges that influence the real-world implementation of open and reusable cultural heritage data.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This section examines the relationship between storage environments (D9), standardisation practices (F4), and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5).

The objective is to assess whether formal governance frameworks are reflected in more structured data management practices, and to identify the extent to which storage

configurations and standardisation approaches align with institutional planning within this profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) x Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between storage configurations and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a weak and uneven alignment between infrastructural practices and formal governance frameworks (*Figure 9.6*).

Across most storage environments, the absence of a Data Management Plan represents the most frequent condition. This is particularly evident in institutional, cloud-based and local environments, where respondents reporting the absence of a DMP consistently outnumber those indicating its presence. This suggests that the use of structured or widely adopted storage infrastructures does not necessarily correspond to the existence of formalised data governance frameworks.

At the same time, a substantial proportion of respondents report uncertainty regarding the presence of a DMP, especially in local, cloud-based and collaborative environments. This indicates limited awareness of institutional governance conditions, particularly in more distributed or less centralised storage contexts.

A more differentiated pattern emerges in domain-specific repositories, where the presence of a Data Management Plan becomes the most frequent condition and uncertainty is comparatively low. This suggests that more specialised and professionally managed environments are more likely to be associated with structured governance frameworks and clearer organisational practices.

Other environments, including public repositories and collaborative platforms, display intermediate configurations, with a predominance of absent or unknown DMPs and only limited evidence of systematic governance.

Storage (D9) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	8	15	13
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	8	6	2
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	5	12	11
Institutional servers or websites	15	28	10
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	6	8	4
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	5	7	6
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	3	7	2
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	2	2	1
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	4	9	2

Figure 9.6 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Overall, the results indicate that storage practices within this profile are only weakly aligned with formal data management frameworks. The presence of a Data Management Plan does not systematically correspond to the use of particular storage environments, highlighting a gap between infrastructural practices and institutional governance.

Standardised practices and formats (F4) x Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between standardisation practices and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a weak and inconsistent alignment between formal governance frameworks and operational data management practices.

Across several technically oriented practices – including automation and scripting, backup and redundancy, and the use of digital preservation platforms – the absence of a Data Management Plan generally predominates. This suggests that even more advanced or structured archiving practices are often implemented independently of formal governance frameworks (Figure 9.7).

Standardisation (F4) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Automation and scripting (using automated workflows and scripts to manage archiving tasks, including scheduled backups and data migration)	5	17	7
Backup and redundancy (creating duplicate copies of data for safety, stored across multiple locations to ensure resilience)	5	20	7
Cloud-based archiving (using cloud platforms for data storage, including general cloud services and dedicated archival solutions)	7	7	5
Collaboration with trusted repositories (depositing data in recognised repositories or archives that ensure long-term preservation and accessibility)	9	10	6
Data tiering and lifecycle management (managing data by moving it between storage types based on usage, transitioning from active to archival storage over time)	3	3	1
Digital preservation platforms (employing specialised tools and systems designed for long-term digital preservation and compliance with archival standards)	3	11	3
Encryption and security (protecting archived data through encryption and implementing strict access controls to ensure confidentiality and integrity)	0	4	1
Institutional or enterprise systems (archiving within organisational repositories or enterprise systems like research data centres and DAM/CMS platforms)	3	7	3
Local storage solutions (storing data on physical devices, such as external drives, NAS devices, or optical media)	5	9	7
Metadata and documentation (archiving data along with descriptive information, annotations, and contextual details for easier discovery and use)	7	15	4
Periodic review and migration (regularly reviewing archived data for obsolescence and migrating to updated formats or systems to maintain usability over time)	0	6	3
Physical archiving (maintaining physical records or media, such as printed documents, microfilm, or magnetic tapes, in secure environments)	2	13	3
Standardised practices and formats (following established protocols and using standard file formats to ensure long-term data preservation and compatibility)	4	17	3

Figure 9.7 Relationship between the use of standardised practices and formats for data preservation (F4) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Other practices display more balanced configurations. Cloud-based archiving, collaboration with trusted repositories, and metadata-related practices show a more even distribution between the presence and absence of a DMP, indicating only a partial and non-systematic association with institutional governance. In particular, metadata and documentation, as well as standardised formats, show an almost perfectly balanced distribution across all categories, highlighting a complete decoupling between these core practices and formal data management planning.

A further element concerns the relatively high proportion of respondents reporting uncertainty about the presence of a DMP across multiple practices. This suggests limited awareness of governance conditions, even in contexts where structured or formalised practices are in place.

Overall, the results indicate that standardisation practices within this profile are largely independent of formal governance frameworks. The presence of a Data Management Plan does not systematically correspond to more structured or advanced data management approaches, pointing to a gap between institutional planning and operational implementation.

Standardised practices and formats (F4) x Where data are stored or archived (D9)

The cross-analysis between standardisation practices and storage environments shows a broadly distributed pattern, with no single configuration clearly dominating the implementation of specific practices.

Across most practices, institutional environments consistently represent the most frequent configuration, although without reaching dominant proportions. Local storage also maintains a stable presence across all practices, indicating that individual or decentralised environments continue to play a relevant role even in more structured data management activities.

At the same time, all practices are distributed across multiple storage environments, with secondary configurations – including domain-specific repositories, collaborative platforms and self-hosted solutions – contributing in a relatively consistent manner. This suggests that standardisation practices are not confined to specific infrastructures but rather develop across hybrid and overlapping environments.

More marginal configurations, such as social networks and subscription-based platforms, show minimal involvement across all practices, confirming their limited role in structured data management.

Overall, the results indicate that standardisation practices within this profile are not strongly tied to specific storage environments. Instead, they are implemented across a range of configurations, with a moderate prevalence of institutional settings but without exclusive or clearly dominant associations (*Figure 9.8*).

Standardisation (F4) x Storage (D9)	Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor)	Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	Institutional servers or websites	Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, Wikidata)	Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	Social networks or forums (e.g. Research Gate)	Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	
Automation and scripting (using automated workflows and scripts to manage archiving tasks, including scheduled backups and data migration)	16		8	5	23	7	8	1	2	10
Backup and redundancy (creating duplicate copies of data for safety, stored across multiple locations to ensure resilience)	15		6	7	26	6	7	0	0	9
Cloud-based archiving (using cloud platforms for data storage, including general cloud services and dedicated archival solutions)	12		6	6	14	6	6	1	2	6
Collaboration with trusted repositories (depositing data in recognised repositories or archives that ensure long-term preservation and accessibility)	12		8	6	19	6	8	2	2	6
Data tiering and lifecycle management (managing data by moving it between storage types based on usage, transitioning from active to archival storage over time)	3		3	1	4	3	2	0	1	2
Digital preservation platforms (employing specialised tools and systems designed for long-term digital preservation and compliance with archival standards)	9		7	4	14	3	5	1	2	6
Encryption and security (protecting archived data through encryption and implementing strict access controls to ensure confidentiality and integrity)	1		0	1	4	1	1	0	0	1
Institutional or enterprise systems (archiving within organisational repositories or enterprise systems like research data centres and DAM/CMS platforms)	5		3	3	11	3	3	0	2	4
Local storage solutions (storing data on physical devices, such as external drives, NAS devices, or optical media)	12		7	6	19	6	7	0	2	7
Metadata and documentation (archiving data along with descriptive information, annotations, and contextual details for easier discovery and use)	13		9	4	20	7	8	1	2	8
Periodic review and migration (regularly reviewing archived data for obsolescence and migrating to updated formats or systems to maintain usability over time)	4		2	4	8	1	2	0	1	1
Physical archiving (maintaining physical records or media, such as printed documents, microfilm, or magnetic tapes, in secure environments)	6		4	3	16	3	3	1	3	2
Standardised practices and formats (following established protocols and using standard file formats to ensure long-term data preservation and compatibility)	10		7	3	19	5	7	1	1	8

Figure 9.8 Relationship between the use of standardised practices and formats for data preservation (F4) and where data are stored or archived (D9)

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This section examines the relationship between formal governance frameworks – including the presence of Data Management Plans (D5) and different access models (C4) – and the challenges experienced in data management and sharing practices.

The objective is to assess whether different governance conditions are associated with variations in perceived barriers, and to identify the extent to which formal structures influence the practical constraints encountered in this profile.

Challenges (D13) x Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between perceived challenges and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a generally weak relationship between formal governance frameworks and the reduction of operational barriers.

Across most challenges – including issues related to data quality, legal constraints, technical limitations and resource availability – the absence of a Data Management Plan remains the most frequent condition. At the same time, a non-negligible proportion of respondents reporting the presence of a DMP continues to experience these difficulties,

indicating that formal governance does not systematically translate into more effective data management conditions (Figure 9.9).

Challenges (D13) x DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	16	26	14
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	9	18	8
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	10	20	9
Concerns about data misuse	8	10	7
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	8	22	8
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	6	13	8
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	12	11	6
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	6	13	7
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	0	9	3

Figure 9.9 Relationship between the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

An interesting deviation from this pattern emerges in relation to non-digital data. In this case, respondents reporting the presence of a DMP slightly outnumber those without one. This suggests that this specific barrier is not mitigated by governance frameworks, but rather reflects structural conditions linked to the nature of the data itself. More formalised or institutionally embedded contexts – where DMPs are more likely to be present – may also be those dealing with more complex or partially non-digitised collections.

A further relevant element concerns the relatively high proportion of respondents who are uncertain about the presence of a DMP across multiple challenges, indicating limited awareness of governance conditions even where such frameworks may exist.

Overall, the results suggest that while Data Management Plans represent an important element of formal governance, their presence alone does not significantly reduce the range of challenges experienced. This points to a persistent gap between institutional planning and the practical conditions under which data are managed and shared.

Access models (C4) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between access models and perceived challenges does not reveal a strong or differentiated relationship between the type of access and the nature of the barriers encountered (Figure 9.10).

Access models (C4) x Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	49	30	35	21	36	24	25	25	12
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	23	17	19	12	15	13	12	12	5
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	2	2	3	1	3	2	1	2	1
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	11	8	10	2	7	3	6	3	2
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	19	12	15	5	10	8	11	11	5
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	4	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	0
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	32	19	23	8	19	13	15	11	6
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	42	22	28	11	26	17	20	16	9

Figure 9.10 Relationship between access models (C4) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Across all access configurations, the internal distribution of challenges remains remarkably consistent. Issues related to data quality, legal constraints, effort required for data preparation, and privacy concerns systematically represent the most frequent barriers, while other challenges – such as technical limitations, infrastructure gaps, or unclear guidelines – appear with lower but comparable proportions.

This consistency suggests that the type of access model – whether open, licensed, or subscription-based – does not significantly influence the structure of the challenges experienced. Instead, barriers appear to reflect broader and more structural conditions related to data management practices, rather than being shaped by specific access configurations.

Overall, the results indicate that perceived challenges are largely independent of access models, pointing to systemic issues that persist across different types of services and access conditions. This suggests that improving access models alone would not be sufficient to address the main barriers to open data implementation.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between storage environments and perceived challenges reveals a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with only limited variation between different types of infrastructure (Figure 9.11).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	25	13	16	13	18	9	11	14	8
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	15	6	10	4	9	5	10	3	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	19	12	13	14	15	13	7	11	4
Institutional servers or websites	39	26	28	14	24	18	23	17	11
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	14	6	9	5	9	6	7	5	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	14	7	11	4	9	4	6	4	1
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	5	6	3	6	5	6	3	4	2
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	4	1	2	1	2	1	4	0	0
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	11	8	10	5	7	3	4	4	4

Figure 9.11 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Across all storage environments, issues related to data quality systematically emerge as the most frequently reported barrier, followed by legal constraints and the effort required to prepare data for sharing. Other challenges – including technical limitations, infrastructure gaps, and concerns related to misuse or privacy – appear with lower but relatively stable proportions across configurations.

Importantly, the overall distribution of challenges remains largely similar regardless of the storage environment considered.

Overall, the results suggest that challenges related to data management and sharing are not significantly shaped by storage environments. Instead, they reflect broader structural conditions that persist across different infrastructural configurations within this profile.

Profile: Professional Heritage Practitioners

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

A5 – type of institution:

- LAM (library, archive, museum)
- governmental agency or other public authority
- historical monuments, listed buildings, sites
- gallery or exhibition space

A6 – professional activity:

- cultural heritage conservation and preservation
- museology and collection management
- documentation, archives and information management
- urban and spatial planning

A5 & A6:

- Excluding university/research institutions and research-oriented fields

Base: 188 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The Professional Heritage Practitioners profile represents respondents working in operational, curatorial, conservation, site-management and documentation roles within cultural heritage institutions and public heritage environments. Unlike research-driven or academically anchored actors, this group is primarily engaged in the day-to-day management, preservation, documentation and mediation of heritage assets.

Their professional positioning implies direct interaction with collections, sites, archival materials and built environments, as well as responsibility for ensuring continuity, accessibility and regulatory compliance. The analysis below focuses on their technological configuration, data practices and infrastructural orientation within applied heritage contexts.

Summary of findings

Profile positioning

Professional practitioners primarily engage with physical heritage assets, which represent the majority of the materials they work with (54.3%). Their activities also involve a significant use of digital representations, such as digitised images, scans and 3D models (24.5%), while non-digital reproductions play a more limited but still relevant role (11.2%). Multimedia and born-digital assets are only marginally present in their workflows (Figure 10.1).

B2. Which of the following do you mostly use in your work?	Count	%
Physical objects (e.g. artworks, sites, natural specimens, ...)	102	54.3%
Digital representations (e.g., digitised versions of objects, such as high-resolution scans, photographs, or 3D models)	46	24.5%
Non-digital reproductions (e.g., printed photos, casts, or other physical replicas of the object)	21	11.2%
Born-digital assets	10	5.3%
Multimedia assets (e.g., audio recordings, videos, or interactive media related to the object)	9	4.8%

Figure 10.1 Types of heritage assets mostly used in professional activities (B2).

Overall, this profile is characterised by a strong connection to tangible heritage, with digital resources supporting, rather than replacing, hands-on and object-based practices.

Tools and services

The technological configuration of Professional Heritage Practitioners shows a pragmatic and selective adoption of digital tools. In the annotation and analysis domain, manual annotation remains the most established practice (38.8%), while OCR/HTR reaches 18.6%. More advanced automated approaches, such as NLP-based content analysis (7.4%) or automatic shape recognition (5.9%), remain marginal, and 29.3% report not using annotation tools at all.

Engagement with 3D and spatial technologies is differentiated rather than widespread. 3D scanning and modelling tools reach 46.8%, while GIS (26.6%) and VR/AR/MR (26.1%) show moderate diffusion. BIM/HBIM (13.8%) and LiDAR (19.1%) remain more specialised. At the same time, 45.2% indicate no engagement with 3D or spatial tools, confirming that advanced visual production technologies are present but not systematically embedded (*Figure 10.2*).

C1.2b. What types of 3D, spatial or visualisation tools do you use or would like to use?	Count	%
3D scanning or modeling, rendering and reconstruction	88	46.8%
Answered No to C1.2a (Are you using 3D, spatial or visualisation tools?)	85	45.2%
Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial representation of information	50	26.6%
Virtual Reality (VR) / Augmented Reality (AR) / Mixed Reality (MR)	49	26.1%
Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LIDAR)	36	19.1%
Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM)	26	13.8%

Figure 10.2 3D, spatial and visualisation tools (C1.2b)

Data management tools display a more consolidated pattern. Data collection management and structuring reaches 39.9%, and storage and retrieval systems 29.3%, whereas interoperability and API integration remain limited (14.4%). Formal knowledge representation tools show selective uptake: knowledge graphs (26.1%) and taxonomies or controlled vocabularies (23.4%) are present within a segment of the profile, but 44.1% report not using such tools.

Types, formats and documentation

The types of data handled by professional practitioners are strongly rooted in archival and documentary materials. Historical or archival records represent the most prevalent category (78.7%), followed by textual or written information (65.4%) and administrative or regulatory records (49.5%). Descriptive metadata (41.5%) and published research outputs (36.2%) are also widely used, while spatial/geographical and quantitative data

reach more moderate levels (28.2%). More specialised data types, such as experimental results, machine-generated data or biological information, remain marginal (*Figure 10.3*).

D3. What types of data do you typically create, consult or reuse?	Count	%
Historical or archival records (legacy information, records from the past)	148	78.7%
Textual or written information (e.g., narratives, documentation, reports, articles)	123	65.4%
Administrative or regulatory records (government data, legal information, regulations)	93	49.5%
Descriptive metadata (summaries or categorisations of datasets)	78	41.5%
Published research outputs (previously disseminated academic or scientific findings)	68	36.2%
Observational findings (field notes, natural observations, event logs)	60	31.9%
Quantitative data (numerical data, statistics, measured values)	53	28.2%
Spatial / geographical information (location-based data, maps, geographic features)	53	28.2%
Survey and interview responses (data from consultations, interviews, or polls)	30	16.0%
Environmental measurements (data from ecological monitoring or natural systems)	24	12.8%
Experimental results (outcomes from controlled, reproducible experiments)	18	9.6%
Social or behavioural information (data from social networks, behavioural studies)	13	6.9%
Structural or spatial representations (conceptual models, spatial relationships)	13	6.9%
Machine-generated insights (automated logs, data from sensors or IoT devices)	11	5.9%
Biological or genomic information (DNA sequences, biological samples, genetic data)	0	0.0%

Figure 10.3 *Types of data created, consulted or reused (D3).*

This data configuration is reflected in format usage. Image and document formats dominate daily practice (close to 90,0%), followed by presentations and spreadsheets, while more technically specialised formats, such as statistical or streaming data, remain limited.

Format usage follows a mixed approach. A comparable share of respondents report using both open and closed formats (35.6%) or mainly open formats (34.6%), while a smaller proportion rely primarily on proprietary formats (12.8%). A relevant share (17.0%) indicates uncertainty, suggesting that format choices are often context-dependent rather than guided by a fully standardised strategy.

Documentation practices combine informal and structured approaches. Simple notes (41.5%), manual documentation files (35.1%) and annotations directly on data (33.0%) remain widespread. At the same time, more structured practices are present, including metadata creation (29.8%), the use of documentation systems (22.9%) and adherence to established standards (23.4%). Automated documentation systems remain marginal (6.9%).

Production processes and objectives

Data production within the Professional Heritage Practitioners profile is strongly anchored in archival, documentary and site-based practices. Archival research represents the most widespread process (78.7%), followed by digitisation, transcription and 3D/spatial documentation (55.9%). Fieldwork (49.5%), examination and analytical methods (41.5%), and observation (41.5%) are also recurrent. By contrast, computational methods (11.2%) and experimental approaches (8.0%) remain marginal (*Figure 10.4*).

D1. What processes do you typically use to produce data?	Count	%
Archival research (e.g., consulting historical records, documents, or archives)	148	78.7%
Digitisation, transcription and 3D and spatial documentation	105	55.9%
Fieldwork (e.g., on-site data collection or acquisition, conservation treatment documentation and monitoring)	93	49.5%
Examination / analysis (e.g., visual inspection, instrumental analysis, laboratory testing, material analysis and testing, imaging and spectroscopy methods)	78	41.5%
Observation (e.g., direct or indirect observation of phenomena or processes)	78	41.5%
Processing data / resources created by others or reprocessing your own primary data	55	29.3%
Interviews or focus groups (e.g., qualitative data collection through discussion)	38	20.2%
Surveys / questionnaires (e.g., collecting data through participant responses)	37	19.7%
Crowdsourcing or citizen science (e.g., engaging non-specialists to gather data)	23	12.2%
Computational methods (e.g., simulations, algorithms, or modeling)	21	11.2%
Experimental methods (e.g., controlled experiments or trials, material reconstructions, accelerated ageing tests)	15	8.0%

Figure 10.4 Data production processes (D1).

The primary objectives of data creation reflect this preservation-oriented configuration. Archiving or preserving information is by far the dominant purpose (88.3%), followed by cataloguing (61.7%) and the creation of conservation or restoration plans (56.9%). Answering research questions reaches 56.4%, but it coexists with reporting (46.8%) and public communication activities (44.7%). Monitoring, evaluation and decision-support functions remain present but secondary.

The objectives guiding data production and reuse reinforce this preservation-oriented logic. The most frequent aim is to support the management and protection of heritage assets (69.7%), followed by improving dataset completeness and best practices (57.4%) and public engagement (58.0%). Conducting new analyses reaches 48.9%, while tool development and advanced modelling remain more limited

Data management and storage

Formal data governance is uneven. Only 31% of respondents report following a published Data Management Plan, while 38% do not and 30% are unsure.

Storage practices reveal a predominantly institutional configuration (*Figure 10.5*).

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	30 (16.0%)	55 (29.3%)	26 (13.8%)	77 (41.0%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	135 (71.8%)	35 (18.6%)	8 (4.3%)	10 (5.3%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	147 (78.2%)	27 (14.4%)	3 (1.6%)	11 (5.9%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	66 (35.1%)	68 (36.2%)	31 (16.5%)	23 (12.2%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	171 (91.0%)	14 (7.4%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (1.6%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	46 (24.5%)	31 (16.5%)	30 (16.0%)	81 (43.1%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	150 (79.8%)	31 (16.5%)	7 (3.7%)	0 (0.0%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	138 (73.4%)	45 (23.9%)	1 (0.5%)	4 (2.1%)
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	120 (63.8%)	39 (20.7%)	13 (6.9%)	16 (8.5%)

Figure 10.5 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9).

A majority store more than half of their data either on institutional servers (59.1%) or locally (54.8%). Cloud-based commercial platforms play a more moderate role (28.7%), while self-hosted solutions remain limited (15.4%). Domain-specific repositories (9.6%) and public or generic open-access repositories (7.5%) are rarely used as primary storage environments. Overall, storage practices appear fragmented across personal, institutional and commercial infrastructures.

Sharing, licensing and challenges

Data sharing is common but not universal: 20.7% report always sharing data, and 73.4% do so at least sometimes.

Licensing practices reveal a controlled and context-dependent approach to data sharing. Around one third share more than half of their data openly without restrictions (31.4%), while a similar proportion restricts sharing to specific purposes (31.4%). Sharing upon request (28.2%) and the use of specific open licences (21.8%) are also relevant, alongside access restrictions (18.1%) and formal agreements (17.5%).

Challenges in sharing and reuse reflect governance complexity. Confidentiality and privacy concerns (57.4%), legal or contractual restrictions (55.9%), and data or metadata quality issues (54.8%) are among the most cited barriers. Lack of time or resources (50.0%), non-digitised materials (52.7%) and infrastructural limitations (45.2%) further

constrain reuse. Technical barriers and unclear guidelines are also present, though less dominant (Figure 10.6).

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data?	Count	%
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (including GDPR compliance when data refers to specific persons, e.g. archival material)	108	57.4%
Legal or contractual restrictions, intellectual property rights / other legal issues	105	55.9%
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	103	54.8%
Non-digital data, resource is not digitised	99	52.7%
Extra effort is required, lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	94	50.0%
Concerns about data misuse	90	47.9%
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	85	45.2%
Technical barriers (e.g., difficulty accessing or using the required tools or platforms, large format files unable to be shared by common open means)	69	36.7%
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	55	29.3%

Figure 10.6 Challenges in data sharing, consultation and reuse (D13).

Collaboration

Collaboration with development teams appears structured but not systematic across the profile. A segment engages through regular meetings and iterative testing, while other forms of interaction – such as collaborative platforms, workshops or structured requirement documentation – remain more limited.

Communication practices are therefore present but unevenly distributed, often depending on specific projects or contexts rather than being embedded in consistent workflows. Overall, collaboration tends to rely on established but relatively traditional interaction patterns, with more advanced or integrated approaches playing a secondary role (Figure 10.7).

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams?	Count	%
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	44	23.4%
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	33	17.6%
Using collaborative tools like Slack, Trello, or Jira, or Figma	21	11.2%
Via email or written reports only	21	11.2%
Participation in workshops or hackathons	19	10.1%
Through detailed requirement documentation	18	9.6%

Figure 10.7 Collaboration practices with development teams (E6).

Needs & expectations

Professional practitioners express needs primarily linked to operational constraints and the practical implementation of digital tools within everyday workflows.

The main difficulties concern technical and infrastructure limitations, together with financial constraints and the availability of adequate resources. These factors directly affect the capacity to adopt and maintain digital solutions. Skills gaps and training needs also remain significant, particularly in relation to the diversity and complexity of tools used in practice (Figure 10.8).

C2. What difficulties do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?	Count	%
Technical, infrastructure and hardware limitations	35	44.9%
Financial constraints and costs	34	43.6%
Skills, training and learning curve	31	39.7%
Interoperability and system integration issues	26	33.3%
Connectivity and access limitations	22	28.2%
Human resources and staffing constraints	20	25.6%
Legal, copyright and data governance concerns	18	23.1%
Usability and user experience limitations	16	20.5%
Vendor dependency, tool sustainability and support limitations	12	15.4%
Organisational and policy barriers	11	14.1%
Data quality, heterogeneity and standardisation issues	10	12.8%
Data access and availability constraints	9	11.5%
Documentation, guidance and best practice gaps	9	11.5%
Domain-specific limitations and lack of fit	6	7.7%

Figure 10.8 Main difficulties in the use of digital tools and resources (C2).

Interoperability issues and limited integration between systems further complicate workflows, often requiring manual processes and reducing efficiency. Connectivity limitations and organisational constraints also play a role, especially in smaller or resource-constrained institutions.

In terms of expectations, practitioners emphasise the need for more interoperable and integrated systems, alongside improved user-friendliness and simplified interfaces. Training and capacity building are considered essential to support effective use. There is also a clear demand for more affordable solutions, better infrastructure and scalable storage.

Additional expectations include stronger alignment with shared standards, improved collaboration and data sharing mechanisms, and more sustainable and open solutions. Advanced functionalities are mentioned, but remain secondary to usability, cost and integration needs.

Overall Conclusion

Professional Heritage Practitioners emerge as a profile strongly anchored in institutional, documentary and preservation-oriented environments. Digital tools are

present and selectively adopted, particularly in areas directly supporting heritage documentation and management, while more advanced or highly automated approaches remain peripheral. Data production is primarily driven by archival, conservation and reporting logics rather than experimentation or computational innovation.

Governance practices reflect a layered and controlled approach to storage, sharing and licensing, shaped by legal, infrastructural and organisational constraints. Overall, this profile appears oriented toward consolidation and stewardship, prioritising reliability, compliance and institutional continuity over technological disruption.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the internal relationship between technological production practices (C1.2b), data management tools (C1.3b), documentation modalities (D8.1), and formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b).

The objective is to assess the degree of alignment between operational production activities, data structuring infrastructures and semantic formalisation within the Professional Practitioners profile, in order to identify patterns of consolidation as well as potential gaps between technological use and organisational maturity

3D modelling and visualisation (C1.2b) × Data management and storage (C1.3b)

The cross-analysis between 3D/spatial technologies and data management tools within the Professional Practitioners profile shows a relatively consistent internal configuration, with some meaningful variations across technological domains (*Figure 10.9*).

Across all production technologies considered, data collection management and structuring represents the most recurrent associated dimension. This suggests that when data management tools are adopted, they are primarily oriented toward organising and systematising internally produced data rather than toward advanced integration functions.

Production tools (C1.2b) × Data management (C1.3b)	Data collection management and structuring	Data interoperability and API integration	Resource storage and retrieval systems	Answered NO to C1.3a
3D scanning or modeling, rendering and reconstruction	36	12	30	10
Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM)	13	3	8	2
Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LIDAR)	15	6	12	3
Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial representation of information	21	12	14	3
Virtual Reality (VR) / Augmented Reality (AR) / Mixed Reality (MR)	24	9	11	5
Answered NO to C1.2a	32	12	20	21

Figure 10.9 Relationship between 3D modelling and visualisation tools (C1.2b) and data management and storage tools (C1.3b)

Resource storage and retrieval systems constitute the second most prominent dimension, particularly in relation to 3D scanning, modelling and LIDAR technologies, where infrastructural handling of large datasets appears more consolidated. By contrast, data interoperability and API integration remain comparatively less dominant across most technologies, although GIS displays a more balanced distribution, indicating a stronger integration-oriented configuration in spatial environments.

A distinct pattern emerges among respondents who report not using production tools (C1.2a = No). While a substantial portion of this group still engages in data collection and storage practices, the share of respondents not using data management tools at all is significantly higher compared to technology-active groups. This indicates that engagement in production technologies is associated with a more systematic adoption of data management infrastructures.

Overall, the table suggests that within the Professional Practitioners profile, production practices are generally accompanied by structured data management, particularly in terms of collection and storage. However, interoperability-oriented approaches remain secondary, and the alignment between production and integration functions is not uniformly consolidated across technological domains.

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)

The cross-analysis between documentation practices and formal knowledge representation tools within the Professional Practitioners profile reveals a gradual but uneven pattern of alignment.

Across the more informal documentation modalities – particularly simple notes and annotations – the share of respondents not using formal knowledge tools remains

comparatively high. In these cases, taxonomies and controlled vocabularies represent the most recurrent formal dimension, while ontologies remain marginal (*Figure 10.10*).

Documentation (D8.1) × Formal knowledge tools (C1.4b)	Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data	Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies	Ontologies	Answered NO to C1.4a
Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)	14	26	5	33
Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	12	23	6	21
Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)	19	19	7	21
Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)	11	15	8	9
Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)	12	17	8	19
Following established standards or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	14	14	6	10
Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)	4	5	2	2
Using controlled vocabularies (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)	10	8	4	8

Figure 10.10 Relationship between data documentation practices (D8.1) and the use of formal knowledge representation tools (C1.4b)

A more balanced configuration emerges in relation to manual documentation and metadata practices. While a significant proportion of respondents in these groups still report not using formal knowledge tools, the distribution among knowledge graphs, taxonomies and ontologies becomes more even, suggesting a transitional stage between informal documentation and more structured semantic engagement.

The most coherent alignment appears in the case of structured documentation systems and adherence to established standards. In these contexts, the proportion of respondents not using formal knowledge tools decreases substantially, and the distribution among knowledge graphs, taxonomies and ontologies becomes more balanced. Ontologies, although consistently the least widespread tool across the table, reach their highest proportional presence within these more formalised documentation environments.

Overall, the table suggests the existence of a gradual relationship between the level of documentation structuring and the adoption of formal knowledge representation tools. However, the persistent presence of respondents not using formal tools – even within intermediate documentation practices – indicates that semantic integration, while present, is not yet fully consolidated across the profile.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between licensing configurations (D12), data sharing practices (D10), perceived challenges (D13), and file format typologies (D6).

The objective is to analyse how governance choices, technical configurations and perceived barriers interact within the Professional Practitioners profile, and to assess whether sharing behaviours are primarily shaped by openness models, structural constraints, or risk-related considerations.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between licensing modalities and data sharing practices within the Professional Practitioners profile shows a consistent predominance of conditional sharing behaviours (*Figure 10.11*).

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	19	38	2
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	13	26	2
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	7	26	1
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	7	23	3
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	6	10	0
Upon request only	10	38	5
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	7	48	4
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before)	2	11	0

Figure 10.11 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and data sharing practices (D10)

Across all licensing configurations – including fully open models such as CC0 or Public Domain – “Yes, sometimes” represents the dominant response. “Yes, always” remains present but never becomes the prevailing modality, while “No” is consistently marginal. This indicates that the presence of a licence, even when fully open, does not automatically translate into systematic or unconditional sharing.

More restrictive configurations – such as sharing upon request, for specific purposes, under access restrictions or through formal agreements – further reinforce this situational pattern, with sharing practices clearly framed by contextual or procedural conditions.

Overall, the table suggests that within the Professional Practitioners profile, data sharing is broadly embedded but predominantly conditional.

Conditions under which data are shared (D12) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between licensing configurations and perceived challenges reveals the coexistence of structural and risk-related barriers across the Professional Practitioners profile (Figure 10.12).

Licensing (D12) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	37	36	29	25	29	20	34	25	17
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	29	26	24	15	26	18	27	20	14
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	20	16	17	18	16	19	20	13	11
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	20	22	22	22	18	11	14	14	9
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	9	11	12	9	8	7	7	5	5
Upon request only	28	31	29	31	21	19	25	18	16
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	27	32	28	31	28	21	27	22	14
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	6	9	5	7	7	6	6	4	4

Figure 10.12 Relationship between the conditions under which data are shared (D12) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Data and metadata quality, reliability and completeness emerge as a consistently recurrent challenge across nearly all licensing modalities, including fully open configurations. Alongside quality concerns, issues related to non-digital or not yet digitised resources and the additional effort required to prepare data for sharing remain significant. This indicates that structural constraints persist independently of the openness of the licensing model.

At the same time, risk-oriented challenges – particularly confidentiality and privacy concerns, legal or contractual restrictions, and concerns about data misuse – become more pronounced in more controlled sharing configurations, such as formal agreements, sharing upon request, or purpose-bound models. In these cases, governance practices appear closely linked to risk management and accountability considerations.

Overall, the table suggests that consolidated licensing practices do not eliminate structural barriers to sharing, while more restrictive or conditional configurations are

additionally shaped by legal and misuse-related concerns. Governance within this profile thus reflects a layered configuration of operational and risk-related constraints.

Open vs closed formats (D6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between file format typologies and sharing practices shows a stable predominance of situational sharing across all configurations (*Figure 10.13*).

Open vs Closed formats (D6) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Both	11	52	4
Open formats	19	42	4
Closed / proprietary formats	4	18	2
I don't know	5	26	1

Figure 10.13 Relationship between the use of open versus closed formats (D6) and data sharing practices (D10)

“Yes, sometimes” represents the dominant modality regardless of whether respondents use open formats, closed/proprietary formats, or a combination of both. Even among those working primarily with open formats, systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) does not become the prevailing pattern, although it appears proportionally higher than in closed-format environments. At the same time, the proportion of respondents reporting no sharing remains marginal across all groups.

Overall, the table suggests that while the use of open formats may facilitate more consistent sharing practices, file format typology alone does not determine sharing behaviour.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between storage infrastructures (D9), data sharing practices (D10), and perceived challenges (D13).

The objective is to assess whether different infrastructural environments are associated with variations in sharing behaviour and in the type and intensity of structural or governance-related barriers within the Professional Practitioners profile, and to identify whether specific storage configurations enable or constrain data circulation practices.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage infrastructures and sharing practices shows a continued predominance of situational sharing across all configurations (*Figure 10.14*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	19	79	5
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	7	11	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	10	41	3
Institutional servers or websites	27	81	3
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	6	7	1
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	4	3	0
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	1	4	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	2	1	0
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	9	18	2

Figure 10.14 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

“Yes, sometimes” remains the dominant modality regardless of whether respondents rely on local storage, commercial cloud platforms, or institutional servers. Even in environments more structurally oriented toward dissemination – such as domain-specific or public repositories and collaborative platforms – systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) becomes proportionally more visible but does not replace the situational pattern as the prevailing configuration. The proportion of respondents reporting no sharing remains marginal across all storage types.

Overall, the table suggests that storage infrastructures may facilitate more stable sharing practices in repository-based or institutional environments, but they do not fundamentally determine sharing behaviour.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

The cross-analysis between storage infrastructures and perceived challenges indicates that both structural and governance-related barriers remain present across all configurations (Figure 10.15).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	50	51	51	51	47	35	43	43	34
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	15	12	12	12	10	8	14	9	5
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	31	35	31	26	28	21	26	21	19
Institutional servers or websites	60	67	70	51	52	40	61	50	24
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	8	7	8	6	9	5	7	4	4
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	5	5	4	2	4	3	5	3	1
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	2	3	4	3	2	3	3	3	2
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	3	2	2	2	1	0	2	0	1
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	20	18	19	14	17	12	18	15	8

Figure 10.15 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Data and metadata quality, reliability and completeness consistently emerge among the most recurrent challenges, alongside confidentiality and legal or contractual restrictions. These dimensions appear across local storage, commercial cloud platforms and institutional servers, suggesting that infrastructural choices do not eliminate core structural and regulatory constraints.

Some differences in intensity are nevertheless visible. Institutional servers show a comparatively stronger association with legal and privacy-related concerns, while local storage environments display a more diffuse exposure across multiple types of challenges. Repository-based and collaborative platforms tend to present lower overall levels of reported challenges, although no infrastructure appears entirely free from structural or governance-related constraints.

Overall, the table suggests that storage environments influence the configuration and intensity of perceived barriers, but do not fundamentally remove the structural and risk-related conditions shaping data management and sharing practices within the profile.

Comparative Analysis – Collaboration

This block examines the relationship between collaboration modalities (E6), documentation practices (D8.1), and data sharing behaviours (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different forms of collaboration are associated with variations in the structuring of documentation and in the stability of sharing practices within the Professional Practitioners profile, and to identify whether more interactive or

formalised collaborative environments correspond to greater organisational maturity in data governance behaviours.

Collaboration (E6) × Documentation (D8.1)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and documentation practices shows a moderately differentiated but not polarised configuration within the Professional Practitioners profile (*Figure 10.16*).

Collaboration (E6) x Documentation (D8.1)	Manual documentation (e.g. creating standalone documentation files)	Annotations (e.g. marking up files or adding comments directly to data)	Simple notes (e.g. handwritten or digital notes)	Filling in metadata (e.g. titles, keywords, provenance information)	Following established standards or protocols (e.g. Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)	Using a documentation system (e.g. structured platforms or tools)	Using controlled vocabularies (e.g. Getty AAT, domain thesauri, local vocabularies)	Automated systems (auto-generated documentation or embedded metadata)
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	18	16	16	25	27	15	19	6
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	14	9	10	18	19	13	15	6
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	7	5	4	13	15	11	10	4
Participation in workshops or hackathons	10	10	9	12	13	6	9	1
Through detailed requirement documentation	10	6	8	12	11	9	8	3
Via email or written reports only	11	10	12	9	10	5	9	4

Figure 10.16 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data documentation practices (D8.1)

More interactive and structured collaboration forms – such as regular meetings, iterative testing processes and the use of collaborative digital tools – are associated with a comparatively stronger presence of structured documentation practices, particularly metadata filling, adherence to established standards and the use of controlled vocabularies. This suggests that sustained and iterative collaboration environments tend to foster more formalised documentation behaviours.

At the same time, more traditional or less interactive modalities – such as communication via email or written reports only – display a relatively stronger presence of informal practices, including simple notes and manual documentation. However, even in these cases, structured practices such as standards and metadata are not absent.

Overall, the table indicates that collaboration environments influence the degree of documentation structuring, but do not produce sharp divisions. Documentation practices within the profile remain hybrid, combining informal and formal modalities across different collaborative settings.

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between collaboration modalities and sharing practices confirms the predominance of situational sharing across all configurations (*Figure 10.17*).

Collaboration (E6) × Sharing (D10)			
	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Regular meetings and feedback sessions	13	30	1
Direct involvement in testing and iterative development	12	20	1
Collaborative tools (Slack, Jira, Figma, etc.)	6	14	1
Participation in workshops or hackathons	7	12	0
Through detailed requirement documentation	8	10	0
Via email or written reports only	8	12	1

Figure 10.17 Relationship between collaboration practices (E6) and data sharing practices (D10)

“Yes, sometimes” remains the dominant response regardless of the type of collaboration, while “No” is consistently marginal. More structured and iterative forms of collaboration – such as regular meetings, direct involvement in testing, or detailed requirement documentation – show a slightly higher proportional presence of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), but this does not overturn the overall situational pattern.

Overall, collaboration intensity appears to facilitate more stable sharing behaviours, although it does not fundamentally alter the dominant sharing pattern within the profile.

Profile: Semantic Engineer / Data Architect

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

C1.3a – Are you using data management and storage tools or services?

→ Yes

C1.4a – Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?

→ Yes

D6 – Do you mainly use open or closed formats?

→ Mainly open formats

D8.1 – If yes, how do you document your data?

→ Following established standards or protocols

→ Using controlled vocabularies

Base: 39 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The *Semantic Engineer / Data Architect* profile represents respondents who work with structured and interoperable cultural heritage data through the use of data

management tools, knowledge representation tools, open formats, established standards and controlled vocabularies.

This profile captures actors whose practices are oriented towards organising, documenting and aligning data in ways that support consistency, interoperability and reuse across different systems and datasets.

Overall, the profile reflects a technically oriented approach to data structuring and semantic organisation within cultural heritage environments.

Summary of findings

Tools and services

A large share of respondents report being involved in the development and design of digital tools and infrastructures. Nearly three quarters of respondents (74.4%) participate in the development of data management tools or infrastructures, indicating that this profile actively contributes not only to the use but also to the creation of digital environments.

Their level of involvement spans different stages of the development process. Around half of respondents act as project managers or coordinators (51.3%), while others contribute as occasional (41.0%) or frequent contributors (38.5%), and a smaller share is directly involved as primary developers (28.2%).

Their primary roles reflect a combination of conceptual, organisational and technical responsibilities. Many identify as concept designers (56.4%) or project managers (53.8%), while others contribute as data scientists (33.3%), developers (28.2%) or end-users involved in testing and feedback (35.9%). (Figure 11.1).

E3. What is your primary role in the development of such tools?	Count	%
Concept designer (e.g., defining objectives, features, or workflow)	22	56.4%
Project manager / coordinator (e.g., overseeing the development process)	21	53.8%
End-user / tester (e.g., using tools, providing requirements and feedback)	14	35.9%
Data scientist / analyst (e.g., integrating analysis needs into tool design)	13	33.3%
Developer / programmer (e.g., coding, scripting)	11	28.2%

Figure 11.1 Roles in the development of digital tools and services (E3).

These roles reflect a combination of strategic, conceptual and technical responsibilities, including coordination, system design, analytical integration and development activities.

The types of tools associated with this profile are diverse but generally oriented toward the management, interpretation and enrichment of cultural heritage data. Domain-specific tools are the most frequently reported (48.7%), followed by data enrichment tools (43.6%), data analysis tools (35.9%) and data interpretation tools (23.1%). Together, these results indicate that the technical activities of this profile are primarily directed

toward enabling structured data environments and supporting the integration and processing of complex cultural heritage datasets.

Documentation of data

Documentation practices within this profile are strongly oriented toward the use of structured semantic resources and controlled vocabularies. Respondents report relying on a wide range of vocabularies and authority systems to support the standardisation and interoperability of cultural heritage data (Figure 11.2).

International controlled vocabularies are among the most frequently cited resources, particularly the Getty vocabularies (AAT, TGN, ULAN) and VIAF, which together account for approximately 44% of the mentions. National authority files are also widely used (33%), including systems such as GND, BnF, LoC and IdRef.

D8.1. Which controlled vocabularies or semantic resources do you use?	Count	%
International controlled vocabularies (Getty AAT, TGN, ULAN, VIAF)	8	44.4%
National authority files (GND, BnF, LoC, IdRef)	6	33.3%
Domain-specific thesauri (PACTOLS, MIMO, Iconclass, RKD, TaDiRAH)	6	33.3%
Linked open data identifiers (Wikidata, Geonames, ORCID, ROR)	4	22.2%
Additional isolated vocabularies (e.g., Cairo Gazetteer, GBIF, TaDiRAH)	4	22.2%
Ontologies and metadata schemas (CIDOC CRM, NFDI ontologies, LIDO)	3	16.7%

Figure 11.2 Use of controlled vocabularies and semantic resources (D8.1).

Domain-specific thesauri are also widely used (33%), with respondents citing specialised resources such as PACTOLS, MIMO, Iconclass, RKD and TaDiRAH. These vocabularies support the disciplinary description and classification of cultural heritage materials across different subfields.

Ontological and semantic frameworks are also present, including models such as CIDOC CRM, NFDI ontologies and LIDO, although they appear less frequently (17%). In addition, several respondents refer to linked data ecosystems such as Wikidata, Geonames, ORCID and ROR (22%), indicating an active engagement with web-based identifier systems and semantic integration infrastructures.

Together, these results highlight the central role of controlled vocabularies and semantic standards in supporting the documentation and interoperability practices of this profile.

Data management and storage

Institutional data governance appears uneven within this profile. Around one third of respondents (36%) report that their institution follows a published Data Management Plan, while a larger share indicate that no such framework exists (44%), and about one fifth are uncertain (21%). This suggests that formal governance structures for data

management are not systematically established even among technically specialised professionals working on data modelling and integration (Figure 11.3).

D5. Do you have a Data Management Plan (DMP) for your projects?	Count	%
No	17	43.6%
Yes	14	35.9%
I don't know	8	20.5%

Figure 11.3 Use of Data Management Plans (D5).

Storage practices reveal a hybrid infrastructure combining institutional environments, local storage and repository or cloud-based solutions. Institutional servers represent the most prominent storage configuration, with roughly four fifths of respondents (79%) indicating that they store at least half of their data within organisation-managed infrastructures. Local storage also remains significant (49%), while domain-specific repositories (33%), self-hosted cloud environments (31%), generic open-access repositories (28%) and commercial cloud platforms (26%) appear as complementary environments rather than primary storage locations.

Overall, the storage landscape reflects a distributed but institutionally anchored infrastructure, where institutional servers remain central while repositories and cloud environments support integration, sharing and access.

Challenges

Data sharing and reuse are associated with several challenges. The most frequently reported issue concerns data or metadata quality, reliability and completeness (79.5%), followed by legal or contractual restrictions and intellectual property issues (69.2%) (Figure 11.4).

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data?	Count	%
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	31	79.5%
Legal or contractual restrictions, intellectual property rights / other legal issues	27	69.2%
Extra effort is required, lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	20	51.3%
Non-digital data, resource is not digitised	20	51.3%
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (including GDPR compliance when data refers to specific persons, e.g. archival material)	17	43.6%
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	13	33.3%
Technical barriers (e.g., difficulty accessing or using the required tools or platforms, large format files unable to be shared by common open means)	11	28.2%
Concerns about data misuse	10	25.6%
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	6	15.4%

Figure 11.4 Challenges in data sharing, consultation and reuse (D13).

A substantial proportion of respondents also report lack of time or resources required to prepare data for sharing (51.3%), as well as the presence of non-digital resources that are not yet digitised (51.3%). Concerns related to confidentiality or privacy (43.6%) and data misuse (25.6%) are also mentioned, while technical barriers related to accessing or sharing large files or specialised formats (28.2%) affect a smaller but still relevant portion of respondents. Overall, these results highlight how issues related to data quality, legal constraints and resource availability remain significant barriers to interoperability and cross-system reuse.

Needs & expectations

Semantic engineers express needs focused on managing complexity, ensuring interoperability and enabling scalable data integration processes.

The main challenges relate to technical and infrastructure limitations, together with interoperability issues and data heterogeneity. The integration of diverse datasets and the alignment of standards require significant effort, often compounded by limited resources and the need for specialised expertise. Documentation gaps and the complexity of tools also contribute to increasing the learning curve.

Expectations strongly emphasise improved interoperability and alignment with shared standards, alongside better support for collaboration and metadata harmonisation. There is also a clear demand for enhanced data management capabilities, including more efficient processing, linking and retrieval of data (*Figure 11.5*).

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved?	Count	%
Interoperability and integration between systems	8	47.1%
Collaboration, shared standards and metadata harmonisation	7	41.2%
Training, documentation and capacity building	5	29.4%
Automation, AI and advanced data processing functionalities	5	29.4%
Data management, search, retrieval and visualisation	5	29.4%
User-friendliness and simplified interfaces	4	23.5%
Data access, open repositories and sharing	4	23.5%
Organisational support, governance and sustainability	4	23.5%
Funding, affordability and cost reduction	3	17.6%
Infrastructure, storage and scalability enhancements	3	17.6%
Security, legal, ethical and licensing frameworks	3	17.6%
Vendor dependency, open solutions and tool sustainability	3	17.6%
Connectivity and offline functionality	1	5.9%

Figure 11.5 *Suggested improvements for digital tools and services (C3).*

Training and documentation remain important, particularly to support onboarding and the broader adoption of semantic technologies. Respondents also highlight the need for scalable infrastructures and more sustainable and open solutions. Advanced

functionalities such as automation and AI-based processing are considered relevant, but are framed within the need for robust, standardised and well-integrated systems

Institutional infrastructure & governance

Many respondents report being involved in the management of institutional data infrastructures. Around 64% of respondents report being involved in the management of their institution’s databases, servers or repositories, indicating that a substantial share of this group is directly engaged with the technical environments that support data storage and access.

The database environments managed by respondents are diverse. Relational databases represent the most common configuration (41%), followed by object-oriented databases (26%) and NoSQL systems (13%), while graph databases are reported by a smaller subset (8%). This diversity reflects the heterogeneous technical ecosystems in which cultural heritage data infrastructures operate, where multiple database architectures coexist depending on the nature of the data and the requirements of specific systems.

Semantic modelling practices are also present within this group. Around 31% of respondents report using ontological models, such as CIDOC CRM or related semantic frameworks, indicating an active engagement with structured knowledge representation approaches aimed at supporting interoperability and data integration.

Storage, archiving and curation practices further confirm this structured orientation. Metadata and documentation are the most frequently reported methods (53.8%), followed by backup and redundancy strategies (51.3%) and automation and scripting (48.7%). Collaboration with trusted repositories and the use of standardised practices and formats are both reported by 43.6% of respondents, highlighting the role of interoperability, preservation and long-term accessibility within this profile (*Figure 11.6*).

F4. What methods and systems do you use to store, archive and curate data within your organisation?	Count	%
Metadata and documentation (archiving data along with descriptive information, annotations, and contextual details for easier discovery and use)	21	53.8%
Backup and redundancy (creating duplicate copies of data for safety, stored across multiple locations to ensure resilience)	20	51.3%
Automation and scripting (using automated workflows and scripts to manage archiving tasks, including scheduled backups and data migration)	19	48.7%
Collaboration with trusted repositories (depositing data in recognised repositories or archives that ensure long-term preservation and accessibility)	17	43.6%
Standardised practices and formats (following established protocols and using standard file formats to ensure long-term data preservation and compatibility)	17	43.6%
Digital preservation platforms (employing specialised tools and systems designed for long-term digital preservation and compliance with archival standards)	14	35.9%
Local storage solutions (storing data on physical devices, such as external drives, NAS devices, or optical media)	14	35.9%

Cloud-based archiving (using cloud platforms for data storage, including general cloud services and dedicated archival solutions)	13	33.3%
Institutional or enterprise systems (archiving within organisational repositories or enterprise systems like research data centres and DAM/CMS platforms)	11	28.2%
Physical archiving (maintaining physical records or media, such as printed documents, microfilm, or magnetic tapes, in secure environments)	11	28.2%
Data tiering and lifecycle management (managing data by moving it between storage types based on usage, transitioning from active to archival storage over time)	7	17.9%
Periodic review and migration (regularly reviewing archived data for obsolescence and migrating to updated formats or systems to maintain usability over time)	5	12.8%
Encryption and security (protecting archived data through encryption and implementing strict access controls to ensure confidentiality and integrity)	3	7.7%

Figure 11.6 Data storage, archiving and curation methods (F4).

Overall, these results indicate that respondents in this profile are often positioned at the intersection between data modelling, infrastructure management and semantic standardisation, contributing to the design and maintenance of technical environments that enable structured and interoperable cultural heritage data systems.

Overall Conclusion

Semantic Engineers and Data Architects represent a technically specialised group focused on the modelling, structuring and integration of cultural heritage data environments. Their activities extend beyond the use of digital tools to include the design, coordination and implementation of infrastructures that enable structured data management and semantic interoperability across heterogeneous systems.

Respondents in this profile demonstrate strong engagement with semantic standards, controlled vocabularies and structured documentation practices, reflecting their central role in aligning datasets and enabling cross-system integration. At the same time, their work takes place within complex technical and organisational environments where issues related to data quality, legal frameworks and resource constraints continue to affect the effective circulation and reuse of cultural heritage data.

Overall, this profile illustrates the importance of technically specialised roles in supporting interoperable data ecosystems. By bridging data modelling, infrastructure management and semantic standardisation, these professionals contribute to the development of integrated data environments capable of supporting interoperability, long-term reuse and more coherent cultural heritage data ecosystems.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the relationship between vocabulary use (D8.1.1), data management planning (D5), and semantic structuring practices (F2.3) within the Semantic profile.

The objective is to assess how the use of controlled vocabularies – ranging from international standards to domain-specific thesauri and linked open data identifiers – aligns with the adoption of ontological models and formal data management frameworks.

Particular attention is given to whether engagement with semantic resources corresponds to more structured and formalised data practices, or whether these elements remain only partially integrated within broader data management and governance processes.

Controlled vocabularies (D8.1.1) × Use of ontological models (F2.3)

The cross-analysis between the use of controlled vocabularies and the adoption of ontological models reveals differentiated configurations across vocabulary types within the Semantic profile.

International controlled vocabularies show a relatively strong alignment with ontological structuring, with the majority of respondents reporting the use of ontological models. A similarly consistent pattern emerges for ontologies and metadata schemas, where the use of semantic resources is directly associated with the presence of ontological structuring (*Figure 11.7*).

Vocabularies (D8.1.1) × Semantic structuring (F2.3)	Yes	No	I don't know	Answered No to F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?
International controlled vocabularies Getty (AAT, TGN, ULAN), VIAF"	5	1	0	2
National authority files GND, BnF, LoC, IdRef"	2	2	1	1
Domain-specific thesauri PACTOLS, MIMO, Iconclass, RKD, TaDiRAH"	3	0	0	3
Ontologies and Ontologies and metadata schemas CIDOC CRM, NFDI ontologies, LIDO"	2	0	1	0
Linked open data identifiers Wikidata, Geonames, ORCID, ROR"	1	1	0	2
Additional isolated vocabularies were mentioned once (e.g., Cairo Gazetteer, GBIF, TaDiRAH)	0	1	1	2

Figure 11.7 Relationship between the use of controlled vocabularies (D8.1.1) and the use of ontological models (F2.3)

By contrast, national authority files display a highly distributed pattern across all response categories, including a notable presence of uncertainty. This suggests that their use does not systematically correspond to a clear level of semantic structuring.

Domain-specific thesauri exhibit a distinct split configuration. While a portion of respondents report the use of ontological models, an equally significant share corresponds to respondents not involved in database or repository management. This

indicates that such vocabularies are often used in operational contexts without being embedded in structured semantic infrastructures.

Linked open data identifiers show a more fragmented pattern, with limited alignment and a relatively high proportion of respondents not directly involved in data infrastructure management. A similar configuration is observed for isolated or less commonly used vocabularies.

Overall, the results indicate that the relationship between vocabulary use and semantic structuring is not uniform, but varies depending on the type of resource. Full alignment is observed primarily in explicitly ontology-driven environments, while other vocabulary types are associated with more heterogeneous or operationally oriented configurations.

Controlled vocabularies (D8.1.1) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between vocabulary use and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals a generally weak alignment between semantic practices and formal governance structures (*Figure 11.8*).

Vocabularies (D8.1.1) × DMP (D5)	Yes	No	I don't know
International controlled vocabularies Getty (AAT, TGN, ULAN), VIAF"	3	4	1
National authority files GND, BnF, LoC, IdRef"	2	4	0
Domain-specific thesauri PACTOLS, MIMO, Iconclass, RKD, TaDiRAH"	3	2	1
Ontologies and Ontologies and metadata schemas CIDOC CRM, NFDI ontologies, LIDO"	0	3	0
Linked open data identifiers Wikidata, Geonames, ORCID, ROR"	1	3	0
Additional isolated vocabularies were mentioned once (e.g., Cairo Gazetteer, GBIF, TaDiRAH)	1	3	0

Figure 11.8 Relationship between the use of controlled vocabularies (D8.1.1) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Across most vocabulary categories, the absence of a Data Management Plan is the dominant condition. This is particularly evident in the case of ontologies and metadata schemas, where all respondents report the absence of a formal DMP, despite engaging with highly structured semantic frameworks.

International controlled vocabularies and national authority files also show a prevalence of negative responses, indicating that the use of widely recognised semantic resources does not systematically correspond to the adoption of formal data management strategies.

A different pattern emerges for domain-specific thesauri, which represent the only category where the presence of a Data Management Plan is more frequent. This suggests that, in some cases, domain-driven practices may be more closely linked to formalised data management processes.

Linked open data identifiers and less common vocabularies display similarly weak associations with Data Management Plans, reinforcing the overall lack of alignment between semantic resource use and governance frameworks.

Overall, the results indicate that the adoption of controlled vocabularies, including advanced semantic resources, is not necessarily embedded within formal data management structures, highlighting a gap between technical practices and institutional governance.

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between the institutional presence of a Data Management Plan (D5) and the challenges encountered when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13).

The objective is to assess whether the presence of formal governance frameworks is associated with variations in the distribution of structural, legal and technical challenges within the Semantic profile.

Challenges (D13) × Data Management Plan (D5)

The cross-analysis between reported challenges and the presence of a Data Management Plan reveals no clear structural alignment between institutional governance and the difficulties encountered in data sharing, consultation and reuse (*Figure 11.9*).

Challenges (D13) x DMP (D5)			
	Yes	No	I don't know
Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	12	13	6
Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	6	10	1
Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	8	13	6
Concerns about data misuse	6	3	1
Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	7	9	4
Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	5	4	2
Non-digital data / resource not digitised	10	6	4
Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	3	7	3
Unclear guidelines regarding sharing	0	5	1

Figure 11.9 Relationship between the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13) and the presence of a Data Management Plan (D5)

Across most categories, the distribution of challenges remains comparable regardless of whether respondents report the presence or absence of a DMP. Core issues such as data quality, legal restrictions, and the effort required to prepare data for sharing show similar levels across governance conditions, indicating that these challenges are not substantially mitigated by formal data management frameworks.

In several cases, challenges appear even more concentrated among respondents reporting the absence of a DMP. This is particularly evident for issues related to unclear guidelines and lack of appropriate infrastructure, suggesting that institutional governance mechanisms do not consistently translate into clearer operational frameworks.

Some deviations from this general pattern can nevertheless be observed. Concerns related to data misuse show a clearer concentration among respondents reporting the presence of a Data Management Plan. A similar pattern is observed for the presence of non-digital data, which is more frequently reported by respondents with a DMP. Rather than indicating a reduction of these issues, these patterns suggest a higher level of awareness and recognition of data-related risks and lifecycle gaps in more structured governance environments.

Overall, the results suggest that the presence of a Data Management Plan does not significantly reshape the structure of challenges. Rather than reflecting differences in

governance maturity, the observed patterns point to the persistence of systemic constraints that are not fully addressed by formal institutional frameworks.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between storage infrastructures (D9) and the challenges encountered when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13).

The objective is to assess whether different storage configurations are associated with variations in the distribution and intensity of structural, legal and technical barriers within the Semantic profile.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Challenges (D13)

When analysed proportionally within each storage configuration, a stable hierarchy of challenges emerges across all environments.

In most cases, data or metadata quality represents the most prominent issue, followed by legal or contractual restrictions and the effort required to prepare data for sharing. This pattern remains consistent regardless of the storage solution adopted, indicating that core challenges are largely independent of infrastructural configurations.

Differences between storage types are limited and mainly affect secondary aspects. Repository-based environments show a lower proportional presence of challenges related to infrastructure and unclear guidelines, suggesting a more stable organisational context. Conversely, self-hosted solutions display relatively higher proportions of privacy and guideline-related concerns, reflecting the increased responsibility associated with locally managed infrastructures (*Figure 11.10*).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Challenges (D13)	Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness	Confidentiality or privacy concerns (incl. GDPR where data refer to persons)	Legal or contractual restrictions / intellectual property rights / other legal issues	Concerns about data misuse	Extra effort required / lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing	Technical barriers (e.g., access issues, required tools, large files hard to share)	Non-digital data / resource not digitised	Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing	Unclear guidelines regarding sharing
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	15	6	13	5	11	3	7	6	6
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	13	6	9	4	8	3	9	2	0
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	8	3	5	4	5	4	5	5	1
Institutional servers or websites	24	14	21	7	15	9	15	11	6
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	11	3	7	2	6	2	5	3	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	9	3	9	1	8	2	4	3	1
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	1
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	3	1	2	1	2	0	3	0	0
Self-hosted cloud servers (e.g. Nextcloud, OwnCloud)	8	7	9	4	6	2	2	2	5

Figure 11.10 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and the challenges faced when sharing, consulting or reusing data (D13)

Collaborative platforms exhibit a slightly more balanced distribution between data quality and legal issues, alongside a relatively strong weight of effort-related challenges, indicating a greater emphasis on coordination and data preparation. Cloud-based commercial platforms present a more even distribution of challenges, without a clearly dominant hierarchy.

Overall, the results suggest that storage infrastructures do not fundamentally alter the structure of challenges, but rather introduce moderate variations in the relative weight of specific issues.

Profile: Technical Developers

Key questions identifying the people belonging to this profile

D14 – What are your primary objectives when producing, consulting or reusing data?

→ → To develop or refine tools, algorithms or models for prediction or data interpretation, digital visualisation and representation of heritage

E1 – Are you involved in the development of data management tools or infrastructures?

→ → Yes

E2 – What is your level of involvement in the development of such tools?

→ Frequent contributor

→ Primary developer

E3 – What is your role in such projects?

→ Developer / programmer

→ Concept designer

→ Data scientist / analyst

Base: 77 respondents (completed questionnaires)

The Technical Developers profile represents respondents who are actively involved in the development of digital tools and technical solutions used in cultural heritage and data-related environments. These respondents contribute directly to the design, implementation or improvement of software, models and digital services.

They typically participate in the development of tools used for data analysis, digital representation or data processing, and may work as developers, concept designers or data scientists. Their work focuses on refining functionalities, improving technical performance and supporting the creation of digital infrastructures and analytical tools used in heritage-related workflows.

Overall, this profile reflects technically specialised actors who contribute to the development and evolution of digital tools supporting cultural heritage data practices.

Summary of findings

Tools development

The data show that respondents in this profile are actively involved in the development of a range of digital tools designed to support the analysis, interpretation and enhancement of cultural heritage data. The most commonly reported category consists of data analysis tools, developed or contributed to by 71.4% of respondents, highlighting the central role of computational approaches in exploring and processing heritage datasets (*Figure 12.1*).

E4. What are the types of tools?	Count	%
Data analysis tools	55	71.4%
Data enrichment tools	45	58.4%
Domain-specific tools	44	57.1%
Data interpretation tools	42	54.5%

Figure 12.1 *Types of tools used (E4).*

A similarly strong engagement emerges in the development of data enrichment tools, reported by 58.4% of respondents. These tools typically support the improvement, extension or integration of existing datasets, contributing to the enhancement of data quality and interoperability across digital heritage environments. Domain-specific tools

are also widely developed (57.1%), reflecting the need for specialised technological solutions tailored to the particular requirements of cultural heritage research and management.

In addition, more than half of respondents (54.5%) report contributing to data interpretation tools, which facilitate the exploration, contextualisation and understanding of complex datasets. Overall, these results indicate that Technical Developers play a key role in building and refining analytical, interpretative and domain-specific systems that enable more advanced forms of data processing and knowledge production in cultural heritage contexts.

Access models and authentication

Access to digital tools within this profile is largely characterised by open and institutionally supported environments (*Figure 12.2*).

The most widely reported access model consists of free, open-access services, used by 85.7% of respondents. Open-source software is also widely adopted (76.6%), indicating a strong engagement with openly available technological ecosystems. In addition, a substantial share of respondents report working with in-house or custom-built tools developed within their organisations (68.8%), reflecting the technical and development-oriented nature of this profile.

Other access models remain present but less dominant. Free tools with specific licensing conditions are reported by 48.1% of respondents, while paid licence-based services reach 33.8% and subscription-based services are used by 27.3%. More occasional models such as trial-based access (16.9%) and pay-per-use services (10.4%) appear comparatively marginal.

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?	Count	%
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	66	85.7%
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	59	76.6%
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	53	68.8%
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	37	48.1%
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	26	33.8%
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	21	27.3%
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	13	16.9%
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	8	10.4%

Figure 12.2 Access models used for digital tools and services (C4).

Authentication practices are primarily structured around institutional infrastructures. The most common method consists of institutional login systems, used by 77.9% of respondents, suggesting that access to digital services often occurs through organisational credentials. Other widely used authentication providers include Google accounts (50.6%), ORCID identifiers (42.9%), Microsoft accounts (37.7%), and other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions (31.2%), indicating a diversified authentication landscape across both institutional and organisational systems. More specialised or less frequent solutions include Eulogin (13.0%), Apple ID (11.7%), and EduGAIN (10.4%), while social login methods such as Facebook remain rare (2.6%).

Overall, these results indicate that Technical Developers operate within a hybrid access environment combining open technological ecosystems, internally developed tools and institutionally managed authentication systems that regulate access to digital infrastructures and services.

Data production

The software environments used by respondents in this profile reflect a strong orientation toward programming and computational development. The most widely reported category consists of programming and scripting environments, including languages such as Python, R or Java as well as custom scripts and in-house platforms, used by 51.3% of respondents. This highlights the central role of coding and scripting activities in the development and refinement of digital tools and data processing workflows.

Other software categories appear less dominant but still relevant for specific analytical or operational tasks. Office, content management and general-purpose digital tools are used by 23.1% of respondents, often supporting coordination, data handling or documentation activities alongside more specialised technical environments. Statistical and quantitative analysis software, such as SPSS, STATA or analytical uses of Excel, is reported by 20.5% of respondents (*Figure 12.3*).

D7.1. Which tools or software environments do you use for data processing and analysis?	Count	%
Programming and scripting environments (Python, R, Java, Perl, custom scripts, in-house platforms, semantic tools)	20	51.3%
Office, CMS and general-purpose digital tools (MS Office, Google Sheets, MediaWiki, Omeka, dashboards)	9	23.1%
Statistical and quantitative analysis software (SPSS, STATA, Matlab, Origin, Excel when used analytically)	8	20.5%
3D, imaging and AI-based processing tools (CloudCompare, Metashape, Blender, OCR/HTR tools, hyperspectral software)	6	15.4%
GIS and spatial analysis tools (QGIS, ArcGIS)	3	7.7%
Semantic web / graph DB / linked data tools (GraphDB, Neo4j, semantic web tools)	3	7.7%

Figure 12.3 Data processing and analysis tools (D7.1).

More specialised software environments are reported by smaller shares of respondents. 3D, imaging and AI-based processing tools, including platforms used for photogrammetry, visual processing or automated recognition, are mentioned by 15.4% of respondents. GIS and spatial analysis tools are used by 7.7%, while semantic web and graph database tools, such as GraphDB or Neo4j, are also reported by 7.7%.

Overall, these results indicate that Technical Developers primarily rely on programming environments and custom scripting workflows, complemented by a range of analytical and domain-specific tools that support the development, processing and interpretation of cultural heritage data.

Data management and storage

Storage practices within this profile are primarily structured around local environments and institutional infrastructures (*Figure 12.4*). A large majority of respondents report that most of their primary datasets are stored locally (71.4%), indicating that development workflows frequently rely on locally managed systems and environments.

Institutional servers or organisation-managed infrastructures also represent an important storage environment, with 61.1% of respondents reporting that most of their data are stored in these systems. Other storage environments appear more complementary. Commercial cloud platforms (33.8%), self-hosted cloud solutions (31.2%), and collaborative platforms such as GitHub or Wikidata (31.2%) are used for a substantial share of datasets but less frequently represent the primary storage environment.

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets)?	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part (50–75%)	True for all/most (76–100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	5 (6.5%)	17 (22.1%)	15 (19.5%)	40 (51.9%)
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	48 (62.3%)	17 (22.1%)	10 (13.0%)	2 (2.6%)
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	33 (42.9%)	33 (42.9%)	8 (10.4%)	3 (3.9%)
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	28 (36.4%)	23 (29.9%)	16 (20.8%)	10 (13.0%)
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	73 (94.8%)	3 (3.9%)	1 (1.3%)	0 (0.0%)
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	13 (16.9%)	17 (22.1%)	20 (26.0%)	27 (35.1%)
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	23 (29.9%)	30 (39.0%)	18 (23.4%)	6 (7.8%)
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	51 (66.2%)	22 (28.6%)	3 (3.9%)	1 (1.3%)

On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	33 (42.9%)	20 (26.0%)	12 (15.6%)	12 (15.6%)
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Figure 12.4 Primary data storage and archiving practices (D9).

Access to secondary datasets follows a similar pattern. Local environments again represent the most common access point, with 62.4% of respondents indicating that most reused datasets are accessed locally. Institutional servers also play a significant role, supporting access to a large share of reused data for 48.1% of respondents.

Taken together, these findings highlight that Technical Developers operate within hybrid infrastructures where locally managed systems and institutional environments form the backbone of both data storage and data access within development workflows.

Data sharing

Data sharing is a common practice within this profile, although it often occurs in a context-dependent manner (*Figure 12.5*). A majority of respondents report that they sometimes share their data (62.3%), indicating that sharing frequently depends on project conditions, institutional frameworks or the specific nature of the datasets involved.

A substantial share of respondents also report that they always share their data (36.4%), suggesting that open or collaborative data circulation is embedded in part of their workflows. Only a very small minority indicate that they do not share their data (1.3%).

These responses indicate that Technical Developers generally operate in environments where data sharing is widely practiced, although its regularity may vary depending on institutional policies, project requirements or technical constraints.

D10. Do you share your data with others?	Count	%
Yes, sometimes	48	62.3%
Yes, always	28	36.4%
No	1	1.3%

Figure 12.5 Data sharing practices (D10).

Needs and expectations

Technical users express needs focused on performance, scalability and the ability to manage complex and resource-intensive digital workflows.

The main challenges relate to technical and infrastructure limitations, together with interoperability issues and financial constraints (*Figure 12.6*). The need to process large volumes of data, integrate multiple systems and maintain efficient workflows places strong demands on hardware, computing capacity and system architecture. Skills gaps and training needs also remain relevant, particularly in relation to specialised tools and rapidly evolving technologies.

C2. What difficulties do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?	Count	%
Technical, infrastructure and hardware limitations	16	47.1%
Interoperability and system integration issues	15	44.1%
Financial constraints and costs	14	41.2%
Skills, training and learning curve	13	38.2%
Usability and user experience limitations	12	35.3%
Legal, copyright and data governance concerns	9	26.5%
Human resources and staffing constraints	9	26.5%
Data quality, heterogeneity and standardisation issues	8	23.5%
Connectivity and access limitations	8	23.5%
Vendor dependency, tool sustainability and support limitations	7	20.6%
Documentation, guidance and best practice gaps	7	20.6%
Data access and availability constraints	5	14.7%
Organisational and policy barriers	5	14.7%
Domain-specific limitations and lack of fit	4	11.8%

Figure 12.6 *Main difficulties in the use of digital tools and resources (C2).*

Usability issues and documentation gaps further affect efficiency, especially when tools are not designed with clear user workflows or require significant configuration and expertise to operate effectively. Organisational constraints and limited human resources also contribute to slowing down development and implementation processes.

In terms of expectations, respondents emphasise the need for improved interoperability and better integration between systems, supported by shared standards and more cohesive technical ecosystems. Training and documentation are considered important to support adoption and effective use, alongside more user-friendly interfaces.

There is also a clear demand for stronger infrastructure, scalable storage and computing capacity, as well as more sustainable and cost-effective solutions. Additional expectations include enhanced data management capabilities, support for advanced processing (including automation and AI), and greater alignment with collaborative standards and practices.

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the Technical Developers profile reflects professionals who are directly involved in the design and implementation of digital infrastructures and computational tools within cultural heritage environments. Their work is strongly oriented toward the development of analytical, interpretative and domain-specific systems that support the processing, enrichment and visualisation of heritage data.

The results also indicate that these respondents operate within hybrid technical environments combining local infrastructures, institutional systems and collaborative

development platforms. At the same time, their feedback highlights the importance of improving interoperability between systems, simplifying tool usability and strengthening shared technical standards.

Taken together, these findings portray a profile that plays a key role in shaping the technological backbone of digital heritage ecosystems, contributing both to the development of tools and to the technical backbone of digital heritage ecosystems, contributing both to the development of tools and to the technical infrastructures that support data processing, integration and reuse.

Comparative Analysis – Digital Maturity Block

This block examines the relationship between tools (D7.1), storage infrastructures (D9), data access environments (D16), and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether the technical environments used by Technical Developers are associated with more structured, distributed or consistent data practices, or whether these dimensions remain only partially aligned.

Software used (D7.1) × Where data are stored or archived (D9)

The cross-analysis between tools and storage infrastructures shows a consistent structural pattern across all categories, with limited but meaningful variations.

Across all tool types, local storage clearly represents the primary environment, followed by institutional infrastructures. This dual configuration emerges systematically, indicating that even among Technical Developers, data environments remain strongly anchored in locally managed and institutionally controlled systems (*Figure 12.7*).

Tools (D7.1) × Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%)	Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	Institutional servers or websites	Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	Social networks or forums (e.g. Research Gate)	Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites
"Statistical and Quantitative Analysis Software (SPSS, STATA, Matlab, Origin, Excel when used analytically)"	5	1	2	3	0	3	2	1	1
"Programming and Scripting Environments (Python, R, Java, Perl, custom scripts, in-house platforms, semantic tools)"	18	4	5	6	1	11	7	2	5
"GIS and Spatial Analysis Tools (QGIS, ArcGIS)"	3	1	1	1	0	2	1	0	1
"3D, Imaging and AI-based Processing Tools (CloudCompare, Metashape, Blender, OCR/HTR tools, hyperspectral software)"	5	1	1	1	0	4	1	0	2
Semantic web / Graph DB / Linked data (GraphDB, Neo4j Semantic web tools)	2	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	2
Office, CMS and General-purpose Digital Tools (MS Office, Google Sheets, MediaWiki, Omeka, dashboards)	4	1	1	2	0	3	1	1	1

Figure 12.7 Relationship between software used (D7.1) and where data are stored or archived (D9)

At the same time, differences emerge in the degree of diversification. Programming and scripting environments display the most distributed configuration, with a more balanced use of cloud platforms, collaborative environments and self-hosted solutions. This suggests a higher degree of infrastructural flexibility and technical adaptability.

By contrast, more specialised tool categories – particularly 3D/AI-based tools and semantic technologies – show a stronger concentration in institutional and self-hosted environments, with limited reliance on cloud-based or repository-based solutions. This indicates a preference for controlled and technically managed infrastructures, likely linked to performance, data sensitivity or system requirements.

Across all categories, domain-specific and public repositories remain marginal, and subscription-based platforms are almost entirely absent. Overall, the results suggest that storage practices are structured around stable core environments, with only moderate differentiation linked to the technical specificity of tools.

Software used (D7.1) × Where data are accessed (D16)

The cross-analysis between tools and data access environments reveals a pattern largely consistent with storage practices, with local and institutional environments again representing the primary points of access across all categories.

Across all tool types, access is predominantly local, followed by institutional infrastructures, confirming a stable and controlled configuration of data environments. Repository-based access remains secondary, while subscription-based platforms are almost entirely absent.

Programming and scripting environments display the most diversified access patterns, with a broader use of cloud-based platforms, collaborative environments and, to a lesser extent, social networks. This suggests a comparatively higher engagement with distributed and networked data ecosystems (*Figure 12.8*).

Tools (D7.1) × Data access (D16) (True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%))	Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	In domain-specific repositories (e.g., Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	In public archives or generic-purpose open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	On a cloud-based commercial platform (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	On institutional or private servers or websites (e.g., NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	Social networks or forums (e.g., Research Gate, Academia.edu)
"Statistical and Quantitative Analysis Software (SPSS, STATA, Matlab, Origin, Excel when used analytically)"	3	1	1	2	0	2	1	0
"Programming and Scripting Environments (Python, R, Java, Perl, custom scripts, in-house platforms, semantic tools)"	23	4	5	6	1	12	8	4
"GIS and Spatial Analysis Tools (QGIS, ArcGIS)"	2	1	1	1	0	2	1	0
"3D, Imaging and AI-based Processing Tools (CloudCompare, Metashape, Blender, OCR/HTR tools, hyperspectral software)"	4	1	1	1	0	3	1	0
Semantic web / Graph DB / Linked data (GraphDB, Neo4j Semantic web tools)	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
Office, CMS and General-purpose Digital Tools (MS Office, Google Sheets, MediaWiki, Omeka, dashboards)	3	1	1	2	0	2	1	0

Figure 12.8 Relationship between software used (D7.1) and where data are accessed (D16)

By contrast, more specialised tool categories – particularly 3D/AI tools and semantic technologies – show more concentrated access patterns, primarily relying on local and institutional infrastructures, with limited use of cloud-based environments. While these differences should be interpreted with some caution due to smaller absolute counts in certain categories, they nonetheless indicate a tendency toward more controlled and technically managed access conditions.

Overall, the results confirm that data access practices closely mirror storage configurations, with only moderate differentiation linked to the technical nature of tools.

Software used (D7.1) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between tools and data sharing practices shows a highly consistent pattern across all categories, with minimal variation in the regularity of sharing.

Across all tool types, “Yes, sometimes” represents the dominant modality, indicating that data sharing remains predominantly situational. At the same time, a substantial proportion of respondents report systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), suggesting a relatively strong overall propensity to share data within the profile.

Differences between tool categories are limited, with very similar distributions across all configurations. This indicates that the type of tools used does not significantly influence data sharing behaviours. Overall, sharing practices appear largely independent of the technical environments in which data are produced or processed (*Figure 12.9*).

Tools (D7.1) × Data sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
"Statistical and Quantitative Analysis Software (SPSS, STATA, Matlab, Origin, Excel when used analytically)"	2	3	0
"Programming and Scripting Environments (Python, R, Java, Perl, custom scripts, in-house platforms, semantic tools)"	12	21	0
"GIS and Spatial Analysis Tools (QGIS, ArcGIS)"	1	2	0
"3D, Imaging and AI-based Processing Tools (CloudCompare, Metashape, Blender, OCR/HTR tools, hyperspectral software)"	2	4	0
Semantic web / Graph DB / Linked data (GraphDB, Neo4j Semantic web tools)	1	1	0
Office, CMS and General-purpose Digital Tools (MS Office, Google Sheets, MediaWiki, Omeka, dashboards)	4	5	0

Figure 12.9 Relationship between software used (D7.1) and data sharing practices (D10)

Comparative Analysis – Governance

This block examines the relationship between access models (C4), authentication systems (C6), and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether governance and access control mechanisms are associated with variations in the regularity of data sharing, or whether sharing practices remain largely independent of these configurations

Access models (C4) × Sharing practices (D10)

The cross-analysis between access models and data sharing practices shows a highly consistent pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the regularity of sharing (*Figure 12.10*).

Across most access types, “Yes, sometimes” represents the dominant modality. At the same time, a substantial proportion of respondents report systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), suggesting a relatively strong overall propensity to share data within the profile.

Access (C4) x Sharing (D10)			
	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Free, open-access services (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)	27	38	1
Free with a license (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)	14	22	1
Trial-based access (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)	3	10	0
Paid subscription-based services (e.g., monthly or annual fees)	8	13	0
Paid licence-based services (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)	9	17	0
Pay-per-use / usage-based access (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)	6	2	0
Developed in-house or custom-built tools (e.g., software created by your organisation)	18	35	0
Open-source software (freely available to download, modify and distribute)	21	37	1

Figure 12.10 Relationship between access models (C4) and data sharing practices (D10)

Open, licensed, in-house and commercial configurations display very similar distributions, indicating that the type of access does not significantly influence sharing behaviours. While a few configurations show more extreme distributions, these are based on small numbers and should be interpreted with caution.

Overall, the results suggest that data sharing practices operate largely independently of access models, with only marginal variation across different configurations.

Authentication (C6) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between authentication methods and data sharing practices shows a consistent pattern across all configurations, with limited variation in the regularity of sharing.

Across most authentication systems, “Yes, sometimes” remains the dominant modality. At the same time, a substantial proportion of respondents report systematic sharing (“Yes, always”), confirming a relatively strong overall tendency to share data (Figure 12.11).

Authentication (C6) x Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
C6. How do you typically log in or authenticate when accessing digital tools and services? [Apple ID]	3	6	0
C6. EduGAIN	5	3	0
C6. Eulogin	2	8	0
C6. Facebook	2	0	0
C6. Google	12	26	1
C6. Institutional Login (log in using your organisation's credentials)	21	38	1
C6. Microsoft	6	22	1
C6. ORCID	14	19	0
C6. Other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO)	9	15	0

Figure 12.11 Relationship between authentication methods (C6) and data sharing practices (D10)

Widely used systems such as institutional logins, Google and Microsoft display very similar distributions, while variations observed in other configurations are either moderate or based on small numbers and should be interpreted with caution.

Overall, the results suggest that data sharing practices are largely independent of authentication systems, with no clear evidence that access or identity management mechanisms influence the consistency of sharing behaviours.

Comparative Analysis – Infrastructure

This block examines the relationship between storage infrastructures (D9) and data sharing practices (D10).

The objective is to assess whether different storage environments are associated with variations in the regularity of data sharing, and to identify whether specific infrastructures support more consistent sharing behaviours.

Where data are stored or archived (D9) × Sharing (D10)

The cross-analysis between storage infrastructures and data sharing practices shows a more differentiated pattern compared to governance-related configurations.

While “Yes, sometimes” remains the dominant modality across most storage environments, the proportion of systematic sharing (“Yes, always”) varies more substantially between configurations. Repository-based environments – both domain-specific and public – show a higher share of consistent sharing, suggesting that

infrastructures oriented toward dissemination are associated with more stable sharing behaviours (Figure 12.12).

Storage (D9) True for a large part (50–75%) & True for all/most (76–100%) × Sharing (D10)	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes	No
Local storage (PC, hard drive, USB)	20	35	0
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	7	4	1
Cloud-based commercial platforms (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox)	6	19	1
Institutional servers or websites	17	29	1
Public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	6	5	0
Collaborative platforms (e.g. GitHub, Wikidata)	10	13	1
Social networks or forums (e.g. ResearchGate)	1	3	0
Subscription-based platforms (e.g. JSTOR, ProQuest)	1	0	0
Self-hosted cloud servers or personal websites	6	17	1

Figure 12.12 Relationship between where data are stored or archived (D9) and data sharing practices (D10)

By contrast, cloud-based and self-hosted environments display a stronger concentration in the “sometimes” category, indicating more situational sharing practices. Local and institutional storage configurations occupy an intermediate position, with a more balanced distribution between systematic and occasional sharing.

Overall, the results suggest that storage infrastructures are more closely associated with sharing regularity than access or authentication models, particularly when they are explicitly oriented toward dissemination and reuse.

